

Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages

Workshop Proceedings

Working Group Chairs and Publication Editors

Francesco Gelati
Maroussia Bednarkiewicz
Françoise Gouzi
Alíz Horváth

Authors

Maroussia Bednarkiewicz (<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0445-6578>)
IE University (<https://ror.org/02jjdwm75>)

Emiliano Degl'Innocenti (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3839-9024>)
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – CNR (<https://ror.org/04zaypm56>)

Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9709-6392>)
University of Padua (<https://ror.org/00240q980>)

Francesco Gelati (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6066-1308>)
University of Hamburg (<https://ror.org/00g30e956>)

Till Grallert (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5739-8094>)
Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin (<https://ror.org/01hcx6992>)

Alíz Horváth (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9131-5504>)
Central European University (<https://ror.org/02zx40v98>)

Péter Király (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8749-4597>)
Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (<https://ror.org/00cd95c65>)

Francesco Pinna (<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-4925-3467>)
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – CNR

Alessia Spadi (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9670-3426>)
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – CNR

Federica Spinelli (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2195-3930>)
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – CNR

Georgios Vardakis (<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-3251-9356>)
University of Padua

Design

DARIAH ERIC, Sönke Rau and Francesco Gelati

Digital Object Identifier (DOI)

[10.5281/zenodo.17143727](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17143727)

Further Resources

More information about the workshop: <https://gitlab-ce.rz.uni-hamburg.de/uahh-digitale-dienste/creating-managing-and-archiving-textual-corpora>; <https://dariahopen.hypotheses.org/2024>.

Workflow “Building Textual Corpora for Under-resourced Languages”:
<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/67KJnp>.

Workflow “Managing Textual Corpora in under-resourced languages”:
<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/fbXfuH>.

Workflow “Archiving Textual Corpora”:
<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/gDzIoY>.

Workflow “Preparing minority or endangered language corpora for annotation in SIL FLEX”:
<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/MRkIZE>.

Suggested Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH)

[Digital humanities](#)

[Research--Data processing](#)

[Corpora \(Linguistics\)](#)

Funding

The workshop, its resulting workflows and proceedings were made possible by the DARIAH ERIC Funding Scheme for Working Group Activities 2023-25. The subsequent grant was administered by the University of Hamburg. Lead applicant was Francesco Gelati. Co-applicants were Alíz Horváth and Maroussia Bednarkiewicz. The workshop took place in Hamburg (Germany) from the 28th to the 30th of August 2024.

Editorial Note

The articles “Adding Every Arabic Periodical Published Before 1930 to Wikidata” by Till Grallert and “Creating a Scientific Workflow to Manage Old Italian Texts” by Emiliano Degl’Innocenti et al. were firstly published in *Transformations: A DARIAH Journal* (issue n.1, 2025).

Contact

multilingualdh@dariah.eu

wg-rdm@dariah.eu

License

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International ([CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/))

Printed by Universitätsdruckerei Hamburg, October 2025.

Table of Contents

M. Bednarkiewicz, F. Gelati, A. Horváth:

Creating Workflows for Building, Managing, and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages: Challenges, Approaches, and Lessons Learned 7

P. Király:

Multilingual Metadata Standards and Metrics Through Europeana 21

T. Grallert:

Adding Every Arabic Periodical Published Before 1930 to Wikidata 27

E. Degl'Innocenti, F. Pinna, A. Spadi, F. Spinelli:

Creating a Scientific Workflow to Manage Old Italian Texts 66

G. Vardakis, G. M. Di Nunzio:

Seeking Contact-Induced Syntactic Change in Endangered Languages: A Methodology for Building a Morphosyntactically Annotated Corpus for Corfioto 81

F. Gelati:

Archiving Textual Corpora: a Workflow and its Metadata 93

Creating Workflows for Building, Managing, and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages: Challenges, Approaches, and Lessons Learned

Authors¹

Maroussia Bednarkiewicz (IE University, <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0445-6578>)

Francesco Gelati (University of Hamburg, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6066-1308>)

Alíz Horváth (Central European University, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9131-5504>)

Keywords (EN)

Textual corpora; workflows; under-resourced languages; multilingualism; FAIR data.

Keywords (DE)

Textkorpora; Mehrsprachigkeit; Unterrepräsentierte Sprachen; FAIR-Prinzipien.

Abstract (EN)

The article describes the workshop “Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages”: its motivations, methods, challenges, and outcomes. The latter include four workflows, which are described here and have been published online in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace. The article also highlights the importance of having good, available, FAIR and CARE data for textual corpora in under-resourced languages throughout the entire lifecycle of the corpus, providing context and further perspectives.

Abstract (DE)

Der Beitrag stellt den Workshop „Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages“ vor: Methoden, Herausforderungen und Ergebnisse. Letztere umfassen vier Arbeitsabläufe, die im Artikel beschrieben werden, und die online im “Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace” sind. Betont wird überdies die Bedeutung guter, verfügbarer, FAIR- und CARE-konformer Daten für Textkorpora in unterrepräsentierten Sprachen während des gesamten Lebenszyklus des Textkorpus. Weiterhin werden der Kontext und künftige Perspektiven angesprochen.

¹ The authors contributed equally to this paper and are listed alphabetically.

Introduction

From the 28th to the 30th of August 2024, DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) working groups on Research Data Management and Multilingual Digital Humanities joined their forces to organise a hybrid workshop, supported by the DARIAH Working Groups Funding Call 2023-25.² The aim was to develop workflows describing the main steps for the creation, management, and archiving of multilingual corpora.³ A diverse crowd of practitioners with background in research data management, digital humanities (DH), computational linguistics, library science, and research software engineering⁴ came to Hamburg in Germany or joined the event online to share their expertise and solutions to the many challenges faced by those who want to build digital corpora for under-represented languages. After two days of presentations and exchanges, the participants prepared on the last third day four workflows that have been published in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace,⁵ promoting and enabling the sharing of methodologies and best practices when compiling FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)⁶ and machine-readable corpora.⁷

Motivation and Importance of Multilingual Digital Humanities

Text analysis is central in the humanities, and building textual corpora is often one of the first steps in most digital humanities projects. The more data can be included in the corpus, the more new perspectives can be explored. In addition, the quantity of data also influences the quality of most computational analysis, especially when machine learning is involved.⁸ Because

²<https://www.dariah.eu/2024/04/03/dariah-working-groups-funding-call-2023-meet-the-winning-projects/> [Retrieved, like all the following web-addresses, on 31st October, 2024].

³ Regarding our choice of terminology and the use of ‘multilingualism’, we follow here the practice of Viola, L., & Spence, P. (Eds.). (2023). *Multilingual Digital Humanities* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003393696>, see in particular the introduction, p. 4.

⁴ We would like to express our special thanks to our participants who contributed to the workshop in person or online: Françoise Gouzi, Martin Wynne, Péter Király, Cristina Vertan, Shih-Pei Chen, Calvin Yeh, Alexander König, Aleksandr Riaposov, Alexandre Arkhipov, Jonas Müller-Laackman, Gardy Stein, Elena Lazarenko, Till Grallert, Nanette Rißler-Pipka, Monika Xenia Kudela, Paul Spence, Femmy Admiraal, Alessia Spadi, Emiliano Degl’Innocenti, Georgios Vardakis, Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio, and Duncan Paterson. Our special thanks go as well to Merve Tekgürler, co-chair of the ADHO Multilingual DH SIG and one of the workshop presenters, for their thoughtful contribution to the conceptualization of the workshop.

⁵ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/search?categories=workflow&order=label>.

⁶ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship”. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

⁷ Gouzi, F. (16 September 2024). Workflows for Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages. *DARIAH Open*. <https://doi.org/10.58079/12b2b>.

⁸ We will not go into detail about the machine learning side and refer to the extended discussion in Fekete, M. R., et al. “Typological Challenges for the Application of Multilingual Language Models in the Digital Humanities.” In Viola, L., & Spence, P. (Eds.). (2023). *Multilingual Digital Humanities* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003393696>, pp. 148.

scholarly and industrial attention has been given predominantly to English⁹, and more particularly the modern English of social media,¹⁰ most digital corpora, methods, and tools for the pre- and post-processing of textual data have often not been adapted to other languages and scripts¹¹. The relevant existing scholarship has also pointed out the severe lack of tools that could reliably help extract multilingual and non-English data, which results in the uneven representation or even absence of digital data available for these languages.¹² This is also a problem because the lack of digital visibility relegates these languages and scripts to a neglected

⁹ See Horvath A., van Lit C., Wagner C. & Wrisley D. “Towards Multilingually Enabled Digital Knowledge Infrastructures – A Qualitative Survey Analysis” In: Viola, Lorella and Paul Spence, eds. *Multilingual Digital Humanities*. Routledge. (2024): 197-212. DOI: [10.4324/9781003393696-17](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003393696-17). Fiormonte D.. 2021. “Taxation against Overrepresentation? The Consequences of Monolingualism for Digital Humanities.” In *Alternative Historiographies of the Digital Humanities* edited by Dorothy Kim and Adeline Koh, 333–376. Santa Barbara: Punctum Books.; Ghorbaninejad, M., Gibson N.P., and Wrisley D.J. 2023. “Right-to-Left (RTL) Text: Digital Humanists plus Half a Billion Users.” In *Debates in the Digital Humanities 2023* edited by Matthew K. Gold and Lauren Klein, 47–73. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.; Grallert, T. 2022. “Open Arabic Periodical Editions: A Framework for Bootstrapped Scholarly Editions Outside the Global North.” *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 16(2). ; Horvath A. 2022. “Digital Brush Talk: Challenges and Potential Connections in East Asian Digital Research.” In *Global Debates in the Digital Humanities*, edited by Domenico Fiormonte, Sukanta Chaudhuri, and Paola Ricaurte, 127–140. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.; Horváth A., van Lit C., Wagner C., and Wrisley D.J. 2024. “Centring Multilingual Users: Thinking through UX Personas in the DH Community,” in “DH Unbound 2022, Selected Papers,” ed. Barbara Bordalejo, Roopika Risam, and Emmanuel Château-Dutier, special issue. *Digital Studies/Le champ numérique* 13(3): 1–30.; Kirmizialtin S and Wrisley D.J. 2022. “Automated Transcription of Non-Latin Script Periodicals: A Case Study in the Ottoman Turkish Print Archive.” *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 16(2).

¹⁰ Of course, we are aware that English is not one and has multiple variations which can present different levels of challenges in the context of DH - creole English presents a case in point as Setsuko Yokoyama pointed out as part of a mini-conference on multilingual DH, co-organized by the ADHO Multilingual DH Special Interest Group and the DARIAH Multilingual DH Working Group under the auspices of the DH2024 conference in Washington DC.

¹¹ As an example of an excellent English-speaking digital corpus which has no equivalent, to the authors' knowledge, in other languages, see the Princeton Prosody Archive: <https://prosody.princeton.edu/>. In addition, the platform Lanfrica (<https://lanfrica.com/>) aims to collect datasets in various African languages to enhance their visibility and accessibility. In many ways, Ctext.org, initiated by Donald Sturgeon, also has a similar goal by providing the machine readable version of (mostly) classical Chinese historical and philosophical texts, accompanied by additional tools for the users to help digitally analyze the texts directly on the site. At the same time, similarly structured and holistic initiatives are still relatively rare, and many languages are under- or unevenly represented in the broader DH landscape or are represented through individual or scattered datasets. .

¹² See Dombrowski Q. & Burns P. “Language Is Not a Default Setting: Countering DH’s English Problem” In Gold M.K. & Klein L.F. (Eds) (2023). *Debates in the Digital Humanities*. University of Minnesota Press. <https://dhdebates.gc.cuny.edu/read/debates-in-the-digital-humanities-2023/section/704fd8ae-99f1-4bfc-a275-7f5ad88b48af>; Horvath A. “Digital Brush Talk: Challenges and Potential Connections in East Asian Digital Research.” In: Fiormonte D., Ricaurte Quijano P. & Chaudhuri S., (Eds.) *Global Debates in the Digital Humanities*. University of Minnesota Press. (2022): 127-140.; Spence, P. and Brandao R. “Towards Language Sensitivity and Diversity in the Digital Humanities.” *Digital Studies/Le champ numérique* (2021) 11(1): 9, pp. 1–29. DOI: [10.16995/dscn.8098](https://doi.org/10.16995/dscn.8098); Gil A. & Ortega É. “Global Outlooks in Digital Humanities: Multilingual Practices and Minimal Computing.” *Doing Digital Humanities: Practice, Training, Research*. Crompton C. Lane R. J., Siemens R. (Eds.) (2016) Routledge. 22-34.; Horvath A., van Lit C., Wagner C. & Wrisley D. “Towards Multilingually Enabled Digital Knowledge Infrastructures – A Survey Analysis” In: Viola, Lorella and Paul Spence, eds. *Multilingual Digital Humanities*. Routledge. (2024): 197-212.; Horvath A., van Lit C., Wagner C. & Wrisley D. “Centering Multilingual Users: Thinking through UX Personas in the DH Community.” *Digital Studies/Le champ numérique* (2024) in “DH Unbound 2022, Selected Papers,” eds. Bordalejo B., Risam R., & Château-Dutier E. 13(3): 1–30.. <https://doi.org/10.16995/dscn.9608>; Malínek V., Umerle T., Gray E., Heibi I., Király P., Klaes C., Korytkowski P., Lindemann D., Moretti A., Panušková C., Péter R., Tolonen M., Tomczyńska A., Vimr O. “Open Bibliographical Data Workflows and the Multilinguality Challenge”, *Journal of Open Humanities Data* (2024) 10:27, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.190>

status, reducing the likelihood of them becoming the focus of tool development, which further strengthens their marginalisation, creating a sort of vicious circle. A narrow form of English is thus over-represented, while most other languages fall in the background. This downward spiral does not facilitate linguistic diversity and inclusion and does not represent the rich linguistic diversity that exists in the non-digital world. The workshop addressed this gap by focusing on multilingual DH, emphasising the importance of creating equitable and accessible digital resources for all languages.

Moreover, the workshop aimed to further develop on the topic of research data management for multilingual data, as it was tackled in a nutshell by the DARIAH Working Group on Research Data Management in one previous research project¹³, mainly pursuing two research axes: data quality¹⁴ and standardisation¹⁵ of textual corpora. Finally, the workshop wanted to facilitate exchange and cross-fertilisation of expertise between Europe’s two main research infrastructures for humanities, thanks to the presence of specialist researchers from both DARIAH¹⁶ and CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure).¹⁷

Focus on Under-Represented Languages: A word on our terminology

A key lesson learned during the workshop was the importance of nuance in the wording that we utilised when referring to our target languages. This led us to often refer to “under-represented languages”, rather than “under-resourced” or “non-English”, to include the languages that are marginalised but not necessarily under-resourced, such as Chinese, and various forms of English that deviate from the mainstream English. By including these diverse linguistic forms, the workshop aimed to broaden the scope of digital humanities and ensure a more inclusive representation of global linguistic diversity.

¹³ See Buelinckx E., Gelati F. & Király P., “3.2. Challenges in multilingualism” in E. Tóth-Czifra et al., ‘Research Data Management for Arts and Humanities: Integrating Voices of the Community’ (DARIAH, 30 August 2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8059626> or https://gitlab-ce.rz.uni-hamburg.de/uahh-digitale-dienste/rdm-for-arts-and-humanities/-/blob/master/part-03.md?ref_type=heads#32-challenges-in-multilingualism.

¹⁴ See: Király P., ‘Measuring Metadata Quality’ (Göttingen: Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Doctoral Thesis, 2019), <https://doi.org/10.53846/goediss-7578>.

¹⁵ See: Mattern E., ‘The Linguistic Data Life Cycle, Sustainability of Data, and Principles of Solid Data Management’, in *The Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management*, ed. Andrea L. Berez-Kroeker et al. (Cambridge Mass.: The MIT Press, 2022), 61–72, <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12200.003.0009>.

¹⁶ About the functioning and the goals of DARIAH, see Edmond J. et al., ‘9. Springing the Floor for a Different Kind of Dance: Building DARIAH as a Twenty-First-Century Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities’, in Eadem (Ed.), *Digital Technology and the Practices of Humanities Research* (Cambridge, UK: Open Book Publishers, 2020), 207–34, <https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0192.09>.

¹⁷ About the functioning and the goals of CLARIN, see: Fišer D. and Witt A. (Eds.), *CLARIN: The Infrastructure for Language Resources* (De Gruyter, 2022), <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110767377>.

While we include all under-represented languages, we took care to consider the particular challenges faced by under-resourced languages. These languages often lack the necessary digital resources and infrastructure, and this lacuna makes it difficult for those working with them to create comprehensive digital corpora. The workshop addressed these challenges by developing workflows that are adaptable to different linguistic contexts, providing a framework that can be tailored to the specific needs of each language. The workflows also serve as a guideline for institutions to make sure they provide the necessary support (financial and technical) to create sustainable corpora for under-represented and, in particular, under-resourced languages. Without targeted institutional support, these languages that are off the radar of the industry and mainstream funding cannot occupy their place in the digital landscape.

Challenges in Corpus Creation for Under-Represented Languages

Creating, managing, and archiving corpora for under-represented languages involve unique challenges that the workshop revealed in detail. These languages often lack the digital infrastructure and resources that are readily available for more widely spoken languages. Some of the key challenges, which repeatedly appeared throughout the presentations at the workshop, include the following:

- **Data Scarcity:** As Alíz Horváth pointed out in her “un-keynote keynote speech”¹⁸ on the first day of the workshop, there is often a lack of digitised (i.e. OCR’ed and HTR’ed) texts available for these languages, which makes corpus creation difficult. This problem often stems from the lack of available, accessible, and well-functioning text recognition tools, which forces scholars to handle an exceedingly high amount of manual corrections in the output. This may result in the delayed launch of DH projects in under-represented languages or may even cause scholars to abandon their project idea due to the excessive amount of necessary pre-processing work. It is thus clear that corpus building begins with and requires effective text recognition methods.
- **Linguistic Diversity:** Many under-represented languages have numerous dialects and variations (also depending on the period when the texts were produced) and may use non-Latin scripts, which need to be accurately represented in digital corpora and, as Péter Király’s talk also emphasised, relevant multilingual metadata standards.¹⁹

¹⁸ Alíz Horváth’s “unkeynote keynote speech” titled “What is a Corpus/Data/Workflow in a Multilingual Context? Why a Workflow for Non-English Sources? Rationale Behind the Workshop” took place on day 1 of the workshop (28 August 2024).

¹⁹ Péter Király’s presentation, “Multilingual Metadata Standards and Metrics through Europeana,” was part of the panel on “Metadata, Corpus Building” on day 1 (28 August 2024).

Projects, such as Closing the Gap in non-Latin script data and LoGaRT (Local Gazetteers Research Tools for classical Chinese) introduced by Xenia Kudela, as well as Shih-Pei Chen and Calvin Yeh respectively, aim to remedy this problem aim to remedy this problem. The former collects data on non-Latin-script-based (particularly Arabic) digital projects, whereas the latter offers a comprehensive platform to access, analyse, and visualise digitised premodern Chinese local gazetteers.²⁰

- **Technical Limitations:** The presentations of Cristina Vertan and Alessia Spadi and Emiliano Degl’Innocenti both explored innovative tools (such as VLO - Virtual Language Observatory²¹ and RESTORE - smaRt accESs TO digital heRitage and mEmory²²) for corpus processing that can also handle multiple languages.²³ On the other hand, existing digital tools and software may not support the scripts or linguistic features of these languages, necessitating the development of new tools or the adaptation of existing ones. An added issue here, as Till Grallert and Merve Tekgürler also pointed out in their respective presentations, often stems from the relative lack of support, which forces scholars to take up the heavy task of attempting to overcome obstacles on their own.²⁴
- **Cultural Sensitivity:** Care (as well as the CARE principles: Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and Ethics)²⁵ must be taken to respect the cultural and historical contexts of these languages, especially when they are tied to indigenous or marginalised communities.²⁶ These points were also addressed by the presentations of Aleksandr Riaposov and Alexandre Arkhipov on managing corpora in minority

²⁰ These presentations also allowed us to gain a more holistic view on how the complex process of corpus building and management operates in the context of concrete case studies. The talks were held as part of the panel “Putting it all together” on day 2 of the workshop: “Closing the Gap in non-Latin script data” by Xenia Kudela (who substituted Jonas Müller-Laackman) and “LoGaRT - Local Gazetteers Research Tools for classical Chinese” presented by Shih-Pei Chen and Calvin Yeh (29 August 2024).

²¹ See: <https://vlo.clarin.eu/>.

²² See: <http://restore.ovi.cnr.it/>.

²³ Cristina Vertan’s talk “Corpus-Processing with CLARIN Tools,” and the presentation by Alessia Spadi and Emiliano Degl’Innocenti on “Tools for Corpus Processing” were included in the initial panel on day 2, titled “Corpus Processing”. (29 August 2024).

²⁴ These presentations were held on day 1 of the workshop in the panel on “Metadata, Corpus Building”: “Corpus Building from Open, Collaborative and Scholarly Digital Editions” by Till Grallert and “An Ottoman Corpus: How to Think of Existing Materials as Data” by Merve Tekgürler (28 August 2024).

²⁵ See: Carroll, S, et al. 2020. “The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance”. *Data Science Journal*, 19: XX, pp. 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-042>. See also: <https://www.gida-global.org/care>.

²⁶ On how the long-term research project “INEL – Grammatiken, Korpora und Sprachtechnologie für indigene nordeurasische Sprachen” tackled issues like cultural sensitivity, responsibility and ethics see: Ferger, A., “Processing Language Resources of Under-Resourced and Endangered Languages for the Generation of Augmentative Alternative Communication Boards” in *Proceedings of the 12th Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2020)*, p. 2644-2648, <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lrec-1.322.pdf>.

languages and that of Georgios Vardakis and Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio on the linguistic aspects of annotated corpus creation for Corfioto.²⁷

- **Assessments:** When deciding whether to develop new tools or adapt existing ones, scholars should ideally be able to compare the results, but the absence of benchmarks prevents them from assessing the potential improvement, and the same is true for assessing a new tool developed for an under-represented language.
- **Funding:** Under-represented languages are often under-resourced and need special attention from institutions that are not profit-driven.
- **Sustainability:** The lack of funding also affects the sustainability of the work with under-resourced languages, which cannot always be stored or preserved in the long term²⁸. Relevant talks by Francesco Gelati on aspects to consider regarding archiving corpora, particularly from the perspective of research data management, as well as Alexander König's talk on depositing corpora within the CLARIN framework both offered valuable insights, which inspired the third workflow on Archiving Textual Corpora.²⁹

Methodology

Our workshop provided a platform for practitioners from diverse backgrounds to share their expertise and solutions in tackling the challenges mentioned above. Over the course of two and a half days, participants engaged in discussions and hands-on sessions that culminated in the creation of four comprehensive workflows. To ensure the success of our workshop, we adopted the following four main methodological strategies:

- **Participants' diversity:** We gathered specialists with a wide range of backgrounds. This interdisciplinary approach ensures that various perspectives and expertise are represented, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and potential solutions.
- **Challenges identification:** We dedicated a significant portion of the workshop to discussing the challenges that we had identified. Allowing ample time for presentations

²⁷ These presentations took place on day 2 within the framework of the panel on “Managing Minority and Endangered Language Corpora”: “Workflows for Managing Digital Corpora of Minority Languages” by Aleksandr Riaposov and Alexandre Arkhipov and “Seeking Contact-Induced Syntactic Change in Endangered Languages: A Methodology for Building a Morphosyntactically Annotated Corpus for Corfioto” by Georgios Vardakis and Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio. (29 August 2024)

²⁸ See Gelati, F. “Archiving Textual Corpora: a Workflow and its Metadata” in these same proceedings.

²⁹ These presentations concluded the program before the collaborative writing sprint and took place on day 3 as part of the panel “Corpora Archiving”: “Archiving Textual Corpora” by Francesco Gelati and “Depositing Corpora within CLARIN” by Alexander König. (30 August 2024)

and discussions on these topics supported the participants in the development of the reflection and the tools needed to address these challenges.

- Collaborative writing sessions and concrete outcomes: The final session transformed discussions into practical outputs through structured collaborative writing sessions, which led the participants to transform their ideas and discussions into practical tools.
- Open access, FAIR and CARE: All workflows adhere to FAIR and CARE principles, creating technically robust corpora that respect data origins while promoting global accessibility. Their open access further guarantees the broad dissemination of methodologies and best practices, facilitates the contribution to a growing repository of knowledge for researchers worldwide, and participates in advancing the field of multilingual digital humanities.

Workshop Outcomes and Contributions

The success of the workshop can be measured *inter alia* through the openly accessible publication of the four workflows in the SSH Open Marketplace:

Building Textual Corpora for Under-resourced Languages:

<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/67KJnp>

Managing Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages:

<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/fbXfuH>

Archiving Textual Corpora: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/gDzIoY>

Preparing minority or endangered language corpora for annotation in SIL FLEx:

<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/MRkIZE>

These workflows are designed to guide researchers through the process of creating, managing, and archiving corpora in any language, ensuring adherence to both the FAIR and CARE principles. The workflows contribute to addressing the conspicuous absence of pedagogical materials for computer-based textual examination in under-represented languages.³⁰ The FAIR principles are well-established guidelines that ensure data is managed in a way that maximises its usability and accessibility. In the context of multilingual and under-represented languages, it is equally important to consider the CARE principles, which emphasise the need to respect the rights and interests of the communities from which the data originates, ensuring that the data management practices do not exploit or marginalise these communities but instead

³⁰ For more inspiring examples see the review provided in Goodale, I. “Pedagogy and Praxis in Libraries: Natural Language Processing for Non-English Texts.” In: Viola, L., & Spence, P. (Eds.). (2023). *Multilingual Digital Humanities* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003393696>, pp. 104.

contribute to their empowerment and benefit. With the open-access workflows that we have created, we directly apply and enhance the ‘be FAIR and take CARE’ approaches to digital data management.

Based upon the abundance of aspects to consider during the process of building, managing, and archiving textual corpora, we have decided to produce multiple workflows corresponding to the major stages of the procedure - and also the overarching structure of the workshop which began with an extensive introduction to the interface and functionalities of the SSH Open Marketplace (with Alexander König as our guide),³¹ and multiple panels with presentations on corpus creation on day 1, followed by further lively panels on corpus management and archiving on day 2, culminating in a collaborative workflow writing sprint in small groups on day 3. Each panel and the extensive discussion sections afterwards concentrated not only on the question of “What?”, that is the nature of the individual projects that the participants had created, but, equally importantly, on the “How?”, referring to the practical steps they took to create their projects and the lessons learned throughout the journey. All this was meant to help us collect all relevant points at the end of each day as inspirations and workable case studies to be utilised during the compilation of the workflows.

The first two workflows cover the creation and the management of textual corpora for under-resourced languages. They specifically address the issues at stake when resources are lacking to build a digital corpus that is accurate, accessible, as well as sustainably curated and maintained: this explains why aspects such as OCR (Optical Character Recognition)-related issues, data quality, metadata standards, licensing, and ethics play a key role in both workflows. In many ways, the steps mentioned in the workflows apply to any language. At the same time, we aimed to take into account the persistent discrepancies in the outcome of the digitization process, which often shows lower accuracy for non-Latin scripts. This can be witnessed, for example, in the inclusion of a separate step on "Character encoding" to draw the readers' attention to potential issues that can occur in this process. The third workflow on archiving digital corpora focuses on the sustainable preservation of digitised textual materials and guides the users towards platforms, on which academic corpora can be stored together with their metadata and documentation. The last workflow is a guide to prepare minority or endangered

³¹ We decided to place this introduction at the beginning of the workshop in order to orient the participants' attention to the nature of the platform where the workshop deliverables would be published so we could collectively take that into account as we listened to and discussed the presentations and subsequently formulated the structure of the workflows.

language corpora for annotation in SIL FLEx (Fieldworks Standard Format Interlinear).³² Since many under-represented languages have little digitally available data, the ability to add audio files can greatly improve the size and hence the quality of a corpus. In eight steps, or less, this workflow shows how to include such files, whether as audio files or as transcripts, in a corpus, to enhance its scope and representativity.

Further Outcome and Perspective

A corpus is the initial and indispensable step in the whole digital pipeline that leads to computational text analysis. It depends on the digitisation of raw materials, the post-processing and cleaning of the digitisation outcome, which should be aimed at or allow further text processing and analysis. The most crucial takeaway from the event was related to the sheer diversity of the participants themselves, underscoring the benefits of having practitioners from different expertise, areas of interest, and linguistic backgrounds attend the workshop. This has showcased the importance of how solutions to their own issues could be applied in other fields and languages and thus preventing scarce resources from being wasted to often simply reinvent the wheel.³³ The workshop was, in other words, a living example of a minimal computing approach, where only essential technological solutions were developed. While the workflows have been the tangible outcomes of the workshop, the presentations, upon which they are based, the discussions that followed them, and the collaborative writing sprint at the end were necessary for us to be able to collectively produce such concise, but elaborate, workflows in half a day.

Since resources (time, digitised materials, funding, personnel) are often the most important limiting factor for under-represented languages, the format of the workshop, as much as its outcomes, can serve as a basis for similar initiatives in the future.

Funding

This article results from the research project "Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages". The project was conceived by DARIAH Working Groups Research Data Management and Multilingual DH and financed by the DARIAH-ERIC Funding Scheme for Working Group Activities 2023-25. The subsequent grant was

³² See <https://software.sil.org/fieldworks/> [Retrieved 14 November 2024].

³³ See the slides of Till Grallert that were presented during the workshop and were made available by the author at <https://openarabicpe.github.io/slides/2024-dariah/#/title-slide> [Retrieved 9 November 2024].

administered by the University of Hamburg. Lead applicant was Francesco Gelati (he/him). Co-applicants were Alíz Horváth and Maroussia Bednarkiewicz.

Bibliography

Buelinckx, Erik, Francesco Gelati, and Péter Király. 2023. “3.2. Challenges in Multilingualism.” In *Research Data Management for Arts and Humanities: Integrating Voices of the Community*, edited by Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Marta Błaszczńska, and Francesco Gelati. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8059626>

Carroll, Stephanie Russo, Ibrahim Garba, Oscar L. Figueroa-Rodríguez, Jarita Holbrook, Raymond Lovett, Simeon Materechera, Mark Parsons, et al. 2020. “The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance.” *Data Science Journal* 19 (November): 43, <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>

Dombrowski, Quinn, and Patrick J. Burns. 2023. “Language Is Not a Default Setting: Countering DH’s English Problem.” In *Debates in the Digital Humanities 2023*, edited by Matthew K. Gold and Lauren F. Klein, vol. 9. *Debates in the Digital Humanities*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, <https://doi.org/10.5749/9781452969565>

Edmond, Jennifer, Toma Tasovac, Frank Fischer, and Laurent Romary. 2020. “9. Springing the Floor for a Different Kind of Dance: Building DARIAH as a Twenty-First-Century Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities.” In *Digital Technology and the Practices of Humanities Research*, 1st ed., edited by Jennifer Edmond, 207–34. Cambridge, UK: Open Book Publishers, <https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0192.09>

Ferger, Anne. 2020. “Processing Language Resources of Under-Resourced and Endangered Languages for the Generation of Augmentative Alternative Communication Boards.” In *Proceedings of the Twelfth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation*, edited by Nicoletta Calzolari, Frédéric Béchet, Philippe Blache, Khalid Choukri, Christopher Cieri, Thierry Declerck, Sara Goggi, Hitoshi Isahara, Bente Maegaard, Joseph Mariani, Hélène Mazo, Asuncion Moreno, Jan Odijk, and Stelios Piperidis, 2644–48. Paris: The European Language Resources Association (ELRA), <https://www.aclweb.org/anthology/2020.lrec-1.322.pdf>

Fiormonte, Domenico. 2021. "Taxation against Overrepresentation? The Consequences of Monolingualism for Digital Humanities." In *Alternative Historiographies of the Digital Humanities*, edited by Dorothy Kim and Adeline Koh, 333–76, https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/319/oa_edited_volume/book/84502

Fišer, Darja, and Andreas Witt, eds. 2022. CLARIN: The Infrastructure for Language Resources. De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110767377>

Gelati, Francesco. 2024. "Archiving Textual Corpora: A Workflow and Its Metadata." Preprint, Zenodo, November 11, <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14082423>

Ghorbaninejad, Masoud; Gibson, Nathan P.; and Wrisley, David Joseph. 2023. "Right-to-Left (RTL) Text: Digital Humanists Plus Half a Billion Users." In *Debates in the Digital Humanities 2023*, edited by Matthew K. Gold and Lauren F. Klein, vol. 9. *Debates in the Digital Humanities*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, <https://doi.org/10.5749/9781452969565>

Gil, Alex, and Élika Ortega. 2016. "Global Outlooks in Digital Humanities: Multilingual Practices and Minimal Computing." In *Doing Digital Humanities: Practice, Training, Research*, edited by Constance Crompton, Richard Lane, Ray Siemens. Routledge, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315707860>

Gouzi, Françoise. 2024. *Workflows for Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-Resourced Languages*. September 16, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.58079/12B2B>

Grallert, Till. 2022. "Open Arabic Periodical Editions: A Framework for Bootstrapped Scholarly Editions Outside the Global North." *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 016 (2), <https://dhq.digitalhumanities.org/vol/16/2/000593/000593.html>

Horváth, Alíz. 2022. "Digital Brush Talk: Challenges and Potential Connections in East Asian Digital Research." In *Global Debates in the Digital Humanities*, edited by Paola Ricaurte, Sukanta Chaudhuri, and Domenico Fiormonte, 127–40. University of Minnesota Press, https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/23/oa_edited_volume/chapter/3144060

Horváth, Alíz, Cornelis Van Lit, Cosima Wagner, and David Joseph Wrisley. 2023. "Towards Multilingually Enabled Digital Knowledge Infrastructures." In *Multilingual Digital Humanities*, 1st ed., by Lorella Viola and Paul Spence, 197–212. London: Routledge, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003393696-17>

- . 2024. “Centring Multilingual Users: Thinking through UX Personas in the DH Community.” *Digital Studies / Le Champ Numérique* 13 (3), <https://doi.org/10.16995/dscn.9608>
- Király, Péter. 2019. “Measuring Metadata Quality.” Georg-August-University Göttingen. <https://doi.org/10.53846/goediss-7578>
- Kirmizialtin, Suphan, and David Joseph Wrisley. 2022. “Automated Transcription of Non-Latin Script Periodicals: A Case Study in the Ottoman Turkish Print Archive.” *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 016 (2), <https://dhq.digitalhumanities.org/vol/16/2/000577/000577.html>
- Malínek, Vojtěch, Tomasz Umerle, Edward Gray, Ivan Heibi, Péter Király, Christiane Klaes, Przemysław Korytkowski, et al. 2024. “Open Bibliographical Data Workflows and the Multilinguality Challenge.” *Journal of Open Humanities Data* 10 (March): 27, <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.190>
- Mattern, Eleanor. 2022. “The Linguistic Data Life Cycle, Sustainability of Data, and Principles of Solid Data Management.” In *The Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management*, edited by Andrea L. Berez-Kroeker, Bradley McDonnell, Eve Koller, and Lauren B. Collister, 61–72. The MIT Press, <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12200.003.0009>
- Riedel, Nico, Miriam Kip, and Evgeny Bobrov. 2020. “ODDPub – a Text-Mining Algorithm to Detect Data Sharing in Biomedical Publications.” *Data Science Journal* 19 (1): 42, <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-042>
- Spence, Paul Joseph, and Renata Brandao. 2021. “Towards Language Sensitivity and Diversity in the Digital Humanities.” *Digital Studies / Le Champ Numérique* 11 (1), <https://doi.org/10.16995/dscn.8098>
- Viola, Lorella, and Paul Spence. 2023. *Multilingual Digital Humanities*. 1st ed. London: Routledge, <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003393696>
- Wilkinson Mark D. et al., “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship,” *Scientific Data* 3, no. 1 (March 2016): 160018, <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Sitography

Grallert T. “Do It Yourself, Keep It Simple, and There Will Be a Future.” Github.io, 28 August 2024, <https://openarabicpe.github.io/slides/2024-dariah/#/title-slide> (Accessed 14 November 2024, like all other websites)

Papaki, E. “DARIAH Working Groups Funding Call 2023-2025: Meet the Winning Projects | DARIAH.” *Dariah.eu*, 2024, <https://www.dariah.eu/2024/04/03/dariah-working-groups-funding-call-2023-meet-the-winning-projects/>

“Archiving Textual Corpora | Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace.” Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace, 2024, <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/gDzIoY>

“Building Textual Corpora for Under-Resourced Languages | Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace.” Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace, 2024, <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/67KJnp>

Global Indigenous Data Alliance. “CARE Principles of Indigenous Data Governance.” Global Indigenous Data Alliance, <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

“Home - FieldWorks - FieldWorks.” Software.sil.org, 2024, <https://software.sil.org/fieldworks/>

“Managing Textual Corpora in Under-Resourced Languages | Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace.” Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace, 2024, <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/fbXfuH>

“Preparing Minority or Endangered Language Corpora for Annotation in SIL FLEx | Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace.” Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace, 2024, <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/MRkIZE>

“Search | Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace.” *Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace*, 2020, <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/search?categories=workflow&order=label>

Multilingual Metadata Standards and Metrics Through Europeana

Author

Péter Király¹

To understand the role of multilinguality in metadata, and specifically in Europeana's metadata, let's check a good example, an excerpt of an EDM metadata record (EDM stands for Europeana Data Model, this is the name of Europeana's metadata schema that describes the objects found in the database):

dc:title:

- "Die Mauer muß weg!"@de
- "Die Mauer muß weg! (The Wall must go!)"@en

dc:description:

- "Kommentiertes Fotorama mit Bildern von 1989-1990 in Berlin"@de
- "Annotated images from 1989-1990 in Berlin"@en

Place/skos:prefLabel:

- "Brandenburger Tor"@de; "Brandenburg Gate"@en
- "Grenzübergang Potsdamer Platz"@de; "Postdamer Platz border crossing"@en
- "Reichstag"@de; "Reichstag building"@en

We show here three properties of a metadata record, title, description and preferred label of places. We use the RDF notation, where a string is inside quotes, and the language of the string is denoted by the ISO 639 language code attached to the string with the '@' character. Usually the title and description are unique for each individual object – these are called descriptive fields. The values of the last property, the preferred place name (from the family of contextual fields, that provide a larger context to objects) however usually come from dictionaries. Not surprisingly Europeana prefers multilingual dictionaries. In this example all three properties have multiple values, a German and an English version (translations of each other), so the object can be interpreted (and searchable, accessible) in two languages.

One can imagine that it is more difficult to make descriptive properties multilingual, since they are unique, so it requires more (and not repeatable) work. On the other hand contextual fields are 'low hanging fruits', multilingual versions are already available for several conceptual domains.

How do data end up in Europeana's user interfaces? Behind the service there is a two level data aggregation workflow. The data are genuinely curated by 'data providers', i.e. more than

¹ This text is a summary of research conducted together with Juliane Stiller.

3000 cultural heritage organisations – galleries, libraries, archives, museums (frequently abbreviated as GLAM or LAM sector). The data they send to Europeana are metadata that describe their collections (such as paintings, books, photos) in whole or in part. They send metadata records to national, regional, domain or thematic ‘data aggregators’ that “gather authentic, trustworthy and robust data and make it accessible through Europeana”,² such as The European Film Gateway (for films), Manuscriptorium (for manuscripts), German Digital Library (for German metadata).

Europeana collects metadata from these platforms (or in exceptional cases directly from data providers). During the ingestion process the original metadata records are transformed and enriched. Each cultural heritage domain has its own standard metadata schema or schemas, such as Dublin Core, LIDO, EAD, MARC, EDM, the localised/customised versions of these. Sometimes they even use some custom, non standard schemas.

Data aggregators might have criteria regarding the ingested data, for example they might accept only records in particular schemas, or those that match even lower level data quality requirements (such as every record should have a machine readable unique identifier). Both data providers and aggregators might transform the data to EDM. In Europeana’s ingestion workflow there are built-in processes to transform records (if needed) and enhance them with contextual information.

The EDM schema enables separation of concerns: the information added by Europeana are clearly separable from those provided by the data provider. EDM defines two entity types for the descriptive fields: provider Proxy and Europeana Proxy. They have identical structure, but they separate the provenance of information. Most of the enhancements come from semantic sources, usually well known and carefully curated multilingual knowledge organisation systems, and they are stored in contextual entities, such as Agent, Concept, Place or Timespan. Of course data providers can also create these entities.

When we talk about multilingual values or a property we can make distinction between four different scenarios. We have texts without any language annotation, such as the subject “*Germany*”. Here a human mind can recognize that it is in English, but there is no formal annotation, so we cannot automatically use this information when the user wants to use some

² Europeana Aggregators Forum <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/aggregators>

language related feature of the service such as selecting only English subjects. The next level is when the property has a language annotation, for example in the case of subject:

“Germany”@en. Here we know that the literal value is in English, but it is still monolingual. It becomes multilingual if we have multiple values in different languages, such as *subject*: “Germany”@en, “Deutschland”@de.

The best approach is when the subject comes from a multilingual dictionary, and the service can fetch not only the different translations, but additional properties, such as synonyms, or broader and narrower terms (in case of concepts), dates (in case of personal names), coordinates (in case of place names) and others.

Here is a fictional example (we use RDF notation):

```
<#record> a ore:Proxy ; edm:europenaProxy false ;
  dc:subject "Ballet", "Opera" .

<#record> a ore:Proxy ; edm:europenaProxy true ;
  dc:subject <http://data.europeana.eu/concept/base/264>
    , <http://data.europeana.eu/concept/base/247> .

<http://data.europeana.eu/concept/base/264> a skos:Concept ;
  skos:prefLabel "Ballett"@no, "बैले"@hi, "Ballett"@de, "Балет"@be, "Балет"@ru,
  "Balé"@pt, "Балет"@bg, "Baletas"@lt, "Balet"@hr, "Balets"@lv .

<http://data.europeana.eu/concept/base/247> a skos:Concept ;
  skos:prefLabel "Opera"@no, "ओपेरा (गीतिनाटक)"@hi, "Oper"@de, "Ooppera"@fi,
  "Onepa"@be, "Onepa"@ru, "Ópera"@pt, "Onepa"@bg, "Opera"@lt .
```

The first dc:subject is a non-multilingual set, this is what comes from the ingestion pipeline. The second set is the result of the enhancement process that takes the two subjects, identifies them in a multilingual dictionary, and generates *Concept* entries in the records that are multilingual. They have unique identifiers (in the form of dereferenceable URIs) and preferred labels in several languages.

This language annotation can be expressed not only in RDF, but in JSON or XML. Here are some examples that can be retrieved via different Europeana interfaces:

```
"dcCreator": {
  "nl": ["Stichting Xeno-canto voor Natuurgeluiden"]
}

"dcCreator": [
```

```
{"@lang": "nl", "#value": "Stichting Xeno-canto voor Natuurgeluiden"}
]
```

```
<dc:creator xml:lang="nl">
  Stichting Xeno-canto voor Natuurgeluiden
</dc:creator>
```

```
<dc:language>nl</dc:language>
<dc:creator>Stichting Xeno-canto voor Natuurgeluiden</dc:creator>
```

Note: the xml:lang attribute was initiated by the recently passed C. M. Sperberg-McQueen.

It is worth to mention some of the multilingual vocabularies Europeana prefers, and recommends to be used by the data providers, and aggregators:

Vocabulary name	Base URL	Languages supported by the vocabulary
The Getty - Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)	vocab.getty.edu/aat	Multilingual: English, Spanish, Dutch, German, Italian, French, Swedish, Chinese (written in Traditional and Simplified scripts etc.)
Virtual International Authority File (VIAF)	viaf.org/viaf	Multilingual
Geonames	sws.geonames.org	Multilingual
Iconclass	iconclass.org	Multilingual
UNESCO Thesaurus	vocabularies.unesco.org/browser/thesaurus/en/	English, French, Spanish, Russian, Arabic

Multilinguality is not (yet) implemented perfectly. At the time of writing we get a different number of records for a query expressed in different languages: “Mona Lisa” returns 588 results, while “La Gioconda” returns 437 and “La Joconde” 65 results – all including different variations of the famous painting from the Louvre, and of course other objects holding the same.

Sometimes records have multilingual entities, but improperly annotated, such in the following example:

```
"edmConceptLabel":[
  {"def":"Leinwand"},
  {"def":"Malerei"},
  {"def":"Kangas"},
  {"def":"Maalaustaide"},
  {"def":"Холст"},
  {"def":"Живопись"},
  {"def":"Vászon"},
  {"def":"Festőművészet"}
]
```

Here “def” means the default language that is given instead of the individual language codes. Another problem is that here two different concepts (painting and canvas) are merged into a single entity. Sometimes another issue has occurred: different codes are used for the same language (e.g. *en*, *eng* and *ENG* for English).

How can we measure the saturation, i.e. which records or collections are more (or less) multilingual than others? Within the Europeana Data Quality Committee we introduced four metrics that can be measured in an automated manner. These are

- the number of literals tagged with language code
- the number of distinct language tags
- the number of tagged literals per language tag (often this is equivalent with the number of synonyms)
- the average number of languages per property for which there is at least one language-tagged literal

Measurements showed that multilinguality is not evenly distributed across data providers. At a time the records from the National Library Portugal had low multilingual saturation, while the records from the Wittgenstein Archives at the University of Bergen were on the other end of the scale with high saturation. We implemented a dashboard where the data providers, aggregators, and Europeana could check these values, and based on that they could form a strategy on how to improve the multilingual aspects of their own records.

Literature

Juliane Stiller, and Péter Király. “Multilinguality of Metadata Measuring the Multilingual Degree of Europeana’s Metadata.” In M. Gäde, V. Trkulja, V. Petras (Eds.): Everything Changes, Everything Stays the Same? Understanding Information Spaces. Proceedings of the 15th International Symposium of Information Science (ISI 2017), Berlin, 13th—15th March 2017. Glückstadt: Verlag Werner Hülsbusch, pp. 164—176. http://isi2017.ib.hu-berlin.de/ISI_17_ONLINE_FINAL.pdf

Valentine Charles, Juliane Stiller, Péter Király, Werner Bailer, and Nuno Freire. “Data Quality Assessment in Europeana: Metrics for Multilinguality.” In Joint Proceedings of the 1st Workshop on Temporal Dynamics in Digital Libraries (TDDL 2017), the (Meta)-Data Quality Workshop (MDQual 2017) and the Workshop on Modeling Societal Future (Futurity 2017) (TDDL MDQual Futurity 2017) co-located with 21st International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPLD 2017) (Grand Hotel Palace, Thessaloniki, Greece, 21 September 2017), edited by A. Caputo, N. Kanhabua, P. Basile, S. Lawless, D. Gavrilis, Ch. Papatheodorou, D. Trandabat. (CEUR Workshop Proceedings Volume 2038. ISSN 1613-0073.), Published by CEUR, 2018. <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2038/paper6.pdf>

Péter Király, Juliane Stiller, Valentine Charles, Werner Bailer, and Nuno Freire. “Evaluating Data Quality in Europeana: Metrics for Multilinguality.” In Metadata and Semantic Research 2019. 12th International Conference, MTSR 2018, Limassol, Cyprus, October 23-26, 2018, Revised Selected Papers (Communications in Computer and Information Science, volume 846) Springer, 2019. pp. 199–211. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-14401-2_19

Sarah Fallert. “Multilinguale Herausforderungen in der Sacherschließung.” Master’s thesis, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, 2020. <https://edoc.hu-berlin.de/handle/18452/22048>

Julie Shi, Mike Nason, Marco Tullney, and Juan Alperin. “Identifying Metadata Quality Issues Across Cultures.” *College & Research Libraries* 86:1 (2025) p. 101-134. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.86.1.101>

Dennis Donathan II, Mike Nason, Marco Tullney, Julie Shi, Juan Pablo Alperin. “Evaluating Multilingual Metadata Quality in Crossref” arxiv, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2503.11853>

Adding Every Arabic Periodical Published Before 1930 to Wikidata

Moving the Scholarly Crowdsourcing Project Jarā'id to the Digital Commons

Till Grallert

Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin
NFDI4Memory

Transformations, A DARIAH Journal

Volume 1, 2025

<https://transformations.episciences.org>

Dates

Received: 14/11/2024

Accepted: 22/04/2025

Published: 23/07/2025

DOI: [10.46298/transformations.14749](https://doi.org/10.46298/transformations.14749)

© The authors

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
International

Abstract

This paper documents the contribution of comprehensive bibliographic data on all Arabic periodicals published before 1930 to Wikidata, the largest public and open knowledge graph. The dataset originated with the scholarly crowdsourcing project Jarā'id and comprises information on more than 3,000 periodicals, about 2,700 editors and almost 350 holding institutions. As a living union list of Arabic periodicals, the dataset alleviates the infrastructural weaknesses of library catalogues and discovery systems, as well as the epistemic violence of knowledge ecologies. The move to Wikidata addresses the socio-technical shortcomings of our original approach by making the dataset available in a FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and five-star Linked Open Data environment. In addition, the platform provides multilingual interfaces and robust user management and version control, which significantly improves the usability and maintenance of evolving datasets. The paper details workflows and data models and demonstrates the reusability of our approach in other contexts with a second dataset of periodicals from the Ottoman Empire. Finally, the paper shows how the move to Wikidata generates continuous engagement with wider Wikimedia communities that significantly broaden our knowledge about periodicals and their holdings.

Keywords: Linked Open Data, Wikidata, periodical studies, Arabic periodicals, bibliographic data

إضافة جميع الصحف العربية الصادرة قبل سنة ١٩٣٠م إلى ويكي بيانات
انتقال مشروع المصادر الجماعية الأكاديمية
"جرائد" إلى المشاع الرقمي

يوثق هذا البحث مساهمة البيانات الجغرافية الشاملة لجميع الدوريات العربية المنشورة حتى عام ١٩٣٠ في ويكي بيانات (Wikidata)، أكبر رسم بياني معرفي حر ومفتوح. نشأت مجموعة البيانات من مشروع "جرائد" لتعميد المعلومات الشاملة الجماعي عن تاريخ الصحافة العربية وتتضمن معلومات عن أكثر من ٣٠٠٠ دورية، وحوالي ٢٧٠٠ محرر، وما يقرب من ٣٥٠ مكتبة وأرشيف ومجموعات أخرى. باعتبارها قائمة اتحادية حية للدوريات العربية، تعالج مجموعة البيانات نقاط الضعف الهيكلية لفهارس المكتبة، وأنظمة الاكتشاف بالإضافة إلى العنف المعرفي للنظم البيئية للمعرفة. تتناول الخطوة نحو ويكي بيانات أوجه القصور الاجتماعية والتقنية في نهجنا الأصلي عن طريق جعل مجموعة البيانات متاحة بشكل عادل وفي بيئة بيانات مفتوحة مرتبطة بخمسة نجوم. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، توفر المنصة واجهات متعددة اللغات وإدارة مستخدمين قوية وتحكم الإصدارات مما يحسن بشكل كبير قابلية الاستخدام وصيانة مجموعات البيانات المتطورة. يفصل البحث سير العمل ونماذج البيانات ويظهر إمكانية إعادة استخدام نهجنا في سياقات أخرى باستخدام مجموعة بيانات ثانية للدوريات من الدولة العثمانية ونشرت باللغة التركية العثمانية. وأخيراً يوضح البحث كيف أن الانتقال إلى ويكي بيانات يؤدي إلى مشاركة مستمرة مع مجتمعات الويكي الأوسع والتي توسع بشكل كبير معرفتنا بالدوريات ومقتنياتها في مكتبات

Keywords in Arabic: البيانات مفتوحة مرتبطة، ويكي بيانات، دراسات الدوريات، الصحافة العربية، بيانات بليوجرافية

Data availability statement

Data and code are available under free and open licences:

1. Snapshot of the Arabic periodicals dataset from Wikidata: Grallert (2024a).
2. XSLT for mapping TEI/XML to custom XML of the Wikidata data model: Grallert (2024b).
3. JSON schemas for the upload from OpenRefine to Wikidata: Grallert (2025c).
4. SPARQLqueries: Grallert (2025d).

Introduction

Imagine there was a discovery system that allowed a historian to query for all sources written or published in a specific geographic region around a particular period, identifying those that still survive in libraries or archives—or even better, those that have been digitised and are available online. Wouldn't that be wonderful? As a social historian interested in collective action in the Eastern Mediterranean, I would not have to dig through finding aids, media histories or union catalogues to establish a list of contemporary newspapers that might have reported on a series of food riots across the cities and towns of what is now Palestine, Lebanon, Syria and Israel during the summer of 1910, only to then discover through lengthy communications with colleagues and knowledge-preservation institutions around the globe that no copies could be found of what ought to be there.

This is not just a dream. In the following, I argue that all the components for such a discovery system are readily available and free to use for everyone with the means to access the internet. Against the backdrop of two datasets of bibliographic metadata on almost 4,000 Arabic and Ottoman periodicals, including more than 2,700 editors and almost 350 holding institutions, this article documents the motivation, workflows and data models for contributing such information to [Wikidata](#) as the core of such a discovery system.

The problem

Scholars and prospective readers of periodicals depend on the interfaces of discovery systems for finding and locating materials of interest. Contrary to common perceptions of networked information systems, it is surprisingly difficult to locate copies of periodicals (cf. Gaskelle 2017). This is due to a combination of factors. Firstly, such systems frequently do not allow for browsing based on the criteria outlined above. Instead, they focus on keyword search as an entry point into collections (cf. LeBlanc 2024; Zaagsma 2023; Sherratt 2019; Milligan 2019). Secondly, aggregators such as [OCLC's WorldCat](#) or the [German Zeitschriften Datenbank \(German Union Catalogue of Serials, ZDB\)](#) gather and present cataloguing data of varying quality and depth as they are provided by libraries and other holding institutions at regional, national and transnational levels. Thirdly, catalogues in turn should be considered living artefacts of socio-technical infrastructures with myriads of historical layers of knowledge production and organisation. They depend on the knowledge and skills of their cataloguers and are limited by ever-changing technical affordances, resulting in all sorts of hacks and (what we would now consider) errors. Comprehensive bibliographies or union lists and catalogues of all published works in a given language or genre can fill the gaps between what is found in catalogues and what was published and therefore might have survived in some collection.

But they are prohibitively expensive to produce and maintain, even for a finite number of publications.

This lack of (available) knowledge is particularly relevant for the first mass media of Arabic-speaking communities around the globe. Early Arabic magazines and journals, such as Butrus al-Bustani's *الجنان* (*al-Jinān*, Beirut, 1876–1886), Ya'qub Sarruf, Faris Nimr and Shahin Makariyus's *المقتطف* (*al-Muqtaṭaf*, Beirut and Cairo, 1876–1952), Muhammad Kurd 'Ali's *المقتبس* (*al-Muqtabas*, Cairo and Damascus, 1906–1918/1919) or Rashid Rida's *المنار* (*al-Manār*, Cairo, 1898–1941) were formative forums for a transnational Arabic public sphere, emanating and debating everything from modern science and Islamic reform to foreign literature, the Arabic (cultural) renaissance (*nahḍa*), socialism or the role of women, and coining a new Arabic terminology in the process. Being able to go beyond the small number of well-known titles from Cairo and Beirut will allow us to actually engage with them as an ideosphere spanning communities between Jakarta, Baghdad, Khartoum and Rio de Janeiro, while each of the thousands of Arabic newspapers could be invaluable sources for local microhistories.

In the following, I introduce our dataset of Arabic periodicals and discuss the strengths and weaknesses of our original approach, which, although based on minimal computing, relied on custom implementations that made it hard to maintain and did not reach users beyond a small academic community (section 2). I then discuss [Wikidata](#) as a platform that addresses the socio-technical shortcomings of our original approach by making the dataset available in a FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and five-star Linked Open Data environment with multilingual interfaces, robust user management and version control, and a vibrant community of contributors (section 3). Section 4 details data models, tools and workflows for contributing bibliographic data to Wikidata. The results section (section 5) situates the contribution in the larger context of periodical data on Wikidata and introduces practical use cases for research projects and GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives and museums) institutions for the dataset based on the results of various SPARQL queries. I also demonstrate the general reusability of the data models and workflows with a second dataset of some 700 Ottoman periodicals. The final discussion (section 6) focuses on the experiences within the first year of the initial contribution to Wikidata and how the dataset evolved through the efforts of other Wikidata users and bots.

Project Jarā'id

[Jarā'id: A Chronology of Arabic Periodicals \(1800–1929\)](#) is an ongoing scholarly crowdsourcing effort to address the shortcomings of supposedly comprehensive (printed) histories (e.g. Tarrazi 1913–1914, 1933; an electronic text was only

published recently: Tarrazi 2023; Ayalon 1995) by compiling a digital, and thus searchable, union list of all Arabic periodicals published before 1930. It was initiated by Adam Mestyan in the early 2010s and I have been involved in the project as one of its main contributors and lead on data modelling and first iterations of the website since 2012. Starting from a modest table of a few hundred titles in a Microsoft Word document, Jarā'id has grown into a catalogue with more than 3,200 entries, recording bibliographic data and, more importantly, holding information in original scripts and Latin transcription (titles, editors, publishers, places of publication, date of first issue and publication languages). Dozens of scholars have contributed information based on their own research in libraries and private collections worldwide. As well as being the only comprehensive union list of such material, Jarā'id is the only one that can be searched and browsed in the original script.

Datasets

There are currently two versions of the Project Jarā'id dataset.

1. The original dataset was published in tabular form as TEI/XML (TEI Consortium 2020) on [GitHub](#) and [Zenodo](#). We additionally generated multiple iterations of static websites from this dataset, which served as the main interface for users (Mestyan, Grallert, et al. 2020; Mestyan and Grallert 2012–2015, 2020).
2. I significantly expanded the original dataset and data model in semantically richer formats based on TEI `<biblStruct>` nodes. This enriched dataset is based on my research in periodicals, archives and, more recently, library catalogues and digital facsimile collections, such as [HathiTrust](#), the [ZDB](#) and Lebanese libraries like the American University of Beirut (AUB), Université Saint-Esprit de Kaslik (USEK) and Université Saint-Joseph (USJ) in Beirut, based on public APIs (Application Programming Interfaces), web scraping and personal collaborations with library staff (see Grallert 2022).¹

It is the latter dataset I published to Wikidata and will discuss below.

Data model

Periodicals are somewhat difficult to model as they are socio-technical assemblages: in other words, groups of people using various technologies and tools to publish (meaning to compose, print and distribute) a collection of texts from various genres under a shared title and with a fixed frequency. What ends up in collections are material artefacts—individual copies of specific periodical issues. As material artefacts, these are easy to record and model. But as scholars

1. I especially thank Elie Kahale (AUB) for his support.

interested in periodicals as a historical phenomenon and a source documenting historical events, we are concerned with the larger assemblage, whose parts, including publication titles and places can, and frequently do, change over time (cf. Gaskelle 2017).

Identifying and delineating the assemblage poses some challenges. Sometimes, continued publication—the fundamental periodicity of periodicals—was more of an aspirational claim than a reality. The medical journal الطيب (*al-Ṭabīb*), for instance, was originally published as أخبار طبية (*Akḥbār Ṭibbiyya*) in Beirut by George Post, and edited by John Wortabet and William van Dyck, in January 1874. In May that year, they changed the title to الطيب (*al-Ṭabīb*). Publication ceased in 1876. The journal was revived in 1881 with Shahin Makariyus, a well-known journalist and prolific editor, as a manager. Publication was stopped in 1882 due to controversies over Darwin’s theory of evolution, and Makariyus left Beirut for Cairo.² الطيب (*al-Ṭabīb*) resumed publication with a new volume count in March 1884 and came to yet another halt in 1885. The journal reappeared after a 10-year hiatus until its final demise with the outbreak of World War I (Sa’di and Sarton 1938).³ There are good arguments for cataloguing this journal as either a single periodical, five individual titles or a combination thereof. Holding libraries of the full publication run, such as AUB and USJ, chose the former, while others took the volume count starting in 1884 as a clue to the journal’s start date.

In contemporaneous sources, periodicals were identified by their titles and, if necessary, places of publication. The same is true for the ruling authorities, with whom publishers had to apply or register their planned endeavours in most jurisdictions.⁴ We therefore assume, as do most catalogues, that different titles signify different publications and grant each its own entry in our union list.⁵ We link successive titles through pointers. This decision also caters to those who search for a specific title without in-depth knowledge of individual publication histories.

A closely related challenge is how to model publishers moving to new places, and sometimes continents, and taking their periodical operations with them. Technically, they will have had to acquire a new permit, licence or concession. We should thus model such “moving” publications as new titles and successors of their publishers’ previous periodical, particularly if volume and issue counts

2. On this episode, known as the “Lewis Affair,” see Farag (1972).

3. Surviving artefacts show that Tarrazi provided an evidently incorrect account of the title’s publication history (2023, 289–92).

4. For the legal history of periodical publishing in the Ottoman Empire, see Boyar (2006, 20–22) and Grallert (2014, 45–49, 62–63). Cioeta (1979) and Ayalon (1995) ignore legal developments and paint a rather static picture.

5. Cf. Gaskelle (2017). Tildesley (2009) points to the endemic nature of title changes in the nineteenth-century press of Great Britain and Ireland.

did not continue. Library catalogues and union lists follow this practice save for a number of very famous and influential journals, such as *المقتطف* (*al-Muqtataf*), which moved operations from Beirut to Cairo in 1884; the journal *المقتبس* (*al-Muqtabas*), moving from Cairo to Damascus after the Young Turk Revolution of 1908; the newspaper *الهدى* (*al-Hudā*), moving from Philadelphia to New York in 1903; and the newspaper *الأهرام* (*al-Ahrām*), moving from Alexandria to Cairo in 1898.

Why such a dataset?

I have covered the reasons and necessity for creating such datasets elsewhere in some detail (Grallert 2021, 2025a, 2025b). They can be summarised as historical layers of technical affordances deeply rooted in Western, colonial perceptions of the Other, whose main result is a common lack of support for non-Latin scripts across the entire technology stack and, consequently, the absence or inaccessibility of datasets in languages that rely on such writing systems (cf. Fiormonte et al. 2015). Comprehensive information on the publication history of the Arabic press was generally inexistent and information on titles surviving in library collections was practically inaccessible in any systematic form prior to Project Jarā'id.

In the following, I will only provide a pertinent example to illustrate the state of affairs: Between 1919 and 1938, Bulus Shahade published the weekly newspaper *مرآة الشرق* (*Mir'āt al-Sharq*) in Jerusalem. As can be seen from the linked Wikidata item, this newspaper is available in a significant number of libraries in Palestine, Israel, Lebanon, the US and Germany. At least two of these provide digital facsimiles. But how would one know? Or, rather, how would one find the title in catalogues?

Figure 1: Masthead of *Mir'āt al-Sharq* no. 1, 17 September 1919

Source: National Library of Israel.

Mir'āt al-Sharq is, of course, a Latinisation of the Arabic original *مرآة الشرق*. It follows the widely adopted system of the (American) *International Journal of Middle East Studies* (IJMES) (IJMES, n.d.; Library of Congress 2012). The same is true for rendering the name of its editor, *بولس شحادة*, as *Bulus Shahade* (note that IJMES does not employ diacritics for personal names). Cataloguers in German-speaking countries would employ a different system with 1:1 character transliterations aiming at phonetic replication, originally devised by the *Deutsche Morgenländische Gesellschaft* (DMG) (Brockelmann et al. 1935; DIN 2011; ISO 1984). They Latinise the title as *Mir'āt aš-Šarq*. French scholarly practices are subtly different and record the paper as *Mir'āt al-Šarq*. Note that the Arabic original, as well as the diacritics utilised in the transcriptions, require support for Unicode character encodings for display and search/retrieval operations. Other, historical, technical transcription systems designed pure ASCII representations such as “mir'_a=t aš-^sarq” to address this problem.⁶ The newspaper itself, published in Palestine during the British Mandate, provided the transliteration *Meraat al-Shark* in its masthead (fig. 1).

Discovery systems and catalogue frontends frequently either do not support Arabic script or the underlying catalogue data does not provide information in the original script. In addition, the Latinisation is prone to error. Cataloguers either make mistakes or the machines at their command do not support the appropriate diacritics, resulting in an even larger variety of possible (mis)spellings. Consequently, records have not been merged in aggregating catalogues. Finally, search algorithms commonly deploy some sort of fuzzy matching that mostly removes diacritics—or simply any non-ASCII characters, retaining only the 26 letters of the English alphabet. They might also support wildcards, such as “*” to stand in for any character.

To find holdings of *مرآة الشرق* (*Mir'āt al-Sharq*) one will, therefore, have to search for “Mir'āt al-Sharq” or “Mirat Sharq” in English catalogues such as the [British Library](#) or OCLC's [WorldCat](#), which has at least eight different records for this title. The former also holds Arabic cataloguing data for this title, but cataloguers wrongly recorded *مرآة الشرق* instead of *مرآة الشرق*. German and French catalogues, like the [ZDB](#), the [Catalogue collectif de France \(CCFR\)](#) or the [Bibliothèque nationale de France \(BnF\)](#) do not support the internationally more common *Mir'āt al-Sharq*, but will return hits for “Mir'āt aš-Šarq”, “Mir'at as-sarq”, or even “Mirat Sarq” and “Mir*a* sarq”. Note that the historical phonetic French transcription would have used “ch” instead of “š” for *ش*. The BnF has also catalogued some of their holdings in Arabic and supports search in the original script (this is not the case for the CCFR aggregating the BnF data).⁷

6. Wittern (2013); Unicode Consortium (2022). On the background of Unicode and its application to Arabic, see Nemeth (2017, 400–406); Milo (1999); cf. Romanov ([2015] 2021).

7. The resulting hit in the BnF catalogue leads to another periodical of the same title.

Strength: Overview of uncoordinated digitisation efforts

One of the strengths of Project Jarā'id's dataset is the way it enables a first systematic look into the surviving traces of collection-building efforts and the state of digitisation over the last decades. Table 1 shows the percentage of titles with known holdings and digital remediations. At the time of writing, we can only locate 775 (21.83%) of all 3,550 titles in the dataset in collections. Of these, almost one third, 233 (6.56% of all titles), have digital remediations. The percentage for digitised titles in collections is surprisingly high, but we cannot resolve information on the extent of such digitisation, which varies between a single issue and an entire course of publication. More importantly, the dataset also provides an astonishing insight into the uncoordinated nature of scanning efforts: 66 periodicals or 28.33 percent of all digitised periodicals have been digitised by multiple institutions and 21 of this subset by three and more. Considering the limited resources and relatively high cost of digitisation, it would surely make sense if future efforts were directed towards those titles not yet digitised at all. Making this information readily available and queryable through Wikidata contributes to this goal.

Table 1: Periodical holdings and digitised copies

Periodicals	up to 1918		up to 1929	
Published	2,054		3,550	
Known holdings	540		775	
% of total		26.29		21.83
-----	----	----	----	-----
Digitised	156		233	
% of known holdings		28.89		30.06
% of total		7.59		6.56
-----	----	----	----	-----
Multiple digitisations	51		66	
% of total		2.48		1.86
% of digitised		32.69		28.33

Weaknesses

Jarā'id has a number of weaknesses for users, contributors and maintainers, almost all of them rooted in its nature as an unfunded, volunteer-driven research project.

Users looking for information on Arabic periodicals

Almost all users of Jarā'id as a union list will access the data through the [project website](#), which is implemented as a static site and is currently hosted on GitHub. Updates to the source TEI/XML will trigger an automatic regeneration of the website.

1. The website has only limited visibility beyond those already in-the-know. Somebody searching for Arabic periodicals will either consult established discovery systems such as library catalogues or aggregating platforms, or conduct a web search, where the website will not be prominently ranked.
2. The website has only limited usability. Data is presented in tabular form with a number of indexes. Some core fields have been automatically re-transcribed into the original Arabic script, while more concise information is provided in Latinised transcription and English notes. The surrounding interface is written solely in English. Search is implemented through the browser's full-text search function. Browsing is limited to a number of indexes for publication places and editors, but they provide only Latinised transcriptions. Both points severely limit the circle of potential users to a small community of academic researchers.

Contributors

Contributions can be submitted either via email to the project maintainers or, for the more technically savvy, by directly editing the source and opening a pull-request on GitHub. While this ensures that project editors can vet contributions, it also introduces technical barriers and depends on editors maintaining the project ad infinitum.

Maintainers

The current setup follows minimal computing principles in an attempt to balance “what do *we* need?” with “what do *we* have?” (Gil and Ortega 2016; Risam and Gil 2022, emphasis mine) It has very few overheads and can be easily downloaded, archived and moved to other servers. However, it depends on a number of commercial services (notably GitHub) and requires maintainers to not just curate the dataset but to design and maintain a website and workflows for updating the site's content.

Wikidata

[Wikidata](#) is the largest public knowledge graph with hundreds of millions of items, published under CC0 licence.⁸ Such a graph organises structured

8. See <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Statistics> for up-to-date statistics.

information about items in statements that construct relations between items, such as “*Mir’āt al-Sharq* is a newspaper,” “*Mir’āt al-Sharq* was first published on 17 September 1919,” “*Mir’āt al-Sharq* was published in Jerusalem,” “Jerusalem is a city,” “*Mir’āt al-Sharq* was founded by Bulus Shahade,” “Bulus Shahade was a human being,” etc. Such statements are expressed as properties and should be attributed to a source (another item or URI). Statements can carry further qualifiers, such as temporal information or indications of the certainty of a claim. Even though Wikidata (in)famously does not adhere to a strict ontology and is frequently referred to as a “folksonomy” (see Manzo et al. 2015) characterised by communities of modelling practices, only very few of which are documented, it does have data models. All properties have data types and might come with a set of rules that will result in warnings if violated—although there is no strict technical enforcement of these rules and they are, consequently, frequently violated (or, at least, ignored).⁹ The only exception to this rule seems to be items lacking labels, descriptions and the [instance of \(P31\)](#) property. Without the latter, which identifies the fundamental nature of an item as being, for instance, a [newspaper \(Q11032\)](#), items are left detached from the larger knowledge graph. If no other item links to them, some housekeeping bots might eventually delete them.

In addition to being a huge source of data—and arguably more importantly—Wikidata is an international community of active volunteers. It is also a project of the Wikimedia Foundation and a sister project to Wikipedia. The software it runs on, [Wikibase](#), is maintained as free and open-source software (FOSS) (Vrandečić, Pintscher, and Krötzsch 2023).

Wikidata addresses all the weaknesses of Project Jarā'id, as outlined above: Firstly, Wikidata inherently adheres to the FAIR principles by making all data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable on practicable levels (GO FAIR 2020). Our current setup provided interoperable and reusable data, but was severely lacking in findability and accessibility. Wikidata, on the other hand, is highly visible to search engines and aggregating platforms and provides a multilingual interface supporting all languages within the limits of Unicode. People looking for Arabic periodicals will actually be able to find them with our data published in Wikidata. These advantages are matched on the technical side, where Wikidata provides five-star Linked Open Data (Berners-Lee 2009), in other words, machine-readable structured data in non-proprietary formats, adhering to open standards, with a public domain licence (CC0), and linking to other people’s data through multiple APIs, including SPARQL endpoints. Linking

9. OpenRefine claims that [ALA-LC romanization \(P8991\)](#) is not designed for use as a qualifier, even though that is exactly how it appears in all examples. The Wikidata frontend itself does not reject this use of P8991, e.g. <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q124963763>.

to Wikidata is enabled by canonical identifiers for all items and properties and by permanent URIs for each edit.¹⁰

Secondly, Wikidata is a well-established open infrastructure with large communities of users, contributors and maintainers, which far exceeds anything we as scholars could ever achieve on our own on an infrastructural level. As such, it is increasingly adopted as a platform to share authority data by GLAM institutions and research projects (Fagerving 2023; Allison-Cassin and Scott 2018; Odell, Lemus-Rojas, and Brys 2022; Sardo and Bianchini 2022; Zhao 2023). Thirdly, Wikidata, like its sister projects Wikipedia and Wikimedia Commons, is a community-driven platform and provides easy tools for collaboratively editing and contributing data. The threshold for joining Project Jarā'id's crowd-sourcing effort on Wikidata is thus in practice lowered to having access to a device with an internet connection.

Finally, maintaining a dataset of thousands of periodicals, people and organisations is extremely challenging and prone to errors when data is kept in a collection of tables and XML files. Wikidata, on the other hand, provides a plethora of tools for data cleaning, deduplication and reconciliation that significantly ease maintenance work.

Weaknesses

Wikidata, of course, has weaknesses of its own. Scholars and GLAM institutions are commonly wary of ceding control over “their” datasets to volunteer-driven, radically open projects. While vandalism does not constitute a significant problem, misidentification of items and erroneous edits occur on a daily basis. The larger problem, however, is bulk uploads of datasets from research projects and GLAM institutions creating large numbers of duplicates, which require detection and merging.¹¹

Quality and distribution of data

Unsurprisingly, data quality and consistency vary widely across Wikidata, and biases in coverage mirror those of the digital realm writ large: Latin script, European/colonial languages, predominantly English, the Global North. For

10. In fact, Wikidata recommends always referencing the versioned permanent URL instead of the canonical ID; see <https://www.wikidata.org/w/index.php?title=Special:CiteThisPage&page=Q25212027&id=2313077072&wpFormIdentifier=titleform> for citations of <https://www.wikidata.org/w/index.php?title=Q25212027&oldid=2313077072>.

11. Private communications with Wikimedia Deutschland in 2024. See Sahu-Hough (2025) for similar arguments and observations.

example, before contributing our datasets in mid-March 2024,¹² Wikidata contained information on almost 30,000¹³ periodicals published before 1930 (fig. 2), but only 93 of them were Arabic periodicals (fig. 3).

Figure 2: Map of all periodicals (items created before 18 March 2024), SPARQL query

Figure 3: Map of all Arabic periodicals (items created before 18 March 2024), SPARQL query

Almost 11,000 or roughly one third of the total carried no language information at all (the titles and labels of them were almost exclusively written in Latin script). The remaining dataset was surprisingly tilted towards Swedish—a rather minor language on the global scale, but apparently one with a strong Wikidata

-
12. Wikidata does not provide the date of an item's creation through APIs. I therefore used the sequentially assigned IDs of items as an indirect marker and used the ID of an item with a known creation date as a filter, assuming that all items with lower IDs would have been created before (see Gray 2019).
 13. Wikimedia provides persistent, short URLs for SPARQL queries and their results, but the link shortener has a fixed length for input URLs of 2,000 characters. This limit is easily breached with queries containing non-ASCII symbols that will need expensive URL encoding (Wikimedia Foundation 2025). I therefore use <https://query-chest.toolforge.org/>, a similar service specifically designed for SPARQL queries.

Related projects

Other projects have contributed (smaller) datasets on periodicals to Wikidata before, for example [Agents of Change: Women Editors and Socio-Cultural Transformation in Europe, 1710–1920 \(WeChangEd\)](#) (Thornton et al. 2022) and the National Library of Wales (NLW). The latter spearheaded the usage of Wikidata as a union catalogue for periodicals. Wikidata Visiting Scholar Simon Cobb and National Wikimedian Jason Evans, both at the National Library of Wales, added hundreds of Welsh periodicals to Wikidata from 2017 onwards and linked them to holding institutions.¹⁵ However, their example had not generally caught on and only about 1,200 of the almost 30,000 Wikidata items representing periodicals in mid-March 2024 linked to holdings in specific collections ([SPARQL query](#)).

Data model

The most important aspect of contributing data to an existing dataset is mapping our local data model (TEI/XML `<biblStruct>`s, see appendix A) to the target model of Wikidata items and properties (fig. 5). All modelling decisions serve a specific purpose (cf. Stachowiak 1973). In our case, I wanted to maximise the discoverability of periodicals and holdings while maintaining as much of the semantic expressiveness of our original data model as possible. Given the nature of Wikidata's folksonomy outlined above, data models on the platform largely exist as shared social practices, which are then enacted by SPARQL queries. I therefore looked at existing periodicals and WikiProjects to develop a basic data model of Wikidata properties for our dataset (Wikimedia Foundation 2022).

```

1  PREFIX medium: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1002697>      # set a publication type:
                                                                    periodicals (wd:Q1002697),
                                                                    newspapers (wd:Q11032)
2  SELECT DISTINCT
3    ?periodical ?dateOnset
4  WHERE {
5    VALUES ?dateOfInterest                                     # set a date of interest
6    {"1930-01-01"^^xsd:dateTime}.
7    ?periodical wdt:P31/                                       # limit to medium
      wdt:P279* medium: ;
8    (wdt:P571 | wdt:P580) ?dateOnset.
9    ?periodical wdt:P407/                                       # limit by publication language
      wdt:P279* wd:Q13955.                                       (Arabic = Q13955)
10   FILTER(?dateOnset <                                       # published before a specific
      ?dateOfInterest).                                         date
11 }
12 ORDER BY ?dateOnset
13 LIMIT 4000

```

15. This is evidenced by contributions from their accounts, [Sic19](#) and [Jason.nlw](#).

Figure 5: Schematic drawing of our data model for periodicals

Most statements have been removed for illustrative purposes.

To avoid creating duplicates, I had to reconcile our dataset with existing Wikidata items. I could not, therefore, directly generate [QuickStatements](#), a simple text format for directly manipulating Wikidata items, but had to import our data into [OpenRefine](#) first. OpenRefine is a well-established tool for data wrangling and reconciliation of various data sources, initially released in 2010. It also supports parsing of XML. However, directly importing `<tei:biblStruct>` proved unfeasible as this would have required a direct 1:1 mapping between the TEI and Wikidata or extensive data manipulation in OpenRefine with [GREL](#) (General Refine Expression Language), a language I am not overly familiar with. In addition, mixed-content nodes containing both plain text and child elements are a common feature in TEI/XML. They also proved nigh impossible to resolve with OpenRefine. I therefore implemented a mapping to the Wikidata data model as custom XML through transforming our TEI/XML source with [XSLT](#) stylesheets. For easier human readability, this custom XML uses Wikidata’s property IDs as element names (e.g. `<wd:P407>` for `<tei:textLang>` expressing the publication language of a periodical) and employs XML’s native tree structure to map qualifiers and references (see appendix B).

The intermediate step of using OpenRefine for reconciliation then necessitates the actual mapping from OpenRefine fields to Wikidata. This is done through OpenRefine’s interface. The resulting JSON schemas have been exported for sharing and reuse (Grallert 2025c).

Mapping scripts and languages

Mapping language and script information proved difficult. HTML5 and TEI/XML use BCP 47 language tags (Network Working Group 2009) in their language attributes, which allow users to freely combine tags for language and script, such as “ar-Latn-x-ijmes” for formally describing “Arabic, written in Latin script using a private transliteration scheme called IJMES.” Yet, Wikidata

does not strictly separate information on language and script. It provides its own language tags for monolingual text fields, which can only be edited by the development team (Wikimedia Foundation 2024).

Creativity was thus required. One option is to provide the original Arabic title and add transliterations through a qualifier. This would explicitly demonstrate that the transcription was not found on the material artefact. However, there is currently only a single property for one of the myriad Latin transcriptions of Arabic or Ottoman Turkish beyond the generic [transliteration or transcription \(P2440\)](#)¹⁶: namely, [ALA-LC romanization \(P8991\)](#), which for all practical purposes is similar to the IJMES transcription (Library of Congress 2012). Proposing new properties, which might require lengthy discussions with the community of Wikidata editors and might stall for years, seemed insufficiently promising in the short term. Yet, I consider such proposals a worthwhile endeavour for the most common transcriptions of languages written in Arabic script and I plan to submit them in the future. However, using qualifiers leaves three issues. First, our original dataset does not explicitly link transcriptions to original script, leaving a small number of “dangling” transcriptions which cannot be unambiguously associated with an original. Second, such usage of qualifiers is currently not very common. A [SPARQL query](#) for publications (not restricted to periodicals) with transliterated titles using P2440 returns 184 items. The overwhelming majority of these works are written in Uzbek.¹⁷ Using such a rarely deployed property as P2440, while feasible, would therefore not necessarily increase the findability of our data. Third, qualifiers cannot be further qualified, which means that we cannot provide individual sources for transliterations.

On the other hand, there are numerous examples of wrongly labelled languages on existing items for periodicals, where transcriptions carry the tag of either the target or source language. This is particularly true for Hebrew periodicals, for example “Hadashot” as the English title of [חדשות \(Q1058638\)](#) or “Mekiyлта” as the Hebrew title of [מכילתא \(Q120618180\)](#). The aforementioned WECHANGED project equally recorded some Latinised transcriptions of Greek titles, such as “Estiades” for [Εστιάδες \(Q88564665\)](#), as Greek titles. I followed this example and (wrongly) labelled transcriptions of Arabic, Ottoman and Ladino with their target language in other words “English,” “German” and “Turkish” respectively. I also followed this approach for transcriptions provided in the mastheads of periodicals themselves (see fig. 1). This was done with a view to the discoverability and retrievability of data points through simpler SPARQL queries without qualifiers. However, the current iteration of the XSLT stylesheets for converting TEI/XML to the custom XML of our Wikidata data model also supports mapping transcriptions to the relevant qualifiers and we will amend existing items accordingly.

16. I thank one of the anonymous reviewers for bringing this property to my attention.

17. There are also a small number of items which employ P2440 for translations of the title.

Workflow

The Jarā'id dataset connects four types of entities: periodicals, people (as editors, founders and publishers), organisations (holding institutions) and places. For the time being, I excluded historical organisations such as publishers and printing shops, as we have not systematically recorded them in our input data. Each type of entity requires a multistep upload process:

1. **Reconcile** all properties whose data type is a Wikidata item with existing items in order to avoid creating duplicates. Depending on the data model, this can quickly result in hours and hours of semi-automatic work. The step is significantly helped by persistent identifiers (PIDs) from other authority files, such as [OCLC](#) for publications, [VIAF](#) for people, or [GeoNames](#) for places, which we have already integrated in our dataset as far as possible. Note also that OpenRefine utilises the reconciliation service API, which is not language-agnostic (World Wide Web Consortium 2023). It is important to ensure the language of the API matches the language of the data.¹⁸
2. **Create** new Wikidata items for all unreconciled entities. This was done in batches directly from within OpenRefine.
3. **Integrate** identifiers of newly created and reconciled Wikidata items (QIDs) into our local dataset in order to maintain the link between the two. This was done through processing data exports (CSV) from OpenRefine and merging the QIDs into the TEI/XML with XSLT.
4. **Link** and enrich Wikidata items. As items for different types of entities, such as periodicals and editors, were created independently from each other, the newly created items then had to be cross-linked through OpenRefine; for example, *مرآة الشرق* (*Mir'āt al-Sharq*) and its editor بولس شحادة (*Bulus Shahade*) were linked through [P112](#) and [P108](#).

Finally, we also decided to **archive** all Wikidata items relevant to our project. Easy and practically unrestricted access to editing items is one of Wikidata's greatest strengths, but also its main weakness from the point of view of the academic community. Data will change, and although one can reference a specific version of a Wikidata item with a PID, Wikidata is not a repository for long-term data preservation and might cease operating. Thus, we wrote the necessary scripts to periodically download, version and push subgraphs to code-sharing platforms and research-data repositories (Dresselhaus and Grallert 2024; Grallert 2024a).

Results

During the initial phase, I added high-quality bibliographic information for more than 3,000 Arabic periodicals, including 2,728 editors and 347 holding

18. I thank one of the anonymous reviewers for pointing me to the API documentation to address this subtlety.

institutions, increasing the total from 93 to 3,248 titles as of 8 August 2024 (fig. 6). Most of these entities required creating new Wikidata items and linking them together.

Figure 6: Map of all Arabic periodicals (items created up to 8 August 2024), SPARQL query

Answering research questions

Having added our dataset to Wikidata allows for the sort of complex queries imagined in the introduction to this article—queries which are otherwise impossible to execute in common discovery systems or in the published tabular form of Jarā'id. Using Wikidata's SPARQL endpoint, we can answer our initial research questions and display the results on an interactive map: Which local newspapers existed at the time of the food riots of summer 1910 in the Eastern Mediterranean (fig. 7)? Where can I find surviving holdings (fig. 8)? Or, even better: Which periodicals can be instantaneously accessed as digitised copies (fig. 9)?

Figure 7: Map of newspapers published in the Eastern Mediterranean during the summer of 1910, SPARQL query

Figure 8: Map of newspapers published in the Eastern Mediterranean during the summer of 1910 with known holdings, SPARQL query

Figure 9: Map of newspapers published in the Eastern Mediterranean during the summer of 1910 with digitised copies, [SPARQL query](#)

One can also use Wikidata to answer questions regarding the visual language and potential regional preferences for specific front page layouts. The relevant [SPARQL query](#) linking places of publication with digital facsimiles of periodicals does not yet yield enough results for a meaningful analysis (fig. 10), but it demonstrates the potential of such visual approaches for browsing and quick classification (broadsheet, multi-column, illustrated). One could rather easily write a bot that follows the links to openly accessible facsimiles provided through our efforts. It could then use machine vision to identify front pages, download a copy and add the image file to WikiCommons if the digitised items are in the public domain. Finally, it would then link these images to the Wikidata items for the relevant periodicals with [P18](#).

Figure 10: Section of the graph connecting places of publication with images of Arabic periodicals published before 1930, SPARQL query

Guiding future digitisation efforts

GLAM institutions stand to benefit immensely from the cross-linking of records between Wikidata and aggregating platforms, authority files and library catalogues. This not only increases the visibility of their collections to wider audiences, but also backlinks to Wikidata based on queries for identifiers from WorldCat (OCLC), the Library of Congress (LoC) or the Zeitschriften Datenbank (ZDB) already available in their cataloguing data, and would make it possible to pull in additional information such as titles in original scripts and complementary collections. Summary statistics on collections (table 2) or digitised periodical titles (table 3) can help direct the limited funds for costly digitisation efforts towards titles that are not yet scanned or those in urgent need of preservation. This would prevent all too common uncoordinated and redundant digitisation efforts.

Table 2: Result of the SPARQL query ranking periodicals by the number of collections they are found in

rank	periodical	periodicalLabel	countCollections
1	Q124972743	al-Mashriq	50
2	Q15856582	Al-Hilal (magazine)	40
3	Q6033538	Al-Muqtataf	31
4	Q286468	Al-Ahram	30
	Q124964344	Majallat al-Majma‘ al-‘ilmī	30
5	Q65563187	Al-Jinan	24
6	Q4118576	Al-Musawar	16
7	Q6793025	Rose al-Yūsuf	14
	Q17521078	Ad-Diya	14
	Q4702794	Al-Manar	14
	Q12207336	Hadiqat al-Akhbar	14
8	Q124970439	Majallat al-Ustādh	13
9	Q22018602	Az-Zuhur	12
10	Q21605653	Al-Bayan (journal)	11
	Q108084719	Al Bashir	11
	Q124970913	al-Jawā’ib	11
11	Q6559136	Lisan al-Hal	10
	Q43032686	al-Siyāsa al-Usbū‘iyya	10
12	Q124972736	al-Masarra	9
	Q127427564	al-Jāmi‘a al-‘Uthmāniyya	9
	Q124973866	Rawḍat al-Madāris al-Miṣriyya	9

Table 3: Result of the SPARQL query ranking periodicals by the number of times they were digitised

rank	periodical	periodicalLabel	countDigitised
1	Q22018602	Az-Zuhur	13
2	Q15856582	Al-Hilal (magazine)	11
	Q124970439	Majallat al-Ustādh	11
3	Q4702794	Al-Manar	9
	Q12237314	Lughat Al Arab	9
	Q6033538	Al-Muqtataf	9
4	Q19259751	At-Tabib	8
	Q21605653	Al-Bayan (journal)	8
5	Q12238943	Al-Irfan	7
	Q17521078	Ad-Diya	7
6	Q124974308	Majallat al-Azhar	6
	Q65563187	Al-Jinan	6
	Q124972743	al-Mashriq	6

rank	periodical	periodicalLabel	countDigitised
7	Q4118576	Al-Musawar	5
	Q124972674	al-Marʿa al-Jadīda	5
	Q124973866	Rawḍat al-Madāris al-Miṣriyya	5
8	Q124972207	al-Funūn	4
	Q127427564	al-Jāmiʿa al- ʿUthmāniyya	4
	Q124970827	al-Jāmiʿa	4

Reuse of data models and workflows

Once data models and mappings are set up, they can be easily reused for additional datasets. To test this claim, I added hundreds of periodicals from Baykal’s wonderful index for the press of the Ottoman Empire between 1908 and 1914 (Baykal 2019) to Wikidata. The index is based on documentation found in the Ottoman state archives, contemporary accounts (Hakki Bey 1909) and the Hakki Tarık Us Collection (HTU) at Beyazıt State Library. Although the book was only digitally published in unstructured form, the open-access PDF is of sufficient quality to automatically extract the relevant information.¹⁹ I then transformed the extracted data into our familiar `<tei:biblStruct>`s with a combination of regular expressions and XSLT stylesheets. This yielded structured bibliographic information on more than 1,800 periodical titles in all languages of the Ottoman Empire: Ottoman Turkish, Arabic, Armenian, Greek Persian, and so on.

Unfortunately, the index is difficult, if not impossible, to reconcile with existing datasets due to the transcription practices for non-Latin scripts outlined above. Ottoman Turkish was written in Arabic script until the script reform of 1928, when Turkey adopted the Latin alphabet (cf. Fortna 2023; Kirmizialtin and Wrisley 2022). Baykal follows the established practice of Ottomanists and provides modern Turkish renditions for all titles and personal names originally written in non-Latin scripts, such as Arabic, Greek, Judeo-Arabic (in Hebrew script), Karamanlıca (Turkish in Greek script), Ladino (Spanish in Hebrew script) or Ottoman Turkish in Armenian or Hebrew scripts. To my knowledge there exist no readily available tools for an automated reconversion into the original scripts.

As a consequence, I have only uploaded information on 706 Ottoman Turkish periodical titles from Baykal’s index to Wikidata. The existing number of items was small enough to manually reconcile with our dataset. It included mostly

19. I used [pdfx](#).

multilingual periodicals added through our initial contribution of the Jarā'id dataset (SPARQL queries for Ottoman periodicals [before](#) and [after our upload](#)).

Regarding data quality, it must also be noted that Baykal provides only very limited information on publication places. The reason is not entirely clear. Large sections of the Hakkı Tarık Us Collection were digitised and published more than 15 years ago (Baykal 2011; Kirmizialtin and Wrisley 2022). Even though the DjVu format for images was already outdated at the time, it can still be accessed with readily available browser plug-ins,²⁰ making it possible to establish publication places for all of the 500-odd titles in HTU that are listed in the index without locations (out of a total of 722 periodicals). Unfortunately, it seems Baykal only consulted the catalogue.²¹

Discussion

The overall experience of contributing data to Wikidata in bulk is positive. Tools and processes are sufficiently documented and members of the community are rather helpful. Tweaking data models and figuring out some quirks in OpenRefine for macOS (always start from the Java applet launcher!) turned out to be the most time-consuming step. Once the latter was established, it became apparent that Wikimedia maintains a rather aggressive blocklist of IP ranges to prevent people using VPNs to access the site from editing, even when they are logged in and thus identifiable to the system. This particularly impacts contributors living under authoritarian regimes—be they located in the Eastern Mediterranean or North America—who rely on VPNs to escape the surveillance of their governments or the oligarchical corporations running the backbones of our linked knowledge ecologies.

The Wikidata community

People and bots began to contribute data and perform maintenance and data cleaning operations within hours of my initial uploads. Look, for instance, at the journal of *المجلة (al-Majalla)*, published in Buenos Aires from 1915 onwards. I created the item on 18 March 2024 and automatically added information over the course of the next month. One month later, the user “[Sempta](#)” amended information on Spanish-language titles, location of headquarters, and even added a facsimile of the front page. Based on the facsimile, I was then able

20. Such as [DjVu.js Viewer for Firefox](#).

21. A cursory search for three random titles within this sample confirmed that locations and directors of publication (*mudīr al-mas'ūl*, literally “the responsible director”) were indeed provided in mastheads as stipulated by law.

to add subtitles and a publication interval.²² Some human users contribute Latinised transcriptions of Arabic names, such as “Mahmud Ali” for محمود علي,²³ while bots and one diligent user managed to find duplicates and merged them. Thus, for instance, some rudimentary items had been created by bots based on Wikipedia entries for Arabic periodicals in the early 2010s. But these items contained nothing beyond the title of the Wikipedia page and a link to it. In the absence of any statement identifying them as Arabic periodicals, I did not find these items and would have had no capacity to check the linked Wikipedia page, to see whether they should indeed represent a periodical.²⁴

In a small number of cases, human users were too eager to find duplicates and merged clearly distinct items. This has, so far, mostly happened to items for periodical editors and commonly occurred when users did not follow due diligence by ignoring available statements, such as conflicting life dates or locations. To prevent repeated attempts to merge the same items, I have added the statement *different from* (P1889) pointing to the item not to be merged.²⁵ While the number of such misattributions remains small, one still might want to periodically check merges.

Discovery of new titles

Querying Wikidata also returned titles that ought to have been included in the Project Jarā'id dataset but were not covered by the sources we consulted or found in archives and libraries visited by our contributors. Take, for example, *אלחוררייא* (*al-Hurriyya*), a Judeo-Arabic newspaper published in Tangier between 1915 and 1922. Even though none of the information provided on Wikidata is properly referenced, the item points to the catalogue of the National Library of Israel and links to a digital facsimile of the newspaper's front page, which confirm most of the statements.

Conclusion

In this paper, I propose a radically open and democratic approach to some of the scholarly primitives as formulated by John Unsworth—“basic functions common to scholarly activity across disciplines, over time, and independent of theoretical orientation” (Unsworth 2000)—namely, discovering and referring. I present arguments as to why we, as communities of scholars, should gather

22. See the [history of edits for Q124972416](#).

23. See the [history of edits for Q125160798](#).

24. [Original state of the item for Birjīs Bārīs before it was merged with our data](#).

25. For example <https://www.wikidata.org/w/index.php?title=Q12249620&oldid=2336434318> and <https://www.wikidata.org/w/index.php?title=Q125160089&oldid=2336434650>.

and share our collective knowledge of ephemeral cultural artefacts through Wikidata and the socio-technical infrastructure underpinning this particular project within the wider Wikiverse. The paper then thoroughly documents how we can contribute substantial datasets to Wikidata in practice.

I develop my argument against the backdrop of our long-running Project Jarā'id to crowdsource publication histories of all Arabic periodicals published globally before 1930 and document their surviving copies. As a validated union list, the dataset is of immense value to researchers, librarians and the wider public. It remedies many of the fundamental shortcomings of compartmentalised library catalogues and aggregating platforms with their built-in epistemic violence of habitually monolingual—indeed English—technology stacks. However, a dataset is practically irrelevant if it cannot be readily found, accessed and ultimately integrated into the specific workflows and needs of its potential users. In this regard, Project Jarā'id, like so many other scholar-led and underfunded initiatives, should be considered a failure, even though we provide data in a well-established and documented exchange format.

Integrating our datasets into Wikidata solves almost all of the infrastructural problems: Wikibase, the software powering Wikidata and its sister projects, is a well-maintained and open solution, providing well-documented interfaces for human users and machines, as well as the necessary user management for collaborative editing. All user interfaces cater to the linguistic diversity of humanity through support for almost all living languages and scripts (as far as they can be encoded in Unicode). The well-established and thriving community of Wikidata contributors and users, including automated bots for data cleaning and enriching based on external identifiers, will connect us to new communities with interest in and knowledge about the materials we care deeply about. Data on Wikidata might not be as semantically rich as our TEI-based data model, but it is FAIR data with clear licences and fulfils all criteria for five-star Linked Open Data as soon as we link to external catalogues and holdings. Wikimedia Foundation, the organisation behind Wikidata, will outlive anything we can set up within the project-based logic of academic funding. Wikidata, however, is a living project and not a long-term archive despite thorough versioning with stable URIs.

Ultimately, the workflows, data models and code to transform and map bibliographic data from TEI/XML to Linked Open Data, to integrate it into Wikidata and to archive parts of the knowledge graph in public repositories are meant as an invitation. Our experiences with adopting the approach for another dataset demonstrate that other scholars and communities can do likewise with relatively little effort.

References

- Allison-Cassin, Stacy, and Dan Scott. 2018. “Wikidata: A Platform for Your Library’s Linked Open Data.” *The Code4Lib Journal*, no. 40 (May). <https://journal.code4lib.org/articles/13424>.
- Ayalon, Ami. 1995. *The Press in the Arab Middle East: A History*. New York and Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Baykal, Erol. 2011. “Periodicals of the Hakkı Tarık Us Collection.” *Turkish Historical Review* 2 (2): 205–12. <https://doi.org/10.1163/187754611X603065>.
- Baykal, Erol. 2019. *The Ottoman Press (1908–1923)*. The Ottoman Empire and its Heritage, vol. 67. Leiden: Brill. <https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004394889>.
- Berners-Lee, Tim. 2009. “Linked Data—Design Issues.” W3C. Updated 18 June 2009. <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData#fivestar>.
- Boyar, Ebru. 2006. “The Press and the Palace: The Two-Way Relationship Between Abdülhamid II and the Press, 1876–1908.” *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 69 (3): 417–32. <https://doi.org/dr3dn5>.
- Brockelmann, Carl, August Fischer, W. Heffening, and Franz Taeschner. 1935. *Die Transliteration der arabischen Schrift in ihrer Anwendung auf die Hauptliteratursprachen der islamischen Welt. Denkschrift, dem 19. internationalen Orientalistenkongreß in Rom vorgelegt von der Transkriptions-Kommission der Deutschen Morgenländischen Gesellschaft*. Leipzig: Deutsche Morgenländische Gesellschaft, Brockhaus. <https://www.aai.uni-hamburg.de/voror/medien/dmg.pdf>.
- Cioeta, Donald J. 1979. “Ottoman Censorship in Lebanon and Syria, 1876–1908.” *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 10 (2): 167–86. <https://doi.org/d7mtx2>.
- DIN (Deutsches Institut für Normung). 2011. *Information und Dokumentation—Umschrift des arabischen Alphabets für die Sprachen Arabisch, Osmanisch-Türkisch, Persisch, Kurdisch, Urdu und Paschtu*. DIN 31635:2011-07. Beuth Verlag GmbH. <https://doi.org/10.31030/1760820>.
- Dresselhaus, Nicole, and Till Grallert. 2024. “P_wikidata2gitlab.” NFDI4Memory Consortium, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin. https://scm.cms.hu-berlin.de/methodenlabor/p_wikidata2gitlab.
- Fagerving, Alicia. 2023. “Wikidata for Authority Control: Sharing Museum Knowledge with the World.” *Digital Humanities in the Nordic and Baltic Countries Publications* 5 (1): 222–39. <https://doi.org/g56rd>.
- Farag, Nadia. 1972. “The Lewis Affair and the Fortunes of Al-Muqtataf.” *Middle Eastern Studies* 8 (1): 73–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00263207208700195>.
- Fiormonte, Domenico, Desmond Schmidt, Paolo Monella, and Paolo Sordi. 2015. “The Politics of Code. How Digital Representations and Languages Shape Culture.” In *ISIS Summit Vienna 2015—The Information Society at the Crossroads*. Vienna: MDPI AG. <https://doi.org/gkzc7v>.
- Fortna, Benjamin C. 2023. “Multilingualism and the End of the Ottoman Empire: Language, Script, and the Quest for the ‘Modern.’” In *Multilingualism and History*, edited by Aneta Pavlenko, 205–22. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009236287.011>.
- Gaskelle, Beth. 2017. “Bibliographic Issues: Titles, Numbers, Frequencies.” In *Researching the Nineteenth-Century Periodical Press: Case Studies*, edited by Alexis Easley, Andrew King, and John Morton, 46–59. London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315605616>.
- Gil, Alex, and Élika Ortega. 2016. “Global Outlooks in Digital Humanities: Multilingual Practices and Minimal Computing.” In *Doing Digital Humanities: Practice, Training, Research*, edited by Constance Crompton, Richard J. Lane, and Ray Siemens, 22–34. Abingdon: Routledge.
- GO FAIR. 2020. “FAIR Principles.” 5 August 2020. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.
- Grallert, Till. 2014. “To Whom Belong the Streets? Property, Propriety, and Appropriation: The Production of Public

- Space in Late Ottoman Damascus, 1875–1914.” PhD thesis, FU Berlin.
- Grallert, Till. 2021. “Catch Me If You Can! Approaching the Arabic Press of the Late Ottoman Eastern Mediterranean Through Digital History.” Edited by Simone Lässig. *Geschichte und Gesellschaft* 47 (1): 58–89. <https://doi.org/10.13109/gege.2021.47.1.58>.
- Grallert, Till. 2022. “Integrating Library Data into an Authority File: The Challenges of MARC XML and Inconsistent Transcription Practices.” *Digital Humanities Lab* (blog). *Hypotheses*. 18 February. <https://dhlab.hypotheses.org/2631>.
- Grallert, Till. 2024a. “Project Jarā'id: Snapshot of Bibliographic Metadata from Wikidata for All Arabic Periodicals Published Worldwide Before 1930.” Dataset. Zenodo. Version v3, 15 October. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14875615>.
- Grallert, Till. 2024b. “Convert_tei-to-Bibliographic-Data.” XSLT. Zenodo. Version v0.1, 22 November. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14203996>.
- Grallert, Till. 2025a. “Digitalisierung und das textuelle Kulturerbe der Gesellschaften des globalen Südens: Wege für den Umgang mit den Auswirkungen der infrastrukturellen Hegemonie lateinischer Schriftsysteme und Sprachen des globalen Nordens.” In *Clio Guide. Ein Handbuch zu digitalen Ressourcen für die Geschichtswissenschaften*, 3rd ed., edited by Laura Busse, Wilfried Enderle, Rüdiger Hohls, Thomas Meyer, Jens Prellwitz, and Annette Schuhmann. Berlin: Clio-online and Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin.
- Grallert, Till. 2025b. “Editing Mundane Texts Across the Digital Divide: The Case of Arabic Periodicals from the Late Nineteenth-Century Eastern Mediterranean.” In *The Companion to Digital Humanities in Practice*, edited by Constance Crompton, Laura Estill, Richard J. Lane, and Ray Siemens. London: Routledge.
- Grallert, Till. 2025c. “ProjectJaraid/Wikidata-Schemas: Initial release.” Zenodo. Version v0.1, 18 May. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15460309>.
- Grallert, Till. 2025d. “ProjectJaraid/Wikidata-Sparql: Initial Release.” Zenodo. Version v0.1, 18 May. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15460307>.
- Gray, Andrew. 2019. “Gender and Deletion on Wikipedia.” *Andrew Gray* (blog). 6 May. <https://www.generalist.org.uk/blog/2019/gender-and-deletion-on-wikipedia/>.
- Hakki Bey, Isma‘il. 1909. “La Presse Musulmane.” *Revue du monde musulman* 8 (5): 97–139. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k103803m/f101.item>.
- IJMES (*International Journal of Middle East Studies*). n.d. *IJMES Transliteration System for Arabic, Persian, and Turkish*. IJMES. Accessed 1 March 2023. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-file-manager/file/57d-83390f6ea5a022234b400/TransChart.pdf>.
- ISO (International Organization for Standardization). 1984. *Documentation—Transliteration of Arabic Characters into Latin Characters*. ISO 233:1984. ISO. <https://www.iso.org/standard/4117.html>.
- Kirmizialtin, Suphan, and David Joseph Wisley. 2022. “Automated Transcription of Non-Latin Script Periodicals: A Case Study in the Ottoman Turkish Print Archive.” *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 16 (2). <http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/16/2/000577/000577.html>.
- LeBlanc, Zoe. 2024. “More Than Keywords: Histories of Decolonization and Digitized Newspapers.” *The American Historical Review* 129 (1): 164–68. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ahr/rhad499>.
- Library of Congress. 2012. *Arabic Romanization Table*. <https://www.loc.gov/catdir/cpso/romanization/arabic.pdf>.
- Manzo, Christina, Geoff Kaufman, Sukdith Punjasthitkul, and Mary Flanagan. 2015. “‘By the People, For the People’: Assessing the Value of Crowdsourced, User-Generated Metadata.” *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 9 (1). <http://digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/9/1/000204/000204.html>.
- Mestyan, Adam, and Till Grallert. 2012–2015. “A Chronology of Nineteenth-Century Periodicals in Arabic (1800–1900): A

- Research Tool.” Zentrum Moderner Orient (ZMO). Last updated 26 January 2015. <https://web.archive.org/web/20160422071133/https://www.zmo.de/jaraid/>.
- Mestyán, Adam, and Till Grallert. 2020. Jara'id: A Chronology of Arabic Periodicals (1800–1929): A Research Tool. Database. 2020 Edition. <https://projectjaraid.github.io/>.
- Mestyán, Adam, Till Grallert, et al. 2020. “Jarā'id: A Chronology of Arabic Periodicals (1800–1929).” Dataset. Zenodo. Version v1.0, 29 December. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4399240>.
- Milligan, Ian. 2019. *History in the Age of Abundance? How the Web Is Transforming Historical Research*. Montreal: McGill-Queen's University Press.
- Milo, Thomas. 1999. “Some Comments on the Arabic Block in Unicode.” DecoType. <https://www.academia.edu/2480482/>.
- Nemeth, Titus. 2017. *Arabic Type-Making in the Machine Age: The Influence of Technology on the Form of Arabic Type, 1908–1993*. Islamic Manuscripts and Books, vol. 14. Leiden: Brill. <https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004349308>.
- Network Working Group. 2009. *BCP 47: Tags for Identifying Languages*. Edited by A. Phillips and M. Davis. IETF Trust. <https://www.ietf.org/rfc/bcp/bcp47.txt>.
- Odell, Jere, Mairelys Lemus-Rojas, and Lucille Brys. 2022. *Wikidata for Scholarly Communication Librarianship*. Indianapolis: IUPUI University Library. <https://doi.org/10.7912/9Z4E-9M13>.
- Risam, Roopika, and Alex Gil. 2022. “Introduction: The Questions of Minimal Computing.” Edited by Alex Gil and Roopika Risam. *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 16 (2). <http://digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/16/2/000646/000646.html>.
- Romanov, Maxim. (2015) 2021. “Arabic Betacode.” GitHub. <https://github.com/maximromanov/ArabicBetacode>.
- Sa'di, Lutfi M., and George Sarton. 1938. “The Life and Works of George Edward Post (1838–1909).” *Isis* 28 (2): 385–417. <https://doi.org/10.1086/347340>.
- Sahu-Hough, Jasmine Amara. 2025. “Parsing the Payri: The Potentials of Wikidata for Papyrologists.” *International Journal of Information Science and Technology* 9 (1): 1–10. <https://innove.org/ijist/index.php/ijist/article/view/265>.
- Sardo, Lucia, and Carlo Bianchini. 2022. “Wikidata: A New Perspective Towards Universal Bibliographic Control.” *JLIS.It: Italian Journal of Library, Archives and Information Science = Rivista Italiana Di Biblioteconomia, Archivistica e Scienza Dell'informazione* 13 (1): 291–311. <https://doi.org/gn7n2m>.
- Sherratt, Tim. 2019. “Hacking Heritage: Understanding the Limits of Online Access.” In *The Routledge International Handbook of New Digital Practices in Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums and Heritage Sites*, edited by Hannah Lewi, Wally Smith, Dirk vom Lehn, and Steven Cooke, 116–30. London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429506765>.
- Stachowiak, Herbert. 1973. *Allgemeine Modelltheorie*. Vienna, New York: Springer-Verlag.
- Tarrazi, Filib di. 1913–1914, 1933. *Tārīkh al-ṣiḥāfa al-'Arabiyya* [History of the Arabic Press]. 4 vols. Beirut: al-Maṭba'a al-Adabiyya.
- Tarrazi, Filib di. 2023. *Tārīkh al-ṣiḥāfa al-'Arabiyya* [History of the Arabic Press]. 4 vols. Hindāwī. <https://www.hindawi.org/books/47590408/>.
- TEI Consortium. 2025. “TEI P5: Guidelines for Electronic Text Encoding and Interchange.” Zenodo. Version 4.9.0, 24 January. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3413524>.
- Thornton, Katherine, Kenneth Seals-Nutt, Marianne Van Remoortel, Julie M. Birkholz, and Pieterjan De Potter. 2022. “Linking Women Editors of Periodicals to the Wikidata Knowledge Graph.” *Semantic Web* 14 (2): 443–55. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SW-222845>.
- Tildesley, Matthew Brinton. 2009. “Title Changes.” In *Dictionary of Nineteenth-Century Journalism in Great Britain and Ireland*, edited by Laurel Brake and Marysa Demoor, 630–31. Gent, London: Academia Press, British Library. <https://www.dncj.ugent.be/>.

- Unicode Consortium. 2022. *The Unicode Standard 15.0.0—Core Specification*. Unicode Consortium. <https://www.unicode.org/versions/Unicode15.0.0/>.
- Unsworth, John. 2000. "Scholarly Primitives: What Methods Do Humanities Researchers Have in Common, and How Might Our Tools Reflect This?" In *Symposium on Humanities Computing: Formal Methods, Experimental Practice* (King's College, London, 13 May 2000). Vol. 13. London: King's College. <https://web.archive.org/web/20170812152635/http://people.virginia.edu/~jmu2m/Kings.5-00/primitives.html>.
- Vrandečić, Denny, Lydia Pintscher, and Markus Krötzsch. 2023. "Wikidata: The Making Of." In *WWW '23 Companion: Companion Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2023 (Austin, Texas, 30 April–4 May)*, 615–24. New York: Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3543873.3585579>.
- Wikimedia Foundation. 2022. "Wikidata:WikiProject Periodicals." Wikidata. 3 April 2022. https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_Periodicals.
- Wikimedia Foundation. 2024. "Help:Monolingual Text Languages." Wikidata. 5 December 2024. https://www.wikidata.org/w/index.php?title=Help:Monolingual_text_languages&oldid=2283837224.
- Wikimedia Foundation. 2025. "Wikipedia:URLShortener." Wikipedia. <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Wikipedia:URLShortener&oldid=1280569116>.
- Wittern, Christian. 2013. "Character Encoding." In *A Companion to Digital Literary Studies*, edited by Ray Siemens and Susan Schreibman, 564–76. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781405177504.ch31>.
- World Wide Web Consortium. 2023. *Reconciliation Service API v0.2. A Protocol for Data Matching on the Web*. Edited by Antonin Delpeuch, Adrian Pohl, Fabian Steeg, Thad Guidry Sr., and Osmo Suominen. W3C. <https://www.w3.org/community/reports/reconciliation/CG-FINAL-specs-0.2-20230410/>.
- Zaagsma, Gerben. 2023. "Digital History and the Politics of Digitization." *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* 38 (2): 830–51. <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqac050>.
- Zhao, Fudie. 2023. "A Systematic Review of Wikidata in Digital Humanities Projects." *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* 38 (2): 852–74. <https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqac083>.

Appendices

Appendix A – TEI/XML

Exemplary TEI/XML <biblStruct> for the newspaper *Mir'āt al-Sharq* demonstrating our data model. Note how mixing Latin and Arabic script on a single line causes display issues and how Arabic is erroneously rendered from left to right (e.g. lines 4–8).

```
<biblStruct source="https://projectjaraid.github.io/oape:org:73
oape:org:420/wiki:Q124857769" subtype="newspaper" type="periodical">
  <monogr source="oape:org:420">
    <title level="j" xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</title>
    <!-- removed source information (@source) -->
    <title level="j" type="alt" xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</title>
    <title level="j" type="sub" xml:lang="ar">جريدة اسبوعية حرة</title>
    <title level="j" type="sub" xml:lang="ar">جريدة عربية سياسية حرة</title>
    <title level="j" xml:lang="ar-Latn-EN">Meraat al-Sherk</title>
```

```

<title level="j" xml:lang="ar-Latn-x-ijmes">Mir'āt al-Sharq</title>
<title level="j"xml:lang="ar-Latn-x-dmg">Mir'āt aš-Šarq</title>
<title level="j"type="alt" xml:lang="ar-Latn-FR">Meraat alsherq</
title>
<title level="j"type="sub" xml:lang="ar-Latn-x-dmg">ġarīda usbū'īya
hurra</title>
<title level="j"type="alt">Meraat Al-Sherk</title>
<title level="j"type="alt">Meraat al-Shark</title>
<idno type="AUBNO">Mic-NA:000350</idno>
<idno type="OCLC">33001662</idno>
<idno type="jaraid">t1r2801</idno>
<idno type="oape">3513</idno>
<idno type="wiki">Q25212027</idno>
<idno type="zdb">1019615-8</idno>
<!-- removed more identifiers -->
<textLang mainLang="ar"/>
<editor type="owner">
<persName ref="jaraid:pers:2325 oape:pers:1405 wiki:Q125160760"
xml:lang="ar-Latn-x-ijmes">Būlus Shaḥāda</persName>
<persName ref="jaraid:pers:2325 oape:pers:1405 wiki:Q125160760"
xml:lang="ar"><forename>بولس</forename> <surname>شهادة</surname></per-
sName> </editor>
<editor type="editor">
<persName ref="oape:pers:2636 wiki:Q125159749" xml:lang="ar">
<forename>نقولا</forename> <surname>شهادة</surname> </persName> </editor>
<imprint>
<pubPlace>
<placeName ref="geon:281184 oape:place:6 wiki:Q1218"
xml:lang="und-Latn">Jerusalem</placeName>
<placeName
ref="geon:281184 oape:place:6 wiki:Q1218" xml:lang="ar">القدس</
placeName> </pubPlace>
<publisher> <orgName xml:lang="ar">مطبعة مرآة الشرق</orgName> </
publisher>
<date type="onset" when="1919-09-17">1919</date>
<date source="oape:org:73" type="terminus" when="1938">1919-1938</
date>
<!-- removed more dates -->
</imprint>
</monogr>
<note type="holdings"> <list>
<item source="https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/2413018-7">
<label><orgName ref="isil:DE-1w oape:org:287" type="short">Ber-
lin SBB Zeitungsabteilung</orgName> </label>
<listBibl>
<bibl> <idno subtype="DE-1w" type="classmark"
>Ztg 10664 MR</idno> <date type="onset" when="1919">1919</
date> <date type="terminus" when="1938">1938</date> </bibl>
</listBibl> </item>
<item source="oape:org:73">

```

```

    <label> <placeName ref="geon:276781 jaraid:place:2 oape:place:26
wiki:Q3820" resp="#xslt"
    >Beirut</placeName>, <orgName ref="jaraid:org:hAUB oape:org:73"
xml:lang="en">AUB</orgName> </label>
    <ab xml:lang="ar"
    >30 (في المكتبة:مج:1.ع:1- س-مج:20.ع. 1347) 1919:أيلول 17- آذار 30</ab>
    <listBibl>
    <bibl> <idno subtype="AUB" type="classmark">Mic-NA:000350</
idno> </bibl>
    </listBibl> </item>
    <item source="https://projectjaraid.github.io">
    <label> <placeName ref="geon:281184 oape:place:6 wiki:Q1218"
resp="#xslt">Jerusalem</placeName>, <orgName ref="jaraid:org:hEAP119
oape:org:63" xml:lang="und-Latn">Aqṣā</orgName> </label>
    <listBibl>
    <bibl>1922-1936 ()<idno subtype="self" type="URI">https://eap.
bl.uk/collection/EAP119-1-24</idno><idno type="classmark">EAP119/1/24</
idno>, </bibl>
    </listBibl> </item>
    </list> </note>
</biblStruct>

```

Appendix B – Custom XML for Wikidata mapping

The same data for the newspaper *Mir'āt al-Sharq* as transformed into a custom XML with XSLT stylesheets. It uses Wikidata's property IDs as element names. Note how mixing Latin and Arabic script on a single line causes display issues and how Arabic is erroneously rendered from left to right (e.g. lines 5–6).

```

<item xml:id="Q25212027">
  <label xml:lang="en">Mir'āt al-Sharq</label>
  <description xml:lang="en">newspaper published in Jerusalem between
1919 and 1938</description>
  <label xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</label>
  <description xml:lang="ar">جريدة تصدر في القدس بين سنة 1919 و 1938</description>
  <P31>
    <P854>https://projectjaraid.github.io</P854>
    <P854>https://www.aub.edu.lb/libraries/Pages/default.aspx</P854>
    <P854>https://zdb-katalog.de/</P854>
    <P248>Q124857769</P248>
    <QItem>Q111032</QItem>
  </P31>
  <!-- removed source information (P854, P248) -->
  <P31>
    <QItem>Q1002697</QItem>
  </P31>
  <!-- titles -->
  <P1476>
    <string xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</string>
    <P8991>

```

```

    <string>mir'āt al-sharq</string>
  </P8991>
</P1476>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="ar">مرأة الشرق</string>
  <P8991>
    <string>mir'āt al-sharq</string>
  </P8991>
</P1476>
<P1680>
  <string xml:lang="ar">جريدة اسبوعية حرة</string>
</P1680>
<P1680>
  <string xml:lang="ar">جريدة عربية سياسية حرة</string>
</P1680>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="en">Meraat al-Sherk</string>
</P1476>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="en">Mir'āt al-Sharq</string>
</P1476>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="de">Mir'āt aš-Šarq</string>
</P1476>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="fr">Meraat alsherq</string>
</P1476>
<P1680>
  <string xml:lang="de">ğarīda usbū'īya ħurra</string>
</P1680>
<P1476>
  <string>Meraat Al-Sherk</string>
</P1476>
<P1476>
  <string>Meraat al-Shark</string>
</P1476>
<P243>
  <string>33001662</string>
</P243>
<QItem>Q25212027</QItem>
<P1042>
  <string>1019615-8</string>
</P1042>
<!-- removed more identifiers -->
<P407>
  <QItem>Q13955</QItem>
</P407>
<!-- editors -->
<P112>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>

```

```

</P112>
<P127>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>
</P127>
<P98>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>
</P98>
<P98>
  <QItem>Q125159749</QItem>
</P98>
<P2561 xml:lang="ar">
  <string xml:lang="ar">حنا سمعان</string>
</P2561>
<!-- imprint -->
<P291>
  <string>Jerusalem</string>
  <QItem>Q1218</QItem>
</P291>
<P571>
  <date>1919-09-17</date>
</P571>
<P580>
  <date>1919-09-17</date>
</P580>
<P582>
  <date>1938</date>
</P582>
<!-- removed more dates -->
<!-- holding information -->
<P195>
  <P854>https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/2413018-7</P854>
  <string>Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin - Preußischer Kulturbesitz,
Zeitungssammlung</string>
  <QItem>Q28777973</QItem>
  <P580>
    <date>1919</date>
  </P580>
  <P582>
    <date>1938</date>
  </P582>
  <P217>
    <string>Ztg 10664 MR</string>
  </P217>
</P195>
<P195>
  <P854>https://www.aub.edu.lb/libraries/Pages/default.aspx</P854>
  <string>The Library of the American University in Beirut</string>
  <QItem>Q124855340</QItem>
  <P217>
    <string>Mic-NA:000350</string>

```

```

    </P217>
</P195>
<P195>
  <P854>https://projectjaraid.github.io</P854>
  <string>al-Aqṣā Mosque Library</string>
  <QItem>Q22684743</QItem>
  <P217>
    <string>EAP119/1/24</string>
  </P217>
  <P953>
    <string>https://eap.bl.uk/collection/EAP119-1-24</string>
  </P953>
</P195>
</item>
<item xml:id="Q25212027">
  <label xml:lang="en">Mir'āt al-Sharq</label>
  <description xml:lang="en">newspaper published in Jerusalem between
1919 and 1938</description>
  <label xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</label>
  <description xml:lang="ar">جريدة تصدر في القدس بين سنة 1919 و 1938</description>
  <P31>
    <P854>https://projectjaraid.github.io</P854>
    <P248>Q186844</P248>
    <P248>Q124855340</P248>
    <P248>Q107011742</P248>
    <QItem>Q11032</QItem>
  </P31>
  <!-- removed source information (P854, P248) -->
  <P31>
    <QItem>Q1002697</QItem>
  </P31>
  <!-- titles -->
  <P1476>
    <string xml:lang="ar">مرآة الشرق</string>
    <P2440>
      <string xml:lang="en">Meraat al-Sherk</string>
    </P2440>
    <P8991>
      <P854>https://projectjaraid.github.io</P854>
      <P248>Q186844</P248>
      <P248>Q124855340</P248>
      <P248>Q107011742</P248>
      <string xml:lang="en">Mir'āt al-Sharq</string>
    </P8991>
    <P2440>
      <P248>Q186844</P248>
      <string xml:lang="de">Mir'āt aš-Šarq</string>
    </P2440>
  </P1476>
</P1476>

```

```

<string xml:lang="ar">مرأة الشرق</string>
<P8991>
  <string>mir'āt al-sharq</string>
</P8991>
</P1476>
<P1680>
  <P248>Q186844</P248>
  <string xml:lang="ar">جريدة اسبوعية حرة</string>
  <P2440>
    <P248>Q186844</P248>
    <string xml:lang="de">ğarīda usbū'īya ħurra</string>
  </P2440>
</P1680>
<P1680>
  <P248>Q124855340</P248>
  <string xml:lang="ar">جريدة عربية سياسية حرة</string>
</P1680>
<P1476>
  <string xml:lang="fr">Meraat alsherq</string>
</P1476>
<!-- identifiers -->
<P243>
  <string>33001662</string>
</P243>
<QItem>Q25212027</QItem>
<P1042>
  <string>1019615-8</string>
</P1042>
<!-- removed more identifiers -->
<P407>
  <QItem>Q13955</QItem>
</P407>
<!-- editors -->
<P112>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>
</P112>
<P127>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>
</P127>
<P98>
  <QItem>Q125160760</QItem>
</P98>
<P98>
  <QItem>Q125159749</QItem>
</P98>
<P2561 xml:lang="ar">
  <string xml:lang="ar">حنا سمعان</string>
</P2561>
<!-- imprint -->
<P291>

```

```

    <string>Jerusalem</string>
    <QItem>Q1218</QItem>
</P291>
<P571>
    <date>1919-09-17</date>
</P571>
<P580>
    <date>1919-09-17</date>
</P580>
<P582>
    <date>1938</date>
</P582>
<!-- removed more dates -->
<!-- holding information -->
<P195>
    <P854>https://ld.zdb-services.de/resource/2413018-7</P854>
    <string>Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin - Preußischer Kulturbesitz,
Zeitungssammlung</string>
    <QItem>Q28777973</QItem>
    <P580>
        <date>1919</date>
    </P580>
    <P582>
        <date>1938</date>
    </P582>
    <P217>
        <string>Ztg 10664 MR</string>
    </P217>
</P195>
<P195>
    <P854>https://www.aub.edu.lb/libraries/Pages/default.aspx</P854>
    <string>The Library of the American University in Beirut</string>
    <QItem>Q124855340</QItem>
    <P217>
        <string>Mic-NA:000350</string>
    </P217>
</P195>
<P195>
    <P854>https://projectjaraid.github.io</P854>
    <string>al-Aqṣā Mosque Library</string>
    <QItem>Q22684743</QItem>
    <P217>
        <string>EAP119/1/24</string>
    </P217>
    <P953>
        <string>https://eap.bl.uk/collection/EAP119-1-24</string>
    </P953>
</P195>
</item>

```


Creating a Scientific Workflow to Manage Old Italian Texts

Emiliano Degl’Innocenti

Opera del Vocabolario Italiano, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Florence, Italy

Transformations, A DARIAH Journal Abstract

Volume 1, 2025

<https://transformations.episciences.org>

Dates

Submitted: 15/11/2024

Accepted: 14/04/2025

Published: 12/06/2025

DOI: [10.46298/transformations.14779](https://doi.org/10.46298/transformations.14779)

© The authors

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
International

The management and analysis of extensive collections (corpora) of texts is a complex task, encompassing both technological and scientific considerations. Researchers involved in textual studies (including, but not limited to, philologists, palaeographers and codicologists) do not merely extract information from texts; they also examine visual elements—such as layout and *mise-en-page*—and physical characteristics of written materials such as printed books and manuscripts. Their analysis includes text structure, material used, word layout on the page and any annotations or notes. The development of efficient scientific workflows to handle these diverse aspects is a significant challenge in the field of digital humanities. The following article describes a scientific workflow supporting the management of Old Italian texts, offering innovative integration of semantic technologies and philological methods to enhance scholarly digital editions.

Keywords: text corpora management, text corpora analysis, Old Italian texts, digital humanities, scientific workflows, scholarly digital editions

Astratto

La gestione e l'analisi di vaste collezioni di testi (corpora) costituisce un compito complesso, che comprende considerazioni sia tecnologiche che scientifiche. I ricercatori che si occupano di studi testuali (tra cui, ma non solo: filologi, paleografi e codicologi) non si limitano a estrarre informazioni dai testi, ma esaminano anche le caratteristiche visive (cioè l'impaginazione e la *mise-en-page*) e materiali (cioè la fisicità) dei materiali di scrittura (cioè libri stampati e manoscritti), tra cui la struttura del testo, il materiale utilizzato, la disposizione delle parole sulla pagina ed eventuali annotazioni o note. Lo sviluppo di flussi di lavoro scientifici efficienti per gestire questi diversi aspetti è una sfida significativa nel campo delle digital humanities. L'articolo che segue descrive un flusso di lavoro scientifico a supporto della gestione di testi in italiano antico, offrendo un'integrazione innovativa di tecnologie semantiche e metodi filologici per migliorare le edizioni scientifiche digitali.

Parole chiave: gestione di corpora testuali, analisi di corpora testuali, testi in italiano antico, digital humanities, workflow scientifici, edizioni digitali accademiche

Acknowledgements

This paper was presented and discussed during the workshop “Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages.” The workshop was conceived by the DARIAH Research Data Management Working Group and Multilingual DH Working Group, financed by the DARIAH-EU Funding Scheme for Working Group Activities 2023–2025, and hosted by the University of Hamburg from 28 to 30 August 2024.

Conflict of Interest

The authors do not have any conflict of interest to declare

1 INTRODUCTION

This article presents and discusses a scientific workflow supporting the management of textual resources written in Old Italian. Drawing on the experience and activities carried out by DARIAH-IT,¹ this paper describes the methodological considerations and technological solutions devised to address the intricate range of linguistic, textual and philological issues posed by documents dating from the Middle Ages. Since 2022, DARIAH-IT has participated in the H2IOSC (Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud) project,² whose primary goal is to facilitate data-driven research by enabling users to design and run complex scientific workflows, combining different resources (i.e. digital data and/or services) to produce meaningful and replicable research outputs. By linking together different resources, users can automate complex analytical tasks and extract meaningful insights from data. Within the H2IOSC project, DARIAH-IT also develops a number of scientific pilots: custom Virtual Research Environments supported by digital data, tools and services tailored to support specific kinds of disciplinary research, which serve as usable representations of the above approach. To develop the pilots (and hence the workflows), presented as platforms or hubs integrating domain-specific services, workflows and interfaces, DARIAH-IT undertook a set of preparatory activities. These included mapping and evaluating existing resources (tools, datasets and services) relevant to the target scientific communities (e.g. philologists). To build solid use cases, research data management is essential for ensuring the long-term accessibility, reproducibility and impact of the researcher's scholarly work. Effective data management practices not only improve the quality of research; they strengthen the credibility and transparency of the findings.

These efforts are closely aligned with the objectives of the DARIAH Research Data Management Working Group,³ as it, too, seeks to promote best practices, facilitate data sharing and help build sustainable digital infrastructures for the arts and humanities. The good practices shared in this context (through discussion, documents and reference libraries⁴) offered reflection points that could be applied to the work carried out by DARIAH-IT. The preparatory work described in this introduction resulted in a workflow to manage Old Italian textual data in an integrated environment.

-
1. DARIAH-IT is the Italian node of DARIAH ERIC (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, European Research Infrastructure Consortium), an ESFRI Landmark for the Social and Cultural Innovation sector. DARIAH-IT's headquarters are located at the research institute Opera del Vocabolario Italiano (OVI-CNR).
 2. H2IOSC is a federated cluster comprising the Italian branches of four European research infrastructures (RIs) active in the Social Sciences and Humanities ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) domain. These are DARIAH, CLARIN, E-RIHS and OPERAS. The H2IOSC project is funded by Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), which aims to facilitate collaboration among researchers working in different disciplines within the social sciences and humanities. Further details can be found on the project's website: <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>.
 3. The DARIAH Research Data Management Working Group (<https://www.dariah.eu/activities/working-groups/research-data-management/>) is a collaborative initiative that addresses the challenge of sharing and preserving research data in the arts and humanities. It brings together researchers, cultural heritage professionals and data management experts to develop best practices, support open scholarly infrastructure and facilitate access to data.
 4. For more information on the references shared by the DARIAH Research Data Management Working Group, see https://www.zotero.org/groups/2427138/data_management_best_practices_in_the_humanities.

The main steps of the workflow are: data acquisition from stakeholders; data modelling using ontologies; semantic parsing; transformation into semantic data; storage and documentation of code; and querying of data through semantic technologies (e.g. SPARQL endpoints). Each of these steps is designed to address the complexities inherent in Old Italian textual data. It is clear, therefore, that a tailored workflow is required to deal with the specific linguistic and textual characteristics of Old Italian.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 CONTEXT

Modern Italian has often been compared to Old Italian (Ascoli 1882; Castellani 1980) in the perspective of a substantial continuity from Latin to the language spoken today. A fundamental element in this vision of linguistics studies is the Florentine vulgar tongue used by Dante and his contemporaries in the XIII–XVI centuries, making the language spoken in Tuscany the de facto standard for the common Italian language. However, while the thesis of a linguistic continuity of the language was almost uncontested until the last century, more recently, philological and linguistic traditions have given rise to different approaches to the origin and evolution of Italian. These studies either advocate the separation of old and modern Italian (Salvi and Renzi 2010), or provide different perspectives to approach the problem. Interest has also been rekindled in the different regional variants of Italian. Even in contemporary Italy, there are significant differences between regional variants and dialects, reflecting the complex history of a country that was only officially unified in 1861.⁵

Given the complexity of the panorama just outlined,⁶ and in order to have common chronological references, this article uses the term “Old Italian” for all the available historical documentation from the first document that can be called Italian (albeit doubtfully), namely the early-ninth-century Veronese Riddle (*Indovinello Veronese*⁷), until the end of the fourteenth century (a symbolic year, which is sometimes freely exceeded, is 1375, the year of Boccaccio’s death). This clarification is necessary because the period may differ slightly from what is stated in the scientific literature.⁸

While scholarly discussions around the linguistic and historical development of Old Italian are extensive, this paper explicitly focuses on the digital methodologies and technological tools developed to effectively manage and exploit historical textual data through digital workflows. DARIAH-IT supports researchers working on manuscripts containing Old Italian texts by applying different technologies to the complex task of managing resources, including storing, mapping, cleaning, modelling and visualising data.

5. A comprehensive account of how the Italian language developed historically, including its structural shifts and socio-political dimensions, can be found in Lepschy and Lepschy (2006) and Marazzini (2009).

6. To delve deeper into the panorama of romance languages, see Tomasin (2019).

7. *Indovinello Veronese*. Circa eighth—ninth century. Manuscript marginalia, Biblioteca Capitolare di Verona, codex LXXXIX. See also Schiaparelli (1924).

8. See, for example, the *Collins English Dictionary*: <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/old-italian>.

The difference between old and modern Italian editions lies not only in linguistic form but also in editorial practice. Old Italian editions present texts in a language which, although normalised for readability, is not modernised: spelling is standardised, abbreviations are expanded and punctuation is clarified, yet the original lexicon, syntax and verb forms are preserved (e.g. *ond'io, core, vedeasi*). These editions rely on a rich critical apparatus based on multiple, often conflicting, manuscript witnesses, aiming to reconstruct a version close to the lost original. In contrast, modern Italian editions usually derive from autographs or typed drafts authored by the writers themselves, and the language already adheres to contemporary standards. The critical apparatus here serves to document the creative process, highlighting revisions, stylistic variations and editorial interventions rather than textual recovery.

To understand the linguistic divergence between old and modern Italian, consider this example from Petrarch's *Canzoniere*, edited according to philological standards, which reads: "*Voi ch'ascoltate in rime sparse il suono / di quei sospiri ond'io nutriva 'l core*" (Petrarca 2004). This version maintains the original lexicon (*core* for "cuore" *ond'io* for "con cui io") and syntax. In contrast, a version in modern Italian might read "*Voi che ascoltate, in versi sparsi, il suono / di quei sospiri con cui nuttivo il cuore*",⁹ which adapts both vocabulary and structure to modern Italian norms. While the latter is more accessible to today's readers, it alters the poetic and linguistic fabric of the source. It is important, therefore, to highlight critical editorial choices in distinguishing between faithful transcription and modern reinterpretation.

2.2 USE CASE

The development of a workflow for Old Italian texts was first implemented within the framework of the RESTORE project.¹⁰ Co-funded by the Regional Council of Tuscany and coordinated by the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano (OVI-CNR), RESTORE focused on the medieval period and the historical figure of Francesco di Marco Datini.¹¹ The objective was to develop a digital platform fostering the FAIRification¹² of the digital assets (both new and legacy) gathered by several GLAMs¹³ and research organisations. This in turn would enable the ingestion, conversion, mapping and integration of heterogeneous datasets to overcome the high degree of fragmentation and lack of interoperability of the digital resources provided by

9. This modernised rendering is adapted for illustrative purposes and does not reflect a critical edition.

10. The RESTORE (smaRt accESs TO digital heRitage and mEmory) project, co-funded by Regione Toscana (Regional Council of Tuscany), was coordinated by the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano (OVI-CNR), partnering with GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives and museums) institutions and offices in the city of Prato. The project consortium included Prato's key cultural and memory institutions: the Prato State Archive (*Archivio di Stato di Prato*), the Palazzo Pretorio Museum (*Museo di Palazzo Pretorio*), the *Soprintendenza Archivistica e Bibliografica della Toscana*, and *Space SpA* (SME) as a commercial technology provider. For a comprehensive introduction to the RESTORE project see Degl'Innocenti et al. (2023).

11. Francesco di Marco Datini was a merchant from Prato, Italy, who established a successful commercial network across Europe during the fourteenth century. For more on Datini, see Hayez and Toccafondi (2012); Melis (1959, 1966).

12. The FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) Principles are guidelines designed to enhance data reuse by ensuring it is properly managed and shared in ways that facilitate both human and machine access (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

13. Galleries, libraries, archives and museums.

the partners. The case study described in this paper is the result of DARIAH-IT's involvement in H2IOSC and RESTORE.

The resources used to build the RESTORE case study include:

- archival descriptions of resources preserved by the Prato State Archive, composed of XML-EAD files and authority records compliant with the EAC-CPF Schema;¹⁴
- artwork records from Palazzo Pretorio Museum based on the ICCD (Italian Central Institute for Cataloguing and Documentation) standards for works of art, exported in XML format;¹⁵
- lemmatised corpus of Datini Letters from the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano, with the text encoded in a custom XML markup that maps lexical items, anthroponyms and toponyms;¹⁶
- images (JPG format) of documents from the state archive and the art collection of the museum.¹⁷

The raw resources were first stored in CKAN¹⁸ in their original format. To ensure the reliability and consistency of the datasets, particular attention was paid to data quality, considering the structural, syntactic and semantic levels. The heterogeneous nature of the original sources, produced over decades by different institutions and often lacking common standards, meant that a thorough process of data assessment, cleaning, normalisation and validation was necessary. During the ingestion phase, each dataset was subjected to structural checks to verify compliance with its respective schema (in the use case we are presenting: EAD, EAC-CPF, ICCD, TEI), ensuring integrity and syntactic alignment. Semantic quality was checked through compliance with controlled vocabularies, authority files and standardised mappings used in the project, which allowed for the disambiguation of entities (e.g. people, places, institutions) and reconciliation of variant forms. Ambiguities and inconsistencies, particularly common in legacy data, were resolved in collaboration with domain experts (archivists, philologists and curators), who played an active role in refining mappings and validating content. The use of persistent identifiers (Uniform Resource Identifiers, URI) further supported consistency across the datasets, enabling accurate linking and traceability. Documentation of

14. The Encoded Archival Description (EAD) is an Extensible Markup Language (XML) standard for encoding archival finding aids, facilitating the description of archival records and enhancing their discoverability. The EAC-CPF Schema is a standard for encoding contextual information about individuals, organisations and families associated with archival materials using XML. The standard is maintained by the Society of American Archivists in partnership with Berlin State Library.

15. The Italian Central Institute for Cataloguing and Documentation (Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione, ICCD) is an Italian governmental institute belonging to the Ministry of Culture, responsible for defining procedures, standards and tools for cataloguing and documenting cultural heritage.

16. The Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) is a text-centric community that develops and maintains guidelines for encoding digital texts, providing a set of XML tags to represent textual metadata, structure and other features of interest, primarily in the humanities.

17. All of the aforementioned resources were provided by the partner institutions of the RESTORE project. Specifically, the Prato State Archive furnished the archival descriptions, Palazzo Pretorio Museum contributed the artwork records, and the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano provided the lemmatised corpus of letters. The images were linked both to the Prato State Archive and Palazzo Pretorio Museum.

18. The Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN) is an open-source, web-based system for storing, cataloguing and distributing data.

the whole process was also carried out using tools like JupyterLab¹⁹ and Gogs²⁰ to ensure transparency, reproducibility and long-term sustainability of the integrated data environment.

The workflow is designed with the aim of creating a Linked Open Data (LOD) system that integrates the existing resources.²¹ Since it is also necessary to consider how the user can activate (i.e. execute) the steps described in the workflow, its design further implied defining:

- the information available to the user (and therefore acquirable by the machine);
- the format and presentation of the proposed solutions based on the user's request;
- the monitoring process for the operations performed (policies, data management plans or similar tools).

To address the needs of different possible target user groups (e.g. archivists, lexicographers and citizen scientists), the system also required tailored search and visualisation options. To avoid a one-size-fits-all approach, DARIAH-IT developed distinct data visualisation blocks (or contexts, i.e. custom views on data) to be hooked to the workflow for each user group.

In the RESTORE use case, we applied our workflow to the partially lemmatised corpus of Old Italian letters by Francesco di Marco Datini, provided by the Opera del Vocabolario Italiano, extracting both document metadata (sender, recipient, date, place, shelfmark, etc.) and embedded linguistic features to construct a comprehensive knowledge graph. The descriptive metadata was aligned with shared vocabularies and authority files, ensuring terminological consistency across archives, research institutes and museums. Traditional text-processing methods often falter when faced with the linguistic particularities of these documents, which include abbreviations, variant spellings and inconsistently referenced entities; all of these aspects can significantly impede digital research. To address these issues, in the parsing phase, custom algorithms—explicitly designed to handle the mapped peculiarities of Old Italian texts—resolve abbreviations and standardise orthographic variants. In the subsequent transformation phase, semantic alignment and CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM)-based ontology mapping unify divergent entity references and encode the original content into structured semantic triples. In the user interface, the integrated graph is presented through three coordinated panels: (1) alternating-views metadata: juxtaposing each source's records; (2) transcription viewer: offering diplomatic or critical editions (where available) with version-toggle controls; (3) lemma table: listing every annotated form, each marked with part of speech, hyperlemma and, where available, a hyperlink to its entry in the *Tesoro della Lingua Italiana* (TLIO) vocabulary.

19. JupyterLab is a web-based interactive development environment for Jupyter Notebooks, code and data; a Jupyter Notebook is an open-source browser application that allows users to create and share documents containing live code, visualisations and narrative text (such as explanations and descriptions).

20. Gogs is a self-hosted Git service written in Go, aiming to provide a simple, stable and extensible solution for hosting Git repositories.

21. On the benefits of an LOD knowledge ecology, see Brown and Simpson (2015).

This example illustrates the potential of the workflow for managing historical documents. In the following section, we offer a detailed explanation of its constituent components.

3 BEST PRACTICES

To increase efficiency, transparency, rapid dissemination of resources and facilitate reuse, it is good practice to store data according to open access policies and guidelines. The H2020 Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management state that “data should be as open as possible, as closed as necessary” (European Commission 2016, 4).²² These best practices are also comprehensively described and documented by the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) Principles, which provide simple guidelines to track and access data, integrate it with other data and reuse it in new research. In Europe, the Horizon 2020 framework programme and its Open Research Data Pilot have promoted activities related to the data collected, generated and used in research projects, strongly recommending the implementation of FAIR Principles. This is known as data management: the creation, organisation, structuring, storage and sharing of data. Resources can be made available through a wide variety of channels, each offering different platforms and user interfaces with distinct qualities and characteristics.

There are currently several publishing systems that start with direct data exchange,²³ while in the past they relied on traditional self-hosted web server downloads, generic or specialised data repositories, non-profit platform infrastructures or providers of commercial applications. The panorama of tools available for data management is broad²⁴ and there is already a large set of established solutions for publishing data, but the support of the FAIR Principles is still a hot topic.²⁵ These platforms currently provide the means to upload and publish datasets with a general, disciplinary or institutional purpose. They also meet the specific needs of multiple stakeholders in different usage scenarios.

Given the context described, the next section will outline the steps of the proposed workflow, illustrating how the technological and methodological choices directly address the identified requirements.

22. See also the “Open Access and Data Management” section of the H2020 Online Manual: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm.

23. An example is Edition Visualization Technology (EVT). EVT is an open-source software framework developed for the visualisation of critical and diplomatic digital editions encoded in TEI-XML. Designed to support scholarly editing, EVT allows for the visualisation of complex textual features, such as variants, annotations and manuscript structures, within an intuitive web interface. It has been widely adopted in digital philology projects due to its flexibility, user-friendliness and adherence to standards in the digital humanities. For more information, see <http://evt.labcd.unipi.it/>.

24. The European Commission recognises the significance of effective data management and its relevance across diverse academic disciplines. The panorama is complex and needs to be analysed to achieve the objective of a data-driven society: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy_en.

25. The discussion around FAIR data has generated several models for FAIRness evaluation. In 2020, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) published its FAIR Data Maturity Model (Research Data Alliance 2020). The EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) FAIR-IMPACT project has also proposed several solutions for evaluating FAIRness: <https://www.fair-impact.eu/fair-assessment-tools>. These few examples testify that there is still space for further discussion on the topic of evaluating the FAIR Principles.

4 WORKFLOW

4.1 STRUCTURE

The DARIAH-IT team defined a domain workflow for Old Italian text. A domain workflow may be composed of application workflows addressing specific tasks. Our workflow consists of seven main steps, each of which is an application workflow that performs a specific task needing to be completed:

- **Data acquisition from data providers:** the first step is acquiring data from the stakeholders. The data is therefore stored in a container that ensures swift management of the materials. This approach, first validated in RESTORE, has been specifically adapted for Old Italian texts by incorporating specialised XML annotation formats that manage the linguistic and lexical intricacies characteristic of these historical sources.
Reference technologies: CKAN, a well-known open-source platform for the publication of open data collections, aimed at organisations that publish data (national and local governments, companies and institutions) and wish to make it open and accessible to all.
- **Parsing of data on the Entity–Relationship model:** to foster interoperability and semantic coherence, data must be processed to ensure the conceptual alignment of information expressed through different semantic schemes and/or structures, by combining elements belonging to one dataset with those of another if both express the same concept. This can be achieved by processing data to clean, normalise and compare pieces of information.
Reference technologies: custom Python scripts developed by DARIAH-IT.
- **Data modelling:** the goal of data modelling is to formalise knowledge (i.e. translate it into a formal language), to minimise its ambiguity (typical of natural language)²⁶ and make it machine-readable so that inferences can be made about it using algorithms. Data becomes structured according to the rules of the reference ontology,²⁷ which will form the basis for transforming the datasets into semantic triples. Building on methods established within the RESTORE project, the modelling strategy adopted here explicitly addresses the semantic complexity of Old Italian textual data, integrating the CIDOC CRM ontology to manage philological nuances, palaeographic annotations and lexical ambiguity (Coradeschi et al. 2021).
Reference technologies: CIDOC CRM, a flexible ontology for structuring concepts and information in cultural heritage and museum documentation.
- **Data transformation:** the data is transformed into semantic triples to exploit the information identified during the mapping process.
Reference technologies: custom Python scripts developed by DARIAH-IT, the 3M tool.²⁸

26. On the theoretical foundations and implications of using ontologies to make sense of metadata, see Canning et al. (2022).

27. On scientific workflows and their underlying structures across disciplines, see Liu (2017), who identifies shared data “moves” in data-intensive research and the potential role of libraries in supporting brittle points in data trajectories.

28. The Mapping Memory Manager (3M) is a system designed to manage mapping files for XML file schema and underpins the 3M Editor: a suite of applications that helps experts complete the mapping definition process.

- **Code storage and documentation:** all steps in the workflow are to be documented and the code is to be accessible according to open science principles.²⁹
Reference technologies: Jupyter Notebook.
- **Importing data to the triplestore:** the semantic triples are imported in a storage for triples. The triples are atomic semantic statements following the SPO (Subject–Predicate–Object) structure enriched with persistent URIs for entities and properties. The resulting RDF data was loaded into a Virtuoso triplestore, enabling semantic querying and integration via SPARQL endpoints. The data can therefore be interrogated through semantic queries.
Reference technologies: OpenLink Virtuoso, a multi-model data server offering a platform-independent solution for data management, access and integration. Virtuoso is thus a hybrid database that combines the functionality of a traditional Relational Database Management System (RDBMS), Database Management System (DBMS), virtual database, RDF, XML, web application server and file server into a single system. The Virtuoso triplestore also enables a SPARQL endpoint.
- **Semantic data browsing:** through semantic queries, the data can now be interrogated to exploit information and generate new knowledge.
Reference technologies: there are two main ways to use the SPARQL endpoint of the DARIAH-IT triplestore to harness the data and perform semantic searches: Facet Browser and LodLive (visual conceptual browser). Facet Browser is an interface tool integrated with SPARQL endpoints in Virtuoso databases, allowing users to explore and filter linked data by facets—categories of metadata such as date, author or location. In digital humanities, this tool is particularly useful for navigating complex datasets by narrowing down results based on specific attributes, making it easier for researchers to discover relationships and patterns within large cultural datasets. LodLive is a visualisation tool for exploring Linked Open Data through SPARQL endpoints, such as those hosted on Virtuoso. It provides an interactive, graph-based view of RDF data, showing connections between entities in real time. In digital humanities, LodLive enhances research by visually mapping relationships between entities, such as historical figures, places and events, helping scholars contextualise and analyse data within a broader network of cultural information.

29. Open science is a movement aimed at making scientific research and its dissemination accessible to all levels of society. Its principles include open access to publications, open data, open-source software, open methodology, open peer review and open educational resources. See <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>.

WORKFLOW		DATA		
COMPLEX	UNITARY	TECH/PLATFORM	INPUT	OUTPUT
DATA MANAGEMENT TOOL SUITE (RAISE-BE)	DATA CLEANING AND PROCESSING		XML-based standards: EAD, EAC, ICCD, TEI	CSV files
	DATA MAPPING AND MODELLING		CSV files	Semantic triples: TTL Ontology (CIDOC, FOAF) & Vocabulary (GETTY, REPETTI, ICONCLASS)
SEMANTIC DATA INGESTION TOOL SUITE	DATA IMPORT		Semantic triples: TTL	UPLOAD TO VIRTUOSO
DATA VISUALISATION TOOL SUITE (RAISE-FE)	QUERY MANAGER	JAVASCRIPT	QUERY SPARQL	JSON
	DATA BROWSING		GUI plain text	Aggregated data visualisation / data clusters (JS, HTML, CSS)
RAISE ATLANTE MODULE	DATA VISUALISATION		JSON	MAPS & TIMELINE (leaflet.js, timeline.js)
DATA VISUALISATION SPECIALISED TOOLS	IMAGE AND TEXT VIEW	EVT	XML TEI standard	Digital Scholarly Edition Visualization (Online)
	STORYTELLING		Plain text, images	Virtual Exhibition Online
	LOD VIEW		Endpoint SPARQL	Graph representation
DATA STORAGE	WORKFLOW CONFIGURATION AND DOCUMENTATION		PARSER, DATA etc.	Workflow, code, and data in a web-based interactive development environment
	STORAGE OF DEVELOPED COMPONENTS		PARSER, DATA etc.	Components in a GIT repository
	RAW DATA INGESTION		XML-based standards: EAD, EAC, ICCD, TEI	Visualisation and storage of original datasets

Figure 1: workflow description

Figure 1 summarises the workflow steps to ensure that textual data—regardless of its origin, format or institutional context—can be integrated into a unified, semantically expressive knowledge base that meets the FAIR Principles and supports cross-domain interoperability.

4.2 MODELLING

The suite of tools developed to manage the RESTORE use case applied to the described workflow has been deposited in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) Open Marketplace as “RAISE—Restore dATA Integration Suite.”³⁰ The SSH Open Marketplace serves as a central hub where the SSH research community can deposit, discover and share research workflows. As a discovery platform, the SSH Open Marketplace brings together a wide range of curated digital resources (including tools, services, datasets, publications and training materials) and contextualises them to support every stage of the research data life cycle (Barbot et al. 2023b). Within this environment, workflows play a key role as structured, step-by-step representations of research methodologies, linking each phase of the process with relevant resources (Barbot et al. 2023a). Moreover, the workflows developed within

30. See RAISE on the SSH Open Marketplace at <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/plyy0d>. For more information, see Degl’Innocenti et al. (2021).

DARIAH-IT can certainly benefit from comparison with other experiences described in the SSH Open Marketplace. In fact, other research projects deal with the same issues in data management.

The value of the DARIAH-IT workflow lies in its ability to handle the semantic integration of highly heterogeneous cultural heritage data, including archival descriptions, museum catalogues and lemmatised textual corpora. Unlike more generalised workflows, it is specifically designed to address the challenges posed by fragmented legacy resources, varied metadata standards and domain-specific semantic ambiguities. Its complex architecture, established by the organisation in connected blocks, ensures both technical robustness and scholarly relevance. Moreover, the workflow incorporates mechanisms for differentiated data visualisation and user interaction, recognising diverse digital literacy levels and research needs. By combining rigorous methodological principles with domain expertise, DARIAH-IT enables a level of precision, contextualisation and cross-resource interoperability that significantly enhances the study of Old Italian within the mapped context.³¹

Underlying this complex workflow is the delicate role of ontologies, which by definition are formal representations of knowledge shared by a community. An ontology defines entities and properties to describe a knowledge domain in a formal organisation. In the described workflow, ontologies are used to model data in order to:

- describe the structure and hierarchy of the formal models for encoding data (e.g. archival data like EAD), information about the producing entities (e.g. EAC), and the ministerial records used to describe cultural heritage (ICCD);
- describe the legacy of the resources, especially the context of provenance;
- allow integration with other ontologies and conceptual models related to more specific domains (e.g. Ric-O³²).

As a Conceptual Reference Model, the DARIAH-IT team chose the CIDOC CRM for its consolidated use in the social sciences, humanities and cultural heritage domain.³³ CIDOC CRM is a theoretical and practical tool for information integration in the field of cultural heritage. It achieves this by providing definitions and a formal

31. In the SSH Open Marketplace, several workflows are identified as particularly relevant to the themes addressed by the RESTORE project and serve as useful comparative references. The workflow [LODification of Bibliographical Data: Zotero to Wikibase Migration with ZotWb](#) provides insight into lightweight strategies for transforming bibliographic metadata into Linked Open Data, particularly through reconciliation and semantic enrichment. [A Workflow to Publish Collections as Data: The Case of Cultural Heritage Data Spaces](#) offers a clear framework for ensuring ethical openness, transparency and computational reuse of cultural heritage resources, emphasising practical publishing practices. The [Bibliographical Data Science: From Catalogues to Research Data](#) workflow demonstrates robust methods for harmonising and validating structured metadata, especially in multilingual and transnational contexts, underscoring the importance of authority reconciliation. Finally, [Making Data Interoperable for the Semantic Web](#) outlines a technically comprehensive process for aligning domain-specific datasets with ontological models, emphasising vocabulary alignment and triplestore publication. While these workflows address specific facets of data transformation and publication, the RESTORE workflow integrates many of their principles into a unified, domain-specific pipeline tailored to the complexities of historical and linguistic resources.

32. Records in Contexts-Ontology (Ric-O) is an OWL ontology for describing archival record resources and their contextual entities; see <https://www.ica.org/resource/records-in-contexts-ontology/>.

33. Suffice it to say that the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) reference model is also based on the CIDOC CRM ontology: “SSHOCro is modelled as an extension of the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM)” (Bekiari et al. 2022).

structure to describe implicit and explicit concepts and relationships used in cultural heritage documentation and of general interest for querying and exploring such data. Significantly, such models, also known as formal ontologies, enable data from heterogeneous sources to be integrated.³⁴

5 TOWARDS A WORKFLOW FOR DIGITAL EDITIONS

The workflow described in this article has been designed to address the peculiarities associated with Old Italian texts, which present methodological and technological challenges requiring dedicated solutions. Compared to modern Italian, managing Old Italian texts is complex due to their linguistic variability, non-standardised orthography, palaeographic abbreviations and the instability of manuscript and early printed textual transmission. The phases of data acquisition, parsing, modelling, RDF transformation and semantic querying included in this workflow specifically reflect the peculiarities of medieval documents: the adoption of CIDOC CRM, specialised lemmatisation, textual collation and representation through *stemma codicum*, directly addresses philological requirements absent from workflows designed for contemporary texts, which will be fully implemented in the Digital Philology Hub, a DARIAH pilot in the H2IOSC project.

To illustrate an extension of the workflow's capabilities, consider a corpus transmitted through multiple medieval manuscripts, some of which have already been digitised in early pioneering editions. The materials to be edited digitally may include high-resolution manuscript images, diplomatic or critical transcriptions, critical apparatus, variants and annotations.

Researchers working with such richly layered data face considerable challenges. They must integrate transcriptions, lemmatisation, textual variants, glossaries and metadata, and link these to external digital resources (for example, manuscript catalogues, lexical databases and other scholarly repositories). Conventional tools typically fall short in supporting these integrated scholarly workflows, focusing on specific tasks instead of the whole study process.

If modern Italian texts were involved, many orthographic and linguistic normalisation procedures would be unnecessary, significantly reducing the complexity of parsing and textual annotation tasks. The tools involved should therefore be adjusted or trained to deal with modern Italian. The steps of the applicative workflow may remain the same, but each unitary workflow (i.e. step) composing the whole process would need to be revised to deal with different kinds of texts.

Nevertheless, while designed to address the peculiarities of Old Italian, the modular nature of our workflow enables it to be scaled and adapted efficiently to other textual traditions facing similar challenges. Indeed, the semantic modelling provides a flexible structure that can be readily adjusted or expanded upon, allowing researchers working on texts from different historical periods or linguistic contexts to apply similar approaches to their specific needs.

The workflow described in this paper lays the foundation to overcome these obstacles by enabling the structured integration of heterogeneous textual data into a

34. On the transformation of controlled vocabularies into semantic resources, see Vogeler (2025) for an example applied to the field of sigillography.

unified digital environment. It also paves the way for advanced visualisations, such as mapping the provenance of historical documents geographically and through chronological timelines.

Within the H2IOSC project, this workflow is further enhanced to systematically support tasks including manuscript transcription and lemmatisation, precise textual collation, the creation and interrogation of critical apparatuses and glossaries, and seamless linkage to external scholarly resources.

Specifically, DARIAH-IT is coordinating the development of two pilot initiatives: the aforementioned Digital Philology Hub and the Digital Heritage and Memory Hub. These pilots aim to support the implementation of custom Virtual Research Environments to execute scientific workflows within the H2IOSC federation of research infrastructures. In the context of managing textual resources from medieval sources, a key methodological reference has been Leonardi (2021), whose work outlines the fundamental steps of philological analysis. These steps were critical for addressing the specific complexities inherent in processing and interpreting early Italian textual materials. By explicitly addressing specific data needs identified through practical collaborations (such as RESTORE and H2IOSC) and clearly integrating advanced technological solutions, the workflow described in this article offers a coherent and replicable methodological model. Future studies will be able to adapt this workflow to other historical linguistic contexts, taking advantage of its proven ability to effectively handle textual, linguistic and semantic complexities. Indeed, the structured workflow developed here, rooted in the experiences of RESTORE and further refined within the H2IOSC pilot projects, provides a robust and replicable model for academic digital editions of ancient Italian texts, thus significantly advancing the methodological practices of digital philology.

REFERENCES

- Ascoli, Graziadio Isaia. 1882. "L'Italia dialettale." *Archivio glottologico italiano* 8:98–128.
- Barbot, Laure, Elena Battaner Moro, Stefan Buddenbohm, Cesare Concordia, Maja Dolinar, Matej Ďurčo, Edward Gray, et al. 2023a. "Creating a DH Workflow in the SSH Open Marketplace." Zenodo. Version v1, 30 June. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8107729>.
- Barbot, Laure, Elena Battaner Moro, Stefan Buddenbohm, Cesare Concordia, Maja Dolinar, Matej Ďurčo, Edward Gray, et al. 2023b. "The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace: Contextualising Digital Resources in a Registry." Zenodo. Version v1, 30 June. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8107637>.
- Bekiari, Chrysoula, Athina Kritsotaki, Eleni Tsoulouha, and Maria Theodoridou. 2022. "D4.20 SSHOCro (final version)." Zenodo. Version 1.0. 27 April. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6771757>.
- Brown, Susan, and John Simpson. 2015. "An Entity By Any Other Name: Linked Open Data as a Basis for a Decentered, Dynamic Scholarly Publishing Ecology." *Scholarly and Research Communication* 6 (2). <https://doi.org/10.22230/src.2015v6n2a212>.
- Canning, Erin, Susan Brown, Sarah Roger, and Kimberley Martin. 2022. "The Power to Structure: Making Meaning from Metadata Through Ontologies." *KULA: Knowledge Creation, Dissemination, and Preservation Studies* 6 (3): 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.18357/kula.169>.
- Castellani, Arrigo. 1980. "Sulla formazione del 'tipo fonetico italiano'." In *Saggi di linguistica e filologia italiana e romanza (1946–1976)*, 73–95. Roma: Salerno.

- Coradeschi, Francesco, Emiliano Degl’Innocenti, Carmen Di Meo, Maurizio Sanesi, Alessia Spadi, and Federica Spinelli. 2021. “CIDOC CRM Mapping for the Integration of RESTORE Project Resources.” *Umanistica Digitale* 5 (11): 47–70. <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.2532-8816/13690>.
- Degl’Innocenti, Emiliano, Leonardo Canova, Francesco Coradeschi, Carmen Di Meo, Maurizio Sanesi, Alessia Spadi, and Federica Spinelli. 2023. “The RESTORE Project: A Final Review.” In *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 3365:167–179. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3365/paper5.pdf>.
- Degl’Innocenti, Emiliano, Carmen Di Meo, Francesco Coradeschi, Maurizio Sanesi, Elisa Brunoni, Athina Kritsotaki, and Eleni Tsoulouha. 2021. “MS49 Heritage Science and Humanities Pilot Alpha Release.” Zenodo. Version v1.0, 31 March. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5217113>.
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation. 2016. *H2020 Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*. Version 3.0, 26 July. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf.
- Hayez, Jérôme, and Diana Toccafondi, eds. 2012. *Palazzo Datini a Prato. Una casa fatta per durare mille anni*. Firenze: Polistampa.
- Leonardi, Lino. 2021. “Filologia digitale del Medioevo italiano.” *Griseldaonline* 20 (2): 77–89. <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.1721-4777/12817>.
- Lepschy, Anna Laura, and Giulio Lepschy. 2006. *La lingua italiana: Storia, varietà dell’uso, grammatica*. Milano: Bompiani.
- Liu, Alan. 2017. “Assessing Data Workflows for Common Data ‘Moves’ Across Disciplines.” *Alan Liu* (May). <https://doi.org/10.21972/G21593>.
- Marazzini, Claudio. 2009. *La lingua italiana: Profilo storico*. Bologna: Il Mulino.
- Melis, Federigo. 1959. “A proposito di un nuovo volume sul ‘Mercante di Prato’.” *Economia e storia* 6:747–763.
- Melis, Federigo. 1966. “Il problema Datini. Una necessaria messa a punto.” *Nuova Rivista Storica* 50:682–709.
- Petrarca, Francesco. 2004. *Canzoniere*. Edited by Marco Santagata. Milan: Mondadori.
- Research Data Alliance, FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. 2020. “FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines.” Zenodo. Version 1.0, 25 June. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>.
- Salvi, Giampaolo, and Lorenzo Renzi, eds. 2010. *Grammatica dell’italiano antico*. Bologna: Il Mulino.
- Schiaparelli, Luigi. 1924. “Note paleografiche. Sulla data e provenienza del cod. 89 della Biblioteca Capitolare di Verona (orazionale mozarabico).” *Archivio Storico Italiano* 1:106–117.
- Tomasin, Lorenzo. 2019. *Il caos e l’ordine. Le lingue romanze nella storia della cultura europea*. Turin: Piccola Biblioteca Einaudi.
- Vogeler, Georg. 2025. “Transforming the *Vocabulaire de la Sigillographie* into a Semantic Web Resource.” Special collection, “Digital Approaches to Medieval Sigillography,” ed. Martina Filosa, Claes Neufeind, and Claudia Sode, *Digital Medievalist* 18 (1). <https://doi.org/10.16995/dm.17137>.
- Wilkinson, Mark, Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.” *Scientific Data* 3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

Seeking Contact-Induced Syntactic Change in Endangered Languages: A Methodology for Building a Morphosyntactically Annotated Corpus for Corfioto

Georgios Vardakis, University of Padua
Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio, University of Padua

Language contact is a ubiquitous phenomenon in the world's languages manifested at all levels of linguistic analysis. While the role of corpora for research in language contact phenomena in widely spoken languages is well-established, contributions to contact linguistics via the compilation, annotation and archiving of corpora in endangered languages are recent but very promising. In the era marked by the most significant decline of linguistic diversity in the history of world languages, research in developing and deploying technical tools and methods dedicated to the mobilization of large digital corpora keeps demonstrating an ever-growing interest in integrating the collaboration of NLP researchers and formal, computational, and fieldwork linguists in language documentation and analysis. This paper presents current results of a work-in-progress project on the aims, goals, and the methods for compiling a state-of-the-art morphosyntactically annotated corpus of Corfioto, the endangered Italo-Romance variety of the Corfiot Jews.¹ In particular, it outlines the workflow for building, archiving, managing and annotating the first mixed language corpus of oral and written data of Corfioto based on the Universal Dependencies (UD) framework, as well as the designing and the implementation of an application for the Interactive MorPhosyntactic Annotation of CorfioTo (IMPACT). The creation and the annotation of the corpus ultimately serve three goals: i) attain a quantitative analysis of variation and contact-induced syntactic change in the complementation system of Corfioto; ii) enable the creation of a gold standard and the training of a model for the linguistic annotation of all linguistic data in the Universal Dependencies framework; and iii) contribute to the ever-growing research in developing language resources and tools for endangered and low-resourced languages in the fields of computational linguistics and NLP via the collaboration of computational linguists, NLP researchers and formal, computational and fieldwork linguists.

1. Introduction

Contact-induced change (Seifart 2019) is a multifaceted and ubiquitous phenomenon in the world's languages and a property of the adaptive capacity of the faculty of language to recombine and rearrange linguistic features into new structure, in contexts where the speaker is exposed to languages, varieties and repertoires considered different (Aboh 2020, forthcoming). Since the seminal works of Weinreich (1953) and Haugen (1953), the study of language contact has evolved into an ever-growing field of interdisciplinary research in language sciences (for a historical overview see Bidese 2017; 2023; Adamou & Matras 2021; Mufwene & Escobar 2022). The field flows with different perspectives on the study of language contact which are mainly subsumed under the historical and the synchronic perspective (Adamou 2016). The quantitative and qualitative power of corpus linguistic methods has been crucial in our understanding of central issues in language contact, including code-switching in different contact settings and both in top-down and bottom-down approaches (see Adamou 2019 and the literature therein). The position of synchronic analysis in contact-induced phenomena for major languages is well established. However, the role of the documentation of lesser-known, non-

¹ Parts of this paper are based on previous publications (Vardakis & Di Nunzio 2022) and have been presented on the occasion of the 26th International Conference on the Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries 2022 (Padua, 2022) and the Workshop *Creating Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages* of the DARIAH Working Groups Research Data Management and Multilingual DH, (Hamburg, 2024).

standard and endangered languages (Hale et al. 1992; Himmelmann 1998; 2006, Woodbury 2011) in the study of language contact and language change has been acknowledged only recently (see O'Shanessy 2011; Aikhenvald 2020; Adamou 2021), now facing significant growth. While we are facing the most accelerating decline of linguistic diversity in the history of the world's languages (see Kik et al. 2021; Adamou 2024), research in developing and deploying computational tools and methods for resource creation and mobilization in language documentation (see Berez-Kroeker et al. 2023) via the interdisciplinary collaboration of NLP researchers, computational, formal and fieldwork linguists (Anastasopoulos 2019; Galliot et al. 2022) is an ever-growing domain of inquiry. Initiatives for the creation, management and archiving of written and oral corpora of endangered languages contribute not only to their documentation but to their use for the advancement of our understanding of language change based both in qualitative and quantitative terms (Adamou 2019). Still, as is the case for other languages, the compilation of multilingual corpora is hindered by numerous time-consuming tasks, including the transcription 'bottleneck' and manual annotation (see Travis and Torres Cacoullos 2013).

Regarding contact-induced structural change, statistical modeling adapted to the specificities of small free-speech multilingual large corpora from lesser-described languages can contribute to perceiving the mechanisms and constraints of replicated patterns covering a broader sample, providing greater diversity in the study of contact settings (Adamou 2016). Moreover, quantitative measuring of the degree to which mixed languages combine different portions of the grammatical and lexical subsystems of more than one source language is considered a crucial factor for determining different types of mixed languages as well as their typology (for a recent overview see O'Shanessy 2020). Moreover, it offers researchers a more empirical and verifiable base for achieving a consensus on the definition of convergence or contact-induced syntactic change (see Grant 2020), over what constitutes a change, how to recognize and distinguish it from inherent variability and how to determine whether it is contact-induced, via more reliable analyses of principled collections of bilingual performance, including data-driven reports of rates of occurrence and conditioning of variant choice (Poplack 2020: 54).

The important steps in integrating computational tools to endangered and lesser-described languages (see Anastasopoulos et al. 2020) serve a variety of different domains ranging from the facilitation and acceleration of the language documentation process, such as automatic alignment of corpora from lesser-known languages (Michaud et al. 2012), automatic phonemic recognition (Michaud et al. 2018), as well as progress in various tasks, including morphological and syntactic analysis including part-of-speech tagging; parsing and sequence labeling tasks, including code-switching identification, text labeling tasks; stylistic analysis; and text generation tasks, including machine translation or summarization. In this direction, the creation of the first morphosyntactically annotated corpus of written and oral data of Corfioto will offer the linguists community access to a previously undocumented variety within a FAIR data approach, and will enable statistically significant results on the contact-induced effect of clausal complementation based on the annotation of the whole corpus, via automatic annotation based on the creation of a gold standard.

2. Corfioto, the Endangered Variety of the Corfiot Jews

Corfioto (autoglossonym) is a critically endangered Italo-Romance variety traditionally spoken by the Corfiot Jews in Corfu, Greece. Today, it is still spoken by a small number of speakers mainly in Israel, as well as in Greece, Italy, Switzerland and Southern America. Sociolinguistic data and linguistic descriptions of the written and oral linguistic heritage of the Corfiot Jews highlight the role of language contact between Romance, Greek and Hebrew in

the lexicon and the grammar of the Corfiot Jews (see Mücke 2019; Vardakis 2023; forthcoming). Besides the limited sources of documentation in written data dating to the previous century (Gottheil & Belleli 1901–1906; Perotti 1909; 1910; Cortelazzo 1946, 1947, 1948; Levi 1961; Levi & Leydi 1959-1969; Colafemmina 2006) and recent academic works and publications on the linguistic analysis of original data collected in fieldwork (Nachtmann 2002; Mücke 2019; Vardakis 2019; 2021; 2023; forthcoming), a purely linguistic description and analysis of the diachronic and synchronic aspects of Corfioto, and the role of language contact in its genesis are yet to come.

Despite the lack of official data regarding the level of language vitality and endangerment of Corfioto, according to the scale of six factors (henceforward, F1 to F6) proposed in Brenzinger et al. (2003), we estimate that: F1) the degree of Intergenerational Language Transmission of Corfioto is (2) i.e., severely endangered; F2) and F3), as for the absolute number of speakers and the proportion of speakers within the Total Reference Population, the language is critically endangered; F4) besides its use by the speakers for documentation purposes, Corfioto is used in highly limited domains, mainly on rare occasions of gatherings and cultural manifestations of the Corfiot Jewish life, such as cuisine; F5) regarding its Response to New Domains and Media, Corfioto is defined as inactive; F6) as for the Accessibility of Written Materials for Language Education and literacy, a practical orthography is known to the community and some material is being written. Corfioto is not taught and besides a limited number of glossaries compiled by speakers in Hebrew, Greek, and Romance script, Corfioto lacks any standardized orthography.

Regarding available corpora, to our knowledge, no annotated corpus of Corfioto exists to date. Linguistic research on the variety has focused mainly on the description and the analysis of the morphosyntax and the syntax of finite-type clausal complementation. Besides Nachtmann's transcribed recordings in Italian script (2002) and Vardakis (2019), all recent and contemporary oral data attested dates are limited to utterances produced via free-speech production or elicitation (see Mücke 2019; Vardakis 2019; 2021; 2023). In fact, among all different outcomes of language contact attested in the variety, finite-type complementation is the one that has received particular attention in the literature. This is indeed a result of the significant interest on the areal diffusion of infinitival retreat and its replacement by finite-type complementation in Corfioto. This is the second research question that the compilation of the corpus aims to address.

3. The Linguistic Issue Under Study

The replacement of infinitive by finite complementation is the most attested and eminent syntactic feature of Corfioto and the most perspicuous and widely spread morphosyntactic feature of the Balkan Sprachbund (Joseph 1983; Mišeska-Tomić 2006; Friedman & Joseph, forthcoming). Unlike Venetian (1), considered as the main language from which Corfioto has inherited most of its lexical and morphological elements, clausal complementation in contemporary Corfioto shows significant infinitival retreat and replacement by finite clausal complements. In Corfioto, finite clausal complements are all introduced by a homophonous grammatical element *ke*, with distinct distributional properties, while the complement predicate is encoded via a verb form indexing person and number, either in subject co-reference or disjoint reference with the matrix, as shown in (2).²

- (1) *te=vogi-o* *parl-ar*
 2SCL=want-1SG talk-INF

² DET=determiner; F=feminine; INF=infinitive; M=male; NEG=negation; OCL=object clitic; PL=plural; PRT=particle; SCL=subject clitic; SG=singular

'I want to talk to you'
Venetian (Ferguson 2007: 139)

- (2) *vój-o ke=te= párl-o*
want-1SG PRT=OCL.2SG=talk-1SG
'I want to talk to you'
Corfioto (Vardakis, fieldwork 2019)

Although elicited data show robust cohesion in finite complementation constructions across informants, limited cases of infinitive complement clauses in spontaneous speech data need to be integrated in the analysis and to be compared with those in other corpora suggesting infinitive reduction but no clear loss (Mücke 2019; Vardakis, fieldwork 2019-2023).

- (3) *no bizón-a parl-ár italián*
NEG need-3SG speak-INF Italian
'But we must not speak Italian.'
Corfioto (Vardakis, fieldwork 2019)

- (4) *le tsinkue son ke skriv-er*
DET.PL.F five know PRT write-INF
'I can write in these five.'
Corfioto (Vardakis, fieldwork 2019)

Oral data show clear intra-speaker variation in complement clauses introduced by the same matrix verb even in intrasentential contexts:

- (5) *bizón-a liy-ár, [...] ke lo ligh-ano*
need.3SG tie-INF PRT OCL.3SG.M tie-3PL
'It is necessary to tie, tie, for them to tie him.'

At the level of linguistic analysis, the creation of the corpus will enable a quantitative approach to variation between finite and infinitival complementation, revealing the environments which are more prone to the retreat or the retention of the phenomenon. The third axe of the creation of the corpus serves the aim of its annotation and its digital representation within the Universal Dependencies framework along with other lesser-studied languages.

4. A methodology for the creation and management of a morphosyntactically annotated corpus of Corfioto

A major future step that needs to be taken in view of the creation of the first language resource for Corfioto is the creation of a morphosyntactically annotated corpus of Corfioto. This section presents a structured methodology on the progress made in building and annotating the corpus to date, as well as directions for the future development of the project. The methodology as conceived in its current form means to i) integrate the different tasks required for the annotation of morphosyntactic features in any language variety; ii) facilitate the reproducibility of the experiments; and iii) include an in-depth linguistic analysis to furthering our understanding of contact-induced syntactic change in Corfioto.

The workflow adopted for the creation of the corpus is divided in four major steps: building, managing, annotating, and archiving the corpus. The output of the workflow aims at creating the first corpus of mixed oral and written data of Corfioto, the endangered Italo-

Romance variety of Corfu which is based on a) the transcription of more than 30 hours of i) original oral linguistic data (produced via free, semi-structured methods or elicitation) collected in fieldwork with the collaboration of at least 10 consultants in Greece, Israel and Italy from 2019 to date and ii) audio and video recordings dated to the previous century found in institutional and personal archives and offered to us by the informants and; b) written glossaries compiled by speakers or groups of speakers, which contain words and short phrases in Latin, Greek and Hebrew script together with translation equivalents in Italian, French, Greek and Hebrew.

The oral data set are transcribed using ELAN while written sources will be digitized by means of Optical Character Recognition (OCR) software. Following current standards, we opt for near-phonological transcription in Latin script which follows unified spelling conventions established in our metadata. Besides the transcription and the tokenization, morphosyntactic annotation at the morpheme level and translation of the data is carried out on ELAN. All transcribed texts are extracted in a .txt format. Notice that annotation in ELAN may allow for distinct morphological via different L1, L2 and L3 tagging, while syntactic annotation in the Universal Dependencies framework would not allow further tagging of the languages involved.

A crucial step in the compilation of the corpus is the production and the maintenance of the XML metadata including information on the authors, the date and place of the drafting or publication of the written sources, the type of original documents, and sociolinguistic information on the consultants and date and place of recordings. Metadata are also stored in XML data standards, including Dublin Core³ or Open Language Archives Community⁴ or the Component Metadata Infrastructure⁵ provided by CLARIN.

The first data set to be used for morphosyntactic annotation is limited to the corpus transcribed to date. Following the transcription of data and the transformation of the data to text, the compilation of a fraction of the final dataset will serve for the creation of a gold standard which will allow training and evaluating a model and thus create a data set to facilitate and accelerate the morphosyntactic annotation of the whole dataset. Since the goal of the project is to exploit and process oral data to produce specific rules on the quantitative identification of diachronic and synchronic variation and change in complementation constructions in Corfioto, emphasis will be given on the distribution of variation in complementation constructions in the compilation of a representative corpus. Of course, the limited size of the documentary-linguistic character of the corpus cannot deal with theoretical issues regarding how to obtain a balanced and representative corpus of such a low-resource language, and which is confronted with general attrition under the pressure of the dominant language.

A central task is that of the selection of a representative sample of data which will be annotated to create a gold annotated standard that will be used later to train and evaluate the model. Morphosyntactic annotation is a central activity in the documentation workflow aiming to transform raw linguistic data into primary data that can be derived via analytical or presentational methods and turned into linguistic analyses, teaching materials or useful language product (Himmelman 2006; 2012). Morphosyntactic annotation consists in the segmentation and labeling of form-meaning units based on cross-linguistic or language-specific categories, such as Part-of-Speech tagging. The morphosyntactic annotation on IMPACT will be carried out using the Universal Dependencies (UD) framework (de Marneffe et al. 2021).

Inspired by the descriptive and the theoretical tradition of dependency grammar (de Marneffe & Nivre 2019), the UD framework is a framework aiming at developing a framework for cross-linguistically consistent morphosyntactic annotation (Nivre et al. 2016). UD adopts a lexicalist view of syntax, in which syntactic words are the basic units of annotation. The

³ <https://www.dublincore.org/> [last access on 22/10/2024]

⁴ <http://www.language-archives.org/> [last access on 22/10/2024]

⁵ <https://www.clarin.eu/content/cmdi-component-metadata-infrastructure> [last access on 22/10/2024]

framework, which has been so far applied to 161 languages⁶, aims "to capture similarities and idiosyncrasies among typologically different languages and support multilingual research in NLP and linguistics by enabling sound comparative evaluation across languages, crosslinguistic learning to support low-resource languages, development of multilingual natural language understanding systems, and comparative linguistic studies (de Marneffe & Nivre 2019: 209-210). A significant number of tools for the morphosyntactic annotation of corpora based on UD are available today e.g., Arborator-Grew (Guibon et al. 2020)

To summarize, the step-by-step methodology conceived in this work will facilitate the reproducibility of the experiments, integrate the different elements required for the annotation of morphosyntactic features in any language variety, and include an in-depth linguistic analysis to furthering our understanding of contact-induced syntactic change in Corfioto. The methodology of the management and analysis of the linguistic data collected with the interviews is the following:

1. Data Collection and Compilation: gather a substantial dataset of texts, representing various text types and registers. Ensure that the dataset covers a wide range of syntactic structures and linguistic features.
2. Preprocessing: Clean and preprocess the dataset, including tokenization, sentence segmentation, and lowercasing. Ensure that the text is in a format suitable for parsing.
3. Selection of a Universal Dependency (UD) Parser: Choose a UD parser that supports Corfioto or a closely related language or family, e.g., Italo-Romance.
4. Annotation Guidelines: Develop annotation guidelines specific to Corfioto's morphosyntactic features. Define dependency relations, part-of-speech tags, and other linguistic categories relevant to the language.
5. Create a Gold Standard: Annotate a representative portion of the Corfioto dataset manually to create a gold standard. This annotated data will serve as the basis for training and evaluation.
6. Train, Validate, and Evaluate Model: Train the selected UD parser using the annotated Corfioto data. Fine-tune the model to ensure it captures the language's unique morphosyntactic features.
7. Documentation and Sharing: Document the integration process, guidelines, and the trained model. Make the parser accessible to other researchers interested in analyzing Corfiot or similar languages. Engage with the linguistics and NLP research community, sharing insights, best practices, and resources.

The annotation of the golden standard today is limited to a total of 117 sentences coming from transcribed oral data from two distinct documents. In most of the cases, the sentences are segmented at the prosodic level whereas syntactic and semantic criteria are taken into consideration for the segmentation of sentences that are too long. All the sentences include clausal complements of the types described in this thesis, which are marked by the subordinator/modal marker *ke*. Since no prior spelling conventions of the variety exist, tokenization of the dataset is based on 'syntactic words', which are defined at a language-specific level. Tokenization includes separation of clitic particles and argumental clitics from the verb host. Hence, the sequence *ke=ti=ghe=lo=dágha* (PREP=SCL=IOCL=OCL.3SG.M=give.SUBJ.2/3SG) is manually separated into five words. Morphological contractions e.g., preposition-article *al* (PREP.EL) are kept. Syllabic accent is kept on words with more than two syllables. Proper nouns are represented only using the initial

⁶ According to the last release on 05/05/2024 the Version 2.14 includes a total of 283 treebanks for 161 languages <http://hdl.handle.net/11234/1-5502> [last access on 22/10/2024].

letter to protect anonymity of the participants. Preprocessing of the data includes lowercasing for all tokens in the corpus, but for the initial letter of proper names which is capitalized. Punctuation is kept only whenever relevant at the prosodic and/or syntactic and semantic level e.g., interrogative or exclamative clauses. Sentences from the same audio file are assigned a unique number common single number representing the common audio file as well as a second integer for the single number of each sentence. A first automatic annotation is performed via the use of an existing UD annotation treebank used for a genetically affiliated language, preferably a Romance language. At this point, the automatic pre-annotation stage has been performed using the UD_Italian-VIT corpus.⁷

5. IMPACT System

IMPACT is an application designed and implemented using the R shiny framework for Web Interactivity, the datatable (DT) package⁸ to review the annotation, and the textplot package⁹ for text visualization and analysis. The current interface of the IMPACT system is shown in Figure 1. The user can 1) select the sentence to analyze, then 2) transliterate and translate the original sentence, 3) automatically parse the text, 4) interact (edit and modify) with the morphosyntactic annotations produced by the UD parser, and 5) analyze the corresponding dependency parser tree. IMPACT is an integrated Web environment which has been designed and implemented to allow for on-the-fly adjustments, enabling users to fine-tune annotation results or modify display preferences. While the application has been created to serve as a valuable tool for linguistic analysis of Corfioto, it aspires to become a valuable tool for automatic morphosyntactic annotation, especially of genetically affiliated languages. The work-in-progress made here aims at contributing to the creation of a first gold standard of the variety, as has been already done for other minority and under-resource languages (see Millour et al. 2024; Karahóga et al., 2022).

An example of the morphosyntactic annotation and the representation of the syntactic dependencies of an utterance in the first dataset is presented in the figures below:

	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	V7	V8
sentence_id	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
token_id	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
token	bizóna	ce	camémo	úna	paréa	,	úna	tséna
upos	AUX	AUX	VERB	DET	NOUN	PUNCT	DET	NOUN
head_token_id	3	1	0	5	3	3	8	5
dep_rel	aux	mark	root	det	obj	punct	det	parataxis

Figure 1. Morphosyntactic annotation in IMPACT

⁷ https://universaldependencies.org/treebanks/it_vit/index.html [last access on 22/10/2024]

⁸ <https://github.com/rstudio/DT> [last access on 14/11/2024]

⁹ <https://github.com/bnosac/textplot> [last access on 14/11/2024]

Figure 2. Morphosyntactic annotation and dependency relations in IMPACT

IMPACT is an integrated Web environment has been designed and implemented to allow for on-the-fly adjustments, enabling users to fine-tune annotation results or modify display preferences. In this way, experts can explore dependency trees, part-of-speech tagging, and syntactic relationships in an intuitive, interactive manner. This Web application (that can also be used in a stand-alone mode) will serve as a valuable tool for linguistic analysis and facilitate research on language contact and change, particularly in the context of Corfioto or similar languages.

The source code of the Web application is constantly updated and made available to the research community. The morphosyntactic annotation has produced until now the complete annotation and validation of 111 sentences in Corfioto and their respective transliterations and translations in English (for a total of 333 sentences). The annotation of the 1310 tokens were revised together with the dependency tree structure. This initial output constitutes the first dataset for Corfioto, consisting of POS-tagging and representing the universal dependencies.

6. Conclusions

The creation of a morphosyntactically annotated corpus of Corfioto serves multiple goals. Besides the urgent need to preserve the rich linguistic heritage of the Corfiot Jews, it will enable a quantitative approach to the analysis of contact-induced phenomena, including infinitival loss and the emergence of Balkan-type complementation. Finally, it will contribute to current goals on the wider representation of endangered and low-resource languages within the fields of computational linguistics, highlighting the joint opportunities that the collaboration between linguists, fieldworkers and computer scientists can bring.

In this paper, we have presented a methodology for the creation of a morphosyntactic annotated corpus of Corfioto and the current Web application named IMPACT for the collection of morphosyntactic annotations for the analysis of variation and change in the complementation of Corfioto. The steps for the implementation of the annotation process focus on integrating a Universal Dependency (UD) parser for the tagging of morphosyntactic features of Corfioto, or similar varieties, in order to keep this resource up-to-date with the current state of the art in linguistic annotation, make annotation guidelines available as language change occurs, and make this resource available for training syntactic parser with new data.

An additional step will be publishing linguistic data in accordance with the OntoLex-Lemon paradigm.¹⁰ This represents a crucial step in ensuring the interoperability and semantic richness of the data within the broader linguistic and semantic web community. Through this approach, linguistic data, such as morphosyntactic annotations in Corfioto, can be seamlessly integrated into the LOD (Linked Open Data) cloud, enabling researchers and applications to access and utilize the data in a structured and consistent manner. Ongoing work for the implementation of step 7 of the methodology will include a mapping of the tabular morphosyntactic annotation to an RDF one (Chiarcos et al. 2021). The integration of linguistic data into the CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure) framework represents a strategic step for ensuring that the linguistic dataset, annotated in accordance with the OntoLex-Lemon paradigm, becomes an integral part of a broader research infrastructure.

Bibliography

- Aboh, Enoch. 2020. “Lessons From Neuro-(a)-Typical Brains: Universal Multilingualism, Code-Mixing, Recombination, and Executive Functions.” *Frontiers in Psychology* 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00488>.
- . forthcoming. “Contact as the Norm: A Generative Approach.” In *The Cambridge Handbook of Minimalism*, edited by Kleantes Grohmann and Evelina Leivada. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Adamou, Evangelia. 2016. *A Corpus-Driven Approach to Language Contact*. Language Contact & Bilingualism. Boston/Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- . 2019. “52. Corpus Linguistic Methods.” In *Language Contact. An International Handbook. Volume 1*, edited by Jeroen Darquennes, Joseph Salmons, and Wim Vandenburgsche, 638–53. De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110435351-052>.
- . 2021. *The Adaptive Bilingual Mind*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108884266>.
- . 2024. *Endangered Languages*. Cambridge MA: MIT Press.
- Adamou, Evangelia, and Yaron Matras. 2021. *Routledge Handbook of Language Contact*. Oxon/New York: Routledge.
- Aikhenvald, Alexandra. 2020. “Language Contact and Endangered Languages.” In *The Oxford Handbook of Language Contact*, edited by Anthony Grant. Oxford University Press.
- Anastasopoulos, Antonios. 2019. “Computational Tools for Endangered Language Documentation.” Notre Dame, Indiana: University of Notre Dame.
- Anastasopoulos, Antonios, Christopher Cox, Hilaria Cruz, and Graham Neubig. 2020. “Endangered Languages Meet Modern NLP.” In *Proceedings of the 28th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: Tutorial Abstracts*, 39–45. Barcelona, Spain (online).
- Berez-Kroeker, Andrea, Shirley Gabber, and Aliya Slayton. 2023. “Recent Advances in Technologies for Resource Creation and Mobilization in Language Documentation.” *Annual Review of Linguistics* 9:195–214.
- Bidese, Ermenegildo. 2017. “Reassessing Contact Linguistics: Signposts Towards an Explanatory Approach to Language Contact.” *Zeitschrift Für Dialektologie Und Linguistik* 84 (2/3): 126–51.

¹⁰ <https://www.w3.org/2019/09/lexicog/> [last access on 14/11/2024]

- Bidese, Ermenegildo. 2023. *Sprachkontakt Generativ: Eine Untersuchung Kontaktbedingten Syntaktischen Wandels Im Zimbrischen*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110765014>.
- Brenzinger, Matthias, Arienne Dwyer, Tjeerd de Graaf, Colette Grinevald, Michael Krauss, Osahito Miyaoka, Nicholas Ostler, et al. 2003. *Language Vitality and Endangerment*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Chiaros, Christian, Maxim Ionov, Luis Glaser, and Christian Fäth. 2021. “An Ontology for CoNLL-RDF: Formal Data Structures for TSV Formats in Language Technology.” In *3rd Conference on Language, Data and Knowledge (LDK 2021)*, edited by Dagmar Gromann, Gilles Sérasset, Thierry Declerck, John P. McCrae, Julia Bosque-Gil, Fernando Bobillo, and Barbara Heinisch, 93:20:1-20:14. Open Access Series in Informatics (OASISs). Schloss Dagstuhl-Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik, Dagstuhl Publishing.
- Colafemmina, Cesare. 2006. “Armando Perotti e Gli Ebrei Pugliesi Di Corfù.” In *Sulle Orme Di Armando Perotti. Atti Della Giornata Di Studio*, edited by C Crapis, B Leddomade, and M Virno, 69–87. Cassano Murge: Armando Perotti e gli ebrei pugliesi di Corfù.
- Cortelazzo, Manlio. 1946. “L’italiano a Corfù. Di Alcuni Recenti Scambi Linguistici Italo-Corfioti.” *Lingua Nostra* 7:66–69.
- . 1947. “Vicende Storiche Della Lingua Italiana a Corfù.” *Lingua Nostra*, no. 8, 44–50.
- . 1948. “Caratteristiche Dell’italiano Parlato a Corfù.” *Lingua Nostra* 9:29–34.
- Friedman, Victor A, and Brian D Joseph. forthcoming. *The Balkan Languages*. Cambridge University Press.
- Galliot, Benjamin, Guillaume Wisniewski, Séverine Guillaum, Guillaume Jacques, and Alexis Michaud. 2022. “Facilitating NLP Specialists’ Access to Language Archive Materials: An Update.” In *Journées Jointes Des Groupements de Recherche Linguistique Informatique, Formelle et de Terrain (LIFT) et Traitement Automatique Des Langues (TAL)*, 109–18. Marseille, France. <https://hal.science/hal-03846839>.
- Gottheil, Richard, and Lazarus Belleli. 2002. “Judaeo-Greek and Judaeo-Italian.” In *Jewish Encyclopedia*, edited by Isidore Singer, 7:310–13. New York: Funk & Wagnalls.
- Grant, Anthony. 2013. “Contact and Language Convergence.” In *The Handbook of Language Contact*, edited by Hickey Raymond, 2nd ed., 113–28. John Wiley and Sons.
- Guibon, Gaël, Marine Courtin, Kim Gerdes, and Bruno Guillaume. 2020. “When Collaborative Treebank Curation Meets Graph Grammars.” In *Proceedings of the Twelfth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference*, 5291–5300. Marseille, France: European Language Resources Association.
- Hale, K, M Krauss, LJ Watahomigie, AY Yamamoto, C Craig, LaVerne Masayesva Jeanne, and Nora C England. 1992. “Endangered Languages.” *Language* 68 (1): 1–42.
- Haugen, Einar. 1953. *The Norwegian Language in America: A Study of Bilingual Behavior*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Himmelman, NP. 1998. “Documentary and Descriptive Linguistics.” *Linguistics* 36:161–95.
- . 2006. “Language Documentation: What It Is and What It Is Good For?” In *Essentials of Language Documentation*, edited by J GipperT, NP Himmelman, and U Mosel, 1–30. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Joseph, Brian D. 1983. *The Synchrony and Diachrony of the Balkan Infinitive: A Study in Areal, General, and Historical Linguistics*. Cambridge. Cambridge Studies in Linguistics, Supplementary Volume. Cambridge University Press.
- Karahóga, Ritván Jusúf, Panagiotis Krimpas, Vivian Stamou, Vasileios Arampatzakis, Dimitrios Karamatskos, Vasileios Sevetlidis, Nikolaos Constantinides, Nikolaos Kokkas, George Pavlidis, and Stella Markantonatou. 2022. “Morphologically Annotated Corpora of Pomak.” In *Proceedings of the Fifth Workshop on the Use of Computational Methods in the Study of Endangered Languages*, 179–86.

- Kik, Alfred, Martin Adamec, Alexandra Y Aikhenvald, Jarmila Bajzekova, Nigel Baro, Claire Bower, Robert Colwell K., et al. 2021. "Language and Ethnobiological Skills Decline Precipitously in Papua New Guinea, the World's Most Linguistically Diverse Nation." *PNAS* 118 (22).
- Levi, L. 1961. "Tradizioni Liturgiche, Musicali e Dialettali a Corfù." *La Rassegna Mensile Di Israel* 27 (1): 20–31.
- Levi, Leo, and Roberto Leydi. 1959. *AELM 24 M Musica Tradizionale Liturgica (Riti Ebraici)*. Istituto Centrale per i Beni Sonori ed Audiovisivi.
- Marneffe, Marie-Catherine de, Christopher D. Manning, Joakim Nivre, and Daniel Zeman. 2021. "Universal Dependencies" 47 (2): 255–308.
- Marneffe, Marie-Catherine de, and Joakim Nivre. 2019. "Dependency Grammar." *Annual Review of Linguistics* 5:197–218.
- Michaud, Alexis, Oliver Adams, T. A Cohn, Graham Neubig, and Séverine Guillaume. 2018. "Integrating Automatic Transcription into the Language Documentation Workflow: Experiments with Na Data and the Persephone Toolkit."
- Millour, Alice, Lorenza Brasile, Alberto Ghia, and Laurent Kevers. 2024. "Aggettivu, Aggitivu o Aghettivu? POS Tagging Corsican Dialects." In *Proceedings of the 2024 Joint International Conference on Computational Linguistics, Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC-COLING 2024)*, 600–608. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL.
- Mišeska-Tomić, Olga. 2006. *Balkan Sprachbund Morpho-Syntactic Features*. Studies in Natural Language and Linguistic Theory. Springer Netherlands.
- Mücke, Johannes. 2019. "Infinitive Reduction in Corfiot Italian: A Case of Areal Convergence?" In *Proceedings of the 5th Patras International Conference of Graduate Students in Linguistics (PICGL5)*, edited by Andreea-Mandalina Balas, Sophia Giannopoulou, and Angeliki Zagoura, 214–38. Patras: University of Patras. https://13090d2d-5e38-4d98-93e7-47a01aa1c4b4.filesusr.com/ugd/69b6b1_13334a5abde14258abecb06fa588cc3e.pdf.
- Mufwene, Salikoko S., and Anna-Maria Escobar. 2022. *The Cambridge Handbook of Language Contact. Population Movement and Language Contact. Volume 1*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Nachtmann, Jenny. 2001. "Italienisch Als Minderheitensprache: Fallbeispiel Korfu." Unpublished Master's Thesis, Freiburg: University of Freiburg.
- O'Shannessy, Carmel. 2011. "Language Contact and Change in Endangered Languages." In *The Cambridge Handbook of Endangered Languages*, edited by Peter K Austin and Julia Sallabank, 78–99. Cambridge Handbook in Language and Linguistics. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Perotti, Armando. 1909. "Ebrei Pugliesi a Corfù." *Corriere Delle Puglie*, June 13, 1909.
- . 1910. "Ebrei Pugliesi a Corfù." *Corriere Delle Puglie*, January 5, 1910.
- Poplack, Shana. 2020. "A Variationist Perspective on Language Contact." In *The Routledge Handbook of Language Contact*, edited by Yaron Matras and Evangelia Adamou. Routledge.
- Seifart, Frank. 2019. "Contact-Induced Change." In *Language Contact: An International Handbook Volume 1*, edited by Jeroen Darquennes, Joseph Salmons, and Wim Vandenbussche, 13–23. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110435351-002>.
- Travis, Catherine, and Torres Cacoullous. 2013. "Making Voices Count: Corpus Compilation in Bilingual Communities." *Australian Journal of Linguistics* 33:170–94. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07268602.2013.814529>.

- Vardakis, Georgios. 2019. "Linguistic Variation in Jewish-Romance and Greek Dialects: A Structural Analysis of the Judeo-Italian Dialect of Corfu." Master's Thesis, Paris: Sorbonne Université.
- . 2021. "A Formal Analysis of Complementation in Corfioto." Unpublished MA Thesis, Padua: Università degli Studi di Padova.
- . 2023. "Documenting Corfioto. Evidence for Contact-Induced Grammaticalisation in a Romance Variety in Contact with Greek." In *Internal and External Causes of Language Change: The Naxos Papers*, edited by Nikolaos Lavidas, Alexander Bergs, Elly van Gelderen, and Ioanna Sitaridou. London: Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-30976-2_9.
- Weinreich, Uriel. 1953. *Languages in Contact: Finding and Problems*. The Hague: Mouton.
- Woodbury, AC. 2011. "Language Documentation." In *The Cambridge Handbook of Endangered Languages*, edited by PK Austin and J Sallbank. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Archiving Textual Corpora: a Workflow and its Metadata

Francesco Gelati (University of Hamburg, ORCID: 0000-0002-6066-1308)

Keywords (EN)

Textual corpora; archiving; metadata; workflows; research data management.

Keywords (DE)

Textkorpora; Archivierung; Metadaten; Workflows; Forschungsdatenmanagement.

Abstract (EN)

The article describes how a textual corpus can be deposited in a data repository for digital archiving purposes. It discusses which metadata standards should be used, and points out to the importance of a data management plan. It highlights how different types of data repositories may structure metadata differently and explains how data archiving and digital preservation apply for textual corpora. Finally, it suggests a workflow for archiving textual corpora.

Abstract (DE)

Dieser Aufsatz beschreibt, wie ein Textkorpus für die digitale Archivierung in einem Datenrepositorium hinterlegt werden kann. Es wird diskutiert, welche Metadatenstandards verwendet werden können, und es wird auf die Bedeutung des Datenmanagementplans hingewiesen. Es wird aufgezeigt, wie Metadaten in Datenrepositorien unterschiedlich strukturiert werden können, und wie Datenarchivierung und digitale Bestanderhaltung auf Textkorpora anwendbar sind. Abschließend wird ein Arbeitsablauf für die Archivierung von Textkorpora vorgeschlagen.

Introduction

This article explores how research data management, and more specifically its phase archiving, applies to textual corpora. It postulates that, if you are a scholar willing to deposit your textual corpus in a data repository, you should handle over: 1) the textual corpus itself; 2) the metadata; 3) the data management plan.

In this article, I shall focus on the nature and quality of metadata and data management plan, and I shall not discuss how a textual corpus should look like (for this, you may consult

e.g. Paquot and Gries 2020). Also, I tried to condense key learnings from the FAIR-data and open science movement with my own experience in digital preservation and long-term digital archiving as well as with the outcomes of the DARIAH workshop “Creating Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages”¹. This article’s main addressees are scholars willing to deposit their textual corpus in a data repository for digital archiving purposes, for it describes which steps they have to undergo. However, its key ideas can hopefully be of interest for digital humanists, data stewards as well as for cultural heritage professionals too.

Metadata

When speaking about archiving data, and more specifically about archiving textual corpora, not only the quality of your data matters, but also of your metadata. Since linguistics is “a discipline where scholars frequently adopt methods associated with the humanities, social sciences, cognitive sciences, and computer science, among other areas” (Good 2022), human readable, machine-actionable metadata is crucial for textual corpora for it states which methods (and which technology) were used from such a very diverse palette; with no such an information, it will be hard for other scholars to understand and to reuse that textual corpus.

Several different categorisations of metadata for research data and digital objects have been proposed (see Haynes 2018, Riley 2017 and Greenberg 2005). Each metadata scheme or application profile has its own strength and weaknesses, its proper level of granularity, its users’ community, so, if you wish to describe in-depth your corpus, it may be preferable to select, on the basis of your data and your research goals, more than one single metadata scheme, say the [Component Metadata Infrastructure](#) (CMDI, discussed below) and the [Dublin Core Metadata Initiative](#). Metadata creation can however also take place seamlessly: when you upload a dataset to a research data repository, you manually create metadata, while the digital tool or service you are using automatically generates additional metadata, e.g. a Persistent Identifier (PI) in the form of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Human-created and automatically-generated metadata are indeed equally important and complement each other when archiving textual corpora.

¹ See the article by Bednarkiewicz, Gelati and Horváth of this volume, which also aims to provide the critical and theoretical background of this writing.

Data Management Plan

Let us first pay attention to the research project from which the textual corpus was created. Each (data-intensive) research project, as well as its outcome, should be documented by means of a Data Management Plan (DMP). A DMP is a human-written, sometimes machine-actionable, handbook which contains “all the information pertaining to the collection, processing, storage, archiving and publication of the research data arising from the project” (Technische Universität Berlin 2025). For it contains *all the information*, its importance cannot be overestimated.

In order to write a DMP, a variety of DMP questionnaires, templates and guidelines have been made available by research institutions as well as by research-funding organisations. Many of them offer a DMP wizard too: the University of Hamburg have e.g. an instance of [RDMO - Research Data Management Organiser](#) to be filled-out online. If you want to write a DMP, but your institution does not have a similar tool, or if you are an independent scholar, you may use a free-for-all tool like the [DMPOnline](#) powered by the [Digital Curation Centre - DCC](#) or [Argos](#) made available by [OpenAIRE](#) and [EUDAT](#).

If a funding organisation finances your research project, you very probably have to use its DMP template: this is the case for e.g. the [European Research Council](#). Most DMP templates dedicate an entire section to data archiving. Two central questions apply to textual corpora:

- 1- in which file format(s) the data should be saved, and
- 2- how the data should be stored and backed-up.

They will be both briefly discussed hereafter.

1. In which file format(s) should I save my data?

Proprietary file formats (e.g. MS Office DOCX) are to be avoided, for such formats are very likely to be accessible in the long-term only under considerably high time and money efforts (see Purcell 2019, and especially *Chapter 3: Digital Preservation* by B. Lyons). It may occur because of digital obsolescence, or because the owner of the needed software may request in the future very expensive licenses. Files written in proprietary formats “should be converted to open file formats, and the loss of information caused by this transformation should be regarded as the lesser evil” (Tóth-Czifra et al. 2023, *Subchapter 3.6: Long-term archiving*) compared to a possible complete inaccessibility. Even more beneficial would be to work from the very beginning with open-source file formats. Many text formats (e.g. TXT, ODT, PDF/A) are open-source.

All file formats which are widely-used in the digital humanities for structured data (e.g. XML, JSON, Python, R) and for audio recordings (MP3, FLAC, ALAC, WAV/Wave) are open-source, with one exception: WAV/Wave is rather a proprietary format, but it is not subject to any license or patent claims². Textual corpora made out of web-pages, i.e. web-corpora, represent a separate category. They should be saved in the open-source format WARC, for WARC is the [ISO standard for web-archives](#). If every element of the corpus is already stored on a freely-accessible web-archive (e.g. the [Internet Archive Wayback Machine](#)), you can save only the PIs in a text file.

2. How do I store and back-up my data?

While you are creating and working on your corpus, you should regularly do back-ups and store them. In order to make sure that you are always working on the latest version of your data, you should utilise a Git, i.e. a distributed version control system that tracks versions of files. If you use a web-based Git³ application, like GitLab or GitHub, and if appropriate user's rights management reduces the risk of irreversible data deletion, back-ups can be created less frequently, but are still recommended. If you store your back-up copies on your institution's data cloud facility, and regularly update them, your data is secured, as long as your IT department adopt a good risk management strategy. If you have no institutional affiliation, you can still use free-for-researchers cloud-storage and back-up services offered by research infrastructures, like the [ownCloud instance of DARIAH-DE](#) or [B2Drop](#) by EUDAT. In all cases, it is recommended to store one copy of your data offline, so that you can retrieve your data even in case of a cyber-security attack or any other disaster.

Data Repositories

As Andreassen (2022) perfectly summarised, “when we write research papers, we do not haphazardly select the journal to which we submit”, so “you should be equally critical when selecting a data repository”. As highlighted in the following paragraphs, textual corpus can be archived in three different types of data repositories:

² See: <https://kost-ceco.ch/>. For a concise but useful introduction to recommended file formats for textual corpora, see Mattern (2022).

³ About working with Git, see the short course “Git Collaboration” by Omar Siam (<https://campus.dariah.eu/resources/hosted/git-collaboration>) and the MOOC “Let's Git - Versionsverwaltung und OpenSource” by Caterina Mandel et al. (<https://open.hpi.de/courses/git2020>).

- 1- in data repositories conceived for linguistic data, like the CLARIN B-centres, which offer the highest disciplinary expertise;
- 2- in data repositories for social sciences and humanities, whose options and functionalities are conceived for humanities data, so that not all of them are relevant or applicable to textual corpora;
- 3- in discipline-agnostic data repositories, whose metadata schemes are broad enough to be applicable to very different types of data.

Each category will be briefly discussed hereafter.

1. CLARIN B-Centres

Since 2012, CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure) has been a European Research Infrastructure, just like DARIAH. It provides access to a broad range of language data and advanced tools with which to explore, analyse or combine these datasets. It is the knowledge hub for digitally-enhanced research in linguistics, including corpora linguistics⁴.

In CLARIN's distributed network you may find both Knowledge Centres (CLARIN K Centres), which share their knowledge and expertise in a given domain (e.g. in a single language or language family), and CLARIN-B data centres (B-Centres), which storage and give access to resources. If you are a scholar looking for a data repository for your textual corpus, then should a B-Centre be your first address, so that you and your data can take advantage of CLARIN expertise. B-Centres can be found in 16 European countries: see the [list of all B-Centres](#).

Data repositories at B-Centres apply the Component Metadata Infrastructure, which is the most exhaustive and precise metadata standard for textual corpora (see Odebrecht 2018, p.99, and Windhouwer and Goosen 2022). If you deposit your corpus within a CLARIN-B certified data centre, CMDI will be generated and transmitted to CLARIN's central discovery portal, the [Virtual Language Observatory](#). This will ensure your corpus a greater visibility. Most of B-Centres apply one or more metadata schemes additionally: the [CLARIN-LV repository](#), an excellent example of a data repository devoted to an under-resourced language, uses for instance a qualified Dublin Core Metadata Element Set (see Odebrecht 2018, p.97), where

⁴ About CLARIN, see: Fišer and Witt 2022.

refinements describe more precisely what the metadatum refers to. In the [entry 20.500.12574/108](https://repository.clarin.lv/repository/xmlui/handle/20.500.12574/108)⁵ we encounter three different types of dates: date of accession, date of availability, date of issue, all of them clearly identified thanks to qualifiers. This is a relevant information gain compared to the Dublin Core Metadata Element Set in its basic version, where the metadatum “data” is not further specified.

2. Data Repositories for Social Sciences and Humanities

Even though the network of B-Centres is highly diffused, you might sometimes have difficulties to find one that is relevant for you and your corpus. The [Instituut voor de Nederlandse Taal](#) (Dutch Language Institute) is for instance Belgium’s only B-Centre. Should you be based in Belgium, but should your corpus not be eligible from a content perspective (e.g., the language of the corpus is not Dutch), then you should broaden your search and look for data repositories for all social sciences and humanities, like [SODHA](#), Belgium’s Social Sciences and Digital Humanities Archive.

More data repositories for social sciences and humanities can be found on [Re3Data](#), the ultimate catalogue of all research data repositories, and on the [SSH Open Marketplace](#), the portal listing all digital resources in the social sciences and humanities.

3. Discipline-agnostic Data Repositories

You may also choose to deposit your corpus in the institutional, discipline-agnostic research data repository (RDR) of your institution. The University of Hamburg RDR, for instance, hosts [speech corpora](#), mainly from indigenous North-Eurasian languages, received by the Hamburger Zentrum für Sprachkorpora.

Moreover, a freely accessible, discipline-agnostic and inter-institutional data repository like [Zenodo](#)⁶ can be a practical option too, especially for independent scholars or for small research centres. Indeed, textual and speech corpora from under-resourced languages can be found in Zenodo; for instance the datasets produced by the Athena Research Center Institute of Language and Speech Processing (ILSP) are listed under the [institution’s Zenodo community](#).

⁵ Full URL and URI: <https://repository.clarin.lv/repository/xmlui/handle/20.500.12574/108>.

⁶ About Zenodo and its use, see: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/tool-or-service/SA186o>.

In all discipline-agnostic RDRs, metadata schemes are quite concise and focus on licensing, intellectual property and accessibility, rather than on descriptive, structural and technical metadata. In fact, the set of obligatory metadata fields in repositories ensures discoverability and legal clarity, but often falls short of ensuring deeper scholarly reuse because they lack essential discipline-specific context. This tension between minimal, discipline-agnostic metadata requirements and rich, discipline-specific information can be solved by combining different sources of information.

Firstly, it is crucial from a FAIR-data and Open-Science perspective that a CMDI metadata file in its XML (or JSON) specification is archived in the RDR (together with the textual corpus and the DMP). Secondly, country- or category-specific metadata, which may be found in guidelines issued by a given scientific organization or by a specific community, should be provided too for the sake of completeness: for Germany, the *Empfehlungen zu datentechnischen Standards und Tools bei der Erhebung von Sprachkorpora* issued by the German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft - DFG); for web-corpora, the metadata specification to be found in Dooley and Bowers (2018).

The combination of RDR obligatory metadata, DMP, CMDI and country- or category-specific metadata provides exhaustive information, and ensures that state-of-the-art metadata is both human-readable and machine-actionable.

Digital Preservation

Data archiving is consensually supposed to last 10 years after the end of your research project: two of many possible examples of this practice are to be found in the German Research Foundation [Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice](#) (p.20) and in the article by Sbeih et al. (2020, p.6) describing the RDR [Data Inra](#). In such a time-span, your research will be reproducible thanks to the data packages you archived, either in a CLARIN B-Centre or in another repository.

Later on, concerns will arise. In fact, while the [DOI Foundation](#) keeps only track of the URL/URI (i.e., web-address) of a resource, but it does not host or preserve it. In order that your data packages will be accessible in the long term, all CLARIN B-Centres are required both to obtain the [CoreTrustSeal](#), which certify that an institution fulfil a list of [requirements](#) ensuring the long-term disposal of archived data, and to [re-certify](#) in regular intervals by means of an assessment procedure led by the CLARIN [Technical Centres Assessment Committee](#) (TCAC).

The CoreTrustSeal also commit them to perform active digital preservation, which will make the data reusable in the future.

Just like paper preservation means that e.g. a precious book should be constantly monitored by the library staff and, when needed, cleaned or restored, bitstreams must regularly undergo digital preservation actions. These may include measurements (e.g. calculating the checksum of a digital object), migration (e.g. file-format transformation), emulation (development of new software for accessing the bitstream), storage and risk management operations⁷.

Suggested Workflow

Bearing all this in mind, this article proposes a five-step workflow for archiving textual corpora:

1. Decide where to deposit your corpus;
2. Get from the data repository their requirements concerning file formats;
3. If necessary, migrate your corpus and your metadata to accepted, open-source file formats;
4. Check and improve your metadata and your DMP;
5. Deposit corpus, metadata and DMP.

The workflow can be consulted on the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace under the URL <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/gDzIoY>.

Conclusion

Further research would be necessary in order to determine pros and contras of the suggested workflow. It would be of particular interest to see whether one or more steps can be performed by AI (Artificial Intelligence) enhanced tools, with which results, and at which costs (pecuniary and non-pecuniary, the latter referring to concerns about data protection and intellectual property compliance in many Large Language Models).

Funding

This article and the related workflow result from the research project “Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages”. The project was conceived by

⁷ On the importance of digital preservation in digital arts and humanities, see Corrado and Moulaison Sandy 2017.

DARIAH Working Groups *Research Data Management* and *Multilingual DH* and financed by the DARIAH-ERIC Funding Scheme for Working Group Activities 2023-25. The subsequent grant was administered by the University of Hamburg. Lead applicant was Francesco Gelati (he/him). Co-applicants were Alíz Horváth and Maroussia Bednarkiewicz.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank all participants of the workshop “Creating, Managing and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-resourced Languages”, and especially Alexander König, for their contributions and suggestions. This article highly benefitted from the reviewers’ very helpful comments when it was submitted to *Transformations: A DARIAH Journal*.

Bibliography

Andreassen, Helene N. ‘Archiving Research Data’. In *The Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management*, edited by Andrea L. Berez-Kroeker, Bradley McDonnell, Eve Koller, and Lauren B. Collister, 89–100. The MIT Press, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12200.003.0011>.

Bednarkiewicz, Maroussia, Francesco Gelati, and Alíz Horváth, ‘Creating Workflows for Building, Managing, and Archiving Textual Corpora in Under-Resourced Languages: Challenges, Approaches, and Lessons Learned’, preprint published on 14 November 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14166370>.

Corrado, Edward M., and Heather Moulaison Sandy. *Digital Preservation for Libraries, Archives, and Museums*. Second edition. Lanham, Maryland: Rowman & Littlefield, 2017.

Dooley, Jackie, and Kate Bowers. ‘Descriptive Metadata for Web Archiving: Recommendations of the OCLC Research Library Partnership Web Archiving Metadata Working Group’, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.25333/C3005C>.

Fišer, Darja, and Andreas Witt, eds. *CLARIN: The Infrastructure for Language Resources*. Berlin-Boston: De Gruyter, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110767377>.

Good, Jeff. ‘The Scope of Linguistic Data’. In *The Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management*, edited by Andrea L. Berez-Kroeker, Bradley McDonnell, Eve Koller, and Lauren B. Collister, 27–48. The MIT Press, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12200.003.0007>.

Greenberg, Jane. ‘Understanding Metadata and Metadata Schemes’. *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly* 40, no. 3–4 (9 September 2005): 17–36. https://doi.org/10.1300/J104v40n03_02.

Haynes, David. *Metadata for Information Management and Retrieval: Understanding Metadata and Its Use*. 1st ed. Facet, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.29085/9781783302161>.

Mattern, Eleanor. 'The Linguistic Data Life Cycle, Sustainability of Data, and Principles of Solid Data Management'. In *The Open Handbook of Linguistic Data Management*, edited by Andrea L. Berez-Kroeker, Bradley McDonnell, Eve Koller, and Lauren B. Collister, 61–72. The MIT Press, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12200.003.0009>.

Odebrecht, Carolin. 'MKM – ein Metamodell für Korpusmetadaten: Dokumentation und Wiederverwendung historischer Korpora'. Berlin: Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, 2018. <https://edoc.hu-berlin.de/handle/18452/20173>.

Paquot, Magali, and Stefan Thomas Gries. *A Practical Handbook of Corpus Linguistics*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2020.

Purcell, Aaron D., ed. *The Digital Archives Handbook: A Guide to Creation, Management, and Preservation*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2019.

Riley, Jenn. *Understanding Metadata: What Is Metadata, and What Is It For?* Baltimore: National Information Standards Organization, 2017. <https://www.niso.org/publications/understanding-metadata-2017>.

Sbeih, Lina, Fanny Dedet, Patrick Moreau, and Esther Dzale. 'L'archivage des données de la recherche à l'Inra. Éléments de réflexion, démarche et perspectives'. *Cahier des Techniques de l'INRA, Numéro Spécial Données de la Recherche*, 4 April 2020. <https://hal.inrae.fr/hal-02861909>.

Technische Universität Berlin, 'Service Center Research Data Management (SZF)', 20 March 2025, <https://www.tu.berlin/en/ub/szf>.

Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet, Marta Błaszczczyńska, Francesco Gelati, Femmy Admiraal, Mirjam Blümm, Erik Buelinckx, Vera Chiquet, et al. 'Research Data Management for Arts and Humanities: Integrating Voices of the Community'. DARIAH, 30 August 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8059626>.

Windhouwer, Menzo, and Twan Goosen. 'Component Metadata Infrastructure'. In *CLARIN: The Infrastructure for Language Resources*, edited by Darja Fišer and Andreas Witt, 191–222. Berlin-Boston: De Gruyter, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110767377-008>.